

Conference reader

Second Workshop on Computational
Drama Analysis: Achievements and
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Editorial note

This reader compiles contributions accepted for presentation at the Second Workshop on Computational Drama Analysis: Achievements and Opportunities, held on 3 September 2025 at the Freie Universität Berlin as part of the DraCor Summit 2025 (<https://summit.dracor.org>).

The texts are made available in advance both to facilitate informed discussion during the workshop and to provide authors with a citable preprint version of their work. Please note that these contributions have not been copy-edited nor peer-reviewed yet. They represent an early stage of research and are expected to be further developed in response to the outcomes of the workshop discussions.

Mapping the Dramaturgical Arc: Computational Approaches to Shakespeare

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Abstract

The concept of the narrative arc fundamentally shapes how we understand stories, yet it lacks a clear definition. In computational literary studies, different methodological approaches uncover different arcs. This study argues that the most fruitful interpretations of literary texts emerge when such approaches are combined and considered in relation to one another. Drawing on Shakespeare's plays, I examine the temporal evolution of formal features and sentence-level sentiment, along with the frequency of words from clearly defined semantic and grammatical categories. Narrative arcs plotted according to diverse criteria not only enrich the interpretation of individual texts but also illuminate significant differences and similarities across genres. Furthermore, this also demonstrates how narratological concepts commonly applied to fiction can also be adapted to the investigation of drama.

The analysis begins with genre-specific trends in the density of character networks: Shakespeare's comedies tend to form increasingly dense relationships, while tragedies and histories more often portray disintegrating communities. In the next step, although character networks evolve differently, sentiment analysis shows that many plays follow a broadly similar dramaturgical pattern: rising tension and misfortune, resolved only at the conclusion. However, histories often diverge: despite political collapse, they frequently maintain a sense of community and social order. Moreover, while comedies and tragedies commonly portray repeated misfortunes, histories tend to chart the ascent of a central character, resulting in distinct sentiment trajectories. In comedies, the communities that emerge not only resist overt manipulation and foster public discourse but also operate as subtle instruments of normalization and control à la Foucault. Underlying linguistic patterns—including shifts in pronouns, determiners, words describing motion or sexuality, and conditional language—reflect and reinforce this dynamic.

Keywords

narrative arc, character network, sentiment analysis, power mechanism, community structures

1. Introduction

Studying narrative arcs allows us to analyze how stories are told. By visualizing them, we can identify archetypal patterns across narratives [1], examine their effects on readers [2, pp. 19–21], explore the rhetorical foundations of success [3], and investigate the cognitive mechanisms underlying storytelling [4]. Moreover, by presenting plot structure from a particular perspective, arcs strongly influence how we think about both literature and history [5]. This is true in two respects: first, although this visual form has never been the only way to understand plot development, it has by now become so familiar as if it were a natural property of narratives. On the other hand, arcs can be constructed along various dimensions, each emphasizing different features of a text.

The question of plot structure has been central in textual scholarship since Aristotle's *Poetics*. However, in ancient literature plot was often conceived as a simple succession of episodes [6, VII], [7] and just from the late 18th century onward, the ideas of progress and decline began to shape the conceptualization of plot according to graphical models—closely tied to the new invention of time-series graphs [5]. The narrative arc, then, is not an objective or self-evident property of a text but a visual metaphor that frames and shapes how we perceive stories and history in general. It draws attention to shifts in intensity of stories and to the overall shape of the narrative trajectory, typically understood as a linear trend. A paradigmatic example is Gustav Freytag's pyramid, which diagrams the fate of tragic heroes through the stages of rise, climax, fall, and catastrophe/resolution [8]. Later and equally popular

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models—for example Kurt Vonnegut’s story shapes [9]—reinforce this visual and conceptual tradition (see also [10]), such as creative writing courses on literature and film (see e.g. “plot graph” in [11, p. 63, 76]). These models are so deeply embedded in our thinking that it becomes difficult to imagine alternative approaches to plot construction.

At the same time, what exactly we mean by narrative arc is not straightforward. This is especially clear in the various attempts within computational literary studies (CLS) to operationalize the concept by reducing it to measurable textual elements. The diversity of methods—tracking changes in theme [12, 13], sentiment or emotion [2], or form—highlights the challenge of clearly defining the term. As Konle and Jannidis point out, the concept of “plot” as used in CLS often bears only a vague resemblance to how it is understood in literary studies and beyond [14]. Since I will also attempt to measure and automatically represent narrative arcs in the following, it is worth outlining the assumptions that various approaches entail (section 2). In principle, I believe that different methods can reveal different aspects of a text, and that combining multiple approaches is the most productive path toward a more detailed critical perspective.

In section 3, I will investigate and interpret different approaches to narrative arcs in Shakespearean plays. Although the narratological analysis of drama has traditionally been viewed as problematic—since plays do not narrate but rather present sequences of events (see the argumentation in [15])—I follow Monika Fludernik’s claim that drama is “the most important narrative genre whose narrativity needs to be documented” [16, p. 348]. Consider, for instance, that foundational Aristotelian categories are derived from plays rather than other forms of narrative fiction. Like all narratives, drama involves the selection and ordering of events into causal and temporal sequences [17, p. 40], and the arcs of the presented stories can therefore be analyzed accordingly. This approach also aligns with a well-established tradition in Shakespeare studies that focuses on the narrative analysis of the plays [18, 17].

The arcs revealed will be used to examine the specific dramaturgy of individual texts—much like Elkins’ concept of “middle reading” [2, p. 11]—and to identify structural differences among tragedies, comedies, and histories. Intuitively, we might expect these genres—particularly comedies versus tragedies and histories—to follow distinct plot trajectories, a contrast that should be reflected in their narrative arcs. If this proves to be the case, it supports the validity of the method; but it may be equally revealing if different types of stories share similar underlying structures when viewed from a particular perspective.

2. Related Work

There are two main strands of research within CLS that attempt to quantify the narrative arc: those focusing on linguistic-semantic changes and those examining formal changes. Semantic approaches can themselves be further subdivided. One line of inquiry investigates thematic shifts in a text using methods such as word or document embeddings and topic modeling. These techniques can reveal how rapidly a text transitions between topics, the semantic distance of those shifts, and the degree of circularity in the narrative structure [13]. This category also includes Benjamin Schmidt’s [12] observation that many narrative texts exhibit a semantic progression: from spatial terms toward language associated with apology, truthfulness, reconciliation, and promise.

Another line of semantic analysis involves tracking the temporal distribution of predefined word groups—as opposed to those generated through text mining techniques such as topic modeling. For instance, Boyd et al. [4] examine the roles of function words and cognitive verbs in shaping narrative development. They chart texts along three dimensions: scene setting, plot unfolding, and cognitive tension. According to their findings, English-language stories typically begin with a high frequency of articles and prepositions, which serve to establish characters, locations, and relational context. As the narrative progresses, these are increasingly replaced by pronouns, auxiliaries, negations, and conjunctions. Toward the end, a rise in mental-state verbs (e.g., *think*, *believe*, *understand*) signals heightened cognitive tension and reflection. A methodologically similar approach to this study is taken in subsection 3.2.

One of the most popular and widely used methods for identifying semantic variation through specific word groups is the analysis of changes of sentiment in texts. This approach is based on the assumption that fluctuations in emotional tone across a narrative correlate with changes in tension and in the fate of the heroes. This can be inferred from the distribution of words expressing positive or negative sentiments (or categorized along similar dimensions, such as “power” and “danger”; see [19]). The validity of this approach is supported by Reagan et al. [1], who successfully identified six narrative archetypes using sentiment analysis: ‘Rags to Riches’ (rise); ‘Tragedy’ or ‘Riches to Rags’ (fall); ‘Man in a Hole’ (fall–rise); ‘Icarus’ (rise–fall); ‘Cinderella’ (rise–fall–rise); and ‘Oedipus’ (fall–rise–fall).

It is worth noting that the quantification and visualization of dramatic tension was already explored in Iván and Judit Fónagy’s 1971 work. Their method is highly creative, though far from methodologically robust: the degree of tension is inferred from the number of answered and unanswered plot-related questions. In *Hamlet*, for instance, they suggest that the first scene raises the following questions: “Did the soldiers really see Hamlet’s father’s ghost? Will the ghost speak to Hamlet? Will Fortinbras attack Denmark?, etc” [20, p. 74.]. They charted the dramaturgical arc of each play by counting the unresolved and newly emerged questions in each scene (see examples in Appendix C). This procedure is inherently subjective and cannot be formalized in a way suitable for algorithmic analysis. For this reason, computational drama analysis often relies instead on sentiment-based approaches. However, it is important to recognize that the frequency of positive and negative words can also, at best, only indirectly reflect the development of narrative tension.

Sentiment fluctuations can be analyzed—among others—using Matthew Jockers’ R package, *syuzhet*; a name that reflects the focus on the discourse level, i.e., how the story is told [21]. The package assigns a sentiment value to each sentence based on a dictionary: the more positive words a sentence contains, the higher its score; the more negative words, the lower it is. These consecutive values are then smoothed to produce a narrative arc. (For an overview of smoothing techniques used both within and beyond the package, see [2, p. 12–14].) Although the method, particularly in its earlier versions, has been controversial (see [22]), it has sparked significant discussion in the research community (e.g., [23]). Questions surrounding its validity, usability, and comparison with alternative methods are addressed in Katherine Elkins’ *The Shape of Stories* [2], where she argues that sentiment-based investigation remains one of the most effective ways for identifying structural patterns in narrative development. In computational drama analysis, no comprehensive study has yet been published on the sentiment arcs of entire plays. Instead, existing research has primarily focused on changes in emotion within individual characters’ speeches in Shakespearean drama [24]. The present study therefore has a special focus on the application of the method in dramatic texts as wholes (see subsection 3.1).

In the context of sentiment analysis, it is also worth noting the study by Kim, Padó, and Klinger [25], which demonstrates that emotional content can provide useful information for distinguishing between novelistic genres. Their analysis also explores how emotions are distributed across texts and what kinds of emotional arcs emerge. However, their findings show that these arcs can only be used to a limited extent for genre classification. The present study pursues a similar aim, but within the context of drama rather than prose fiction.

Another approach is to focus not on changes in word groups or topics—that is, not on semantic components—but rather on formal changes in a text. Prose fiction has received relatively little attention from this perspective so far.¹ In contrast, computational drama analysis often examines the formal structure of plays mostly through the study of character networks. This can also be done from a dynamic perspective; that is, by analyzing how networks and other formal aspects evolve over the course of a play. To capture the temporality of plot development, Fischer et al., for example, investigate

¹A possible method involves analyzing trends in sentence length throughout a narrative. In Imre Kertész’s Nobel Prize-winning novel *Fatelessness* (*Sorstalanság*), for instance, fluctuations in sentence length appear to reflect the development of the story. The early sections are marked by shorter (but not very short), diary-like sentences. As the narrative progresses—particularly during the deportation—sentences become gradually longer and more complex, peaking in Chapter 7, which is set in the hospital of the camp. Following the protagonist’s return home, shorter sentence units reemerge. This shift in sentence structure reflects not only the rhetorical composition of the novel but also the increasingly saturated, sensory language used to portray life in the concentration camp (see [26, p. 144–145])

Figure 1: Changes in the median of density in five-act plays – ShakeDraCor

the process of “progressive structuration” using both event-based and progression-based measures [27]. An event-based approach might involve identifying the point at which all characters have appeared on stage, while a progression-based measure could track the dynamic change between scenes—such as the ratio of new or departing characters relative to the total number of characters in the scenes.

Szemes and Nagy [28] have investigated the temporal evolution of character networks by conducting a cumulative analysis of network density and average clustering coefficient across five-act comedies and tragedies in the German (2022 version) and Shakespeare sub-collections of Drama Corpus Project [29]. The cumulative method involves calculating a network metric incrementally: first for Act I, then for Acts I–II, then for Acts I–III, and so on, until a final measure representing the entire five-act structure is obtained. In the present context, the findings on network density are particularly significant. Figure 1 shows the median values for Shakespearean texts, grouped into comedies and all other plays (as tragedies and histories exhibit similar patterns in this respect). The analysis of GerDraCor yields a similar graph [28], as do the updated 2025 version of the corpus and the French collection.²

An analysis of these data—along with the graphs of prototypical comedies and tragedies—suggests that the character networks of different dramatic genres evolve in distinct ways. Specifically, comic plots tend to be characterized by the formation of increasingly dense character communities, whereas tragic plots show a pattern of gradual network disintegration. In tragedies, this disintegration is not merely a consequence of the tragic ending; rather, it is the breakdown of the social network itself that precipitates the tragic conclusion. Conversely, comedies follow a cumulative process of community-building, often culminating in a climactic mass scene of resolution [28]. These findings already provide a basis for describing the narrative arc of dramatic texts from a structural perspective, while also highlighting key differences between genres. In the following sections, I compare these results with other approaches focusing on word usage, using the insights gained here to contextualize the outcome of language-based analysis.

²Only including five-act tragedies and comedies with more than 2 scenes and more than 5 characters. The updated results have not yet been published, only presented in the *Tragic Forms Across Europe and Beyond* conference in Sibiu, July 2-3, 2025.

3. Analysis

3.1. Sentiment Arc

In the study of narrative arcs, it is not without precedent to turn to the dramas of Shakespeare: *Romeo and Juliet* has played a central role in the debate surrounding the *syuzhet* package. Ted Underwood, for example, compared the sentiment arc of the play generated by *syuzhet* (see Fig. 2) with annotations produced by human readers (the plot was provided by David Bamman) and found a high degree of similarity[23]. One of Underwood's more widely accepted arguments for the method's validity is that the genre of *Romeo and Juliet* helps explain the arc's shape: the steadily declining emotional trend aligns well with the tragic plot. He also notes that such alignment is harder to achieve when analyzing novels, as they often lack a clearly defined emotional trajectory like some dramatic texts. Elkins supports this view about the play, writing that "tragedy conforms to a typical structure" [2, p. 4]; however, she also observes—without presenting the data or discussing this observation in detail—that "some of Shakespeare's plays that we typically categorize as tragedies do not exhibit a typical tragic shape" [p. 12]. In this section, I will examine whether different genres of Shakespearean plays consistently follow distinct sentiment—and thus narrative—arcs, or whether the different plots driven by the (mis)fortunes of the protagonists resist detection through such sentiment-based analysis.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 present the results generated by the *syuzhet* package using different smoothing techniques. Elkins's suspicion appears to be confirmed—not only because some tragedies fail to exhibit a uniform downward trend (since this pattern does hold for many, such as *Othello*, where increasingly dark themes gradually dominate the narrative), but more strikingly because most comedies also display a growing prevalence of negative sentiment as the plot unfolds. This includes *All's Well That Ends Well* which—despite its title—follows a sentiment curve we tend to associate with tragedy. This is also true for other comedies, most notably *Measure for Measure*, *Much Ado About Nothing*, *The Comedy of Errors* and *The Merry Wives of Windsor*. This difficulty in distinguishing genres may have two explanations. First, the genres may not differ as sharply in their plot development as commonly assumed. Alternatively, an analysis based on sentiment scores is not adequate to make such a distinction.

Let us first explore the latter possibility that we are facing a methodological problem. Several concerns can be mentioned, each is related to the difference between *sentiment* and *emotion*; i.e. perhaps sentiment analysis is not suitable for identifying emotional changes. First, emotions in drama are not conveyed solely through language; much of their impact is communicated through performance, gesture, and tone, which cannot be captured by text-based sentiment analysis alone. Second, the content of Shakespeare's comedies is often far from uniformly joyful. Aside from their conventionally happy endings, many include dark or troubling themes: *Measure for Measure* involves sexual coercion, Bertram's treatment of Helena in *All's Well That Ends Well* is—to say the least—morally questionable, and *Much Ado About Nothing* even includes a faked death scene reminiscent of *Romeo and Juliet*. Conversely, Shakespeare's tragedies are often interspersed with humorous or playful moments—such as the Gravediggers in *Hamlet* or Mercutio's wordplays in *Romeo and Juliet*.

Third, we must be cautious in projecting contemporary understandings of emotion onto texts from the 16th century. Emotional expression and reception were shaped by different cultural and rhetorical norms. As White and Rawnsley observe, "there is a critical tendency to compartmentalise clearly defined emotional states for the sake of analysis—anger, pity, melancholy, shame and so on—rather than noticing that many states of feeling are transitional or inseparably multiple" [30, p. 241]. Indeed, even the term emotion itself was in flux during Shakespeare's time [31, p. 11]. As another example, Nigel Wood highlights the semantic breadth of the word spleen, noting that "Shakespeare favoured it as comprising a remarkably broad spectrum of meaning, frequently returning to the ungovernable qualities of emotional excess, a state equally amenable to tragic as comic narratives" [32, p. 113]. For this reason, White and Rawnsley advocate for the term mixed emotions as more appropriate for describing Shakespearean drama—an argument they support through readings of, among other examples, *The Two Gentlemen of Verona* [30, pp. 244–245].

If we accept these historical arguments, we cannot interpret the results based on sentiment scores

Figure 2: Sentiment arcs of Shakespeare’s plays using discrete cosine transform (DCT) smoothing. DCT compresses a data series by transforming it into a few frequency components, capturing overall patterns while filtering out detail. Compared to Figure 4, this method applies relatively strong smoothing, retaining only the main tendencies in the data.

as a clear representation of the plays’ emotional changes; yet, as is often the case in text mining, the large volume of data can still reveal certain aspects of the plays. In this case, some regular patterns in the sentiment curves point to broader narrative tendencies that transcend genre distinctions. These regularities show that from a dramatic point of view, there is no strong difference between comedies and tragedies (similarly, there is no difference in the overall frequency of emotion-related words in these genres of Shakespeare – see [33]). Notably, the “low point” in the sentiment curves in Figure 2 and Figure 3, regardless of the genre, frequently occurs between 75% and 80% of the way through the plot, with the initially higher values gradually declining toward this point. While these diagrams may not accurately capture the emotional trajectory of the plays—due to the limitations discussed above—they do appear to reflect a fundamental aspect of narrative structure: the decline in sentiment values may correspond to rising complication and tension within the plot. The average sentiment values by genre (see Figure 4 and Figure 5) indicate that both comedies and tragedies tend to follow a similar narrative arc: a gradual buildup of tension and misfortune of the main characters followed by some kind of resolution. In this sense, the curves echo the core logic of Freytag’s pyramid, albeit inverted—which could easily be corrected by multiplying the values by -1 .

An example of this rising tension is found in *Hamlet*. The sentiment graph shows its highest positive value at the beginning of Act II—particularly in the scenes involving Polonius and Reynaldo (II.1) and the witty exchange between Hamlet, Rosencrantz, and Guildenstern (II.2). In contrast, the lowest point occurs at the beginning of Act V, the gravediggers’ scene. This downward arc may reflect Hamlet’s transformation over the course of the play: from a sharp, playful, and intellectually agile figure to a more withdrawn, brooding character who gradually relinquishes imagination and free play [34]. However, a closer look at the scenes and the sentiment values (see Appendix A) assigned to individual

Figure 3: Sentiment arcs of Shakespeare’s plays using simple moving average (SMA) smoothing. SMA smooths data by averaging neighboring values, helping to highlight local trends. The values were first normalized to the same scale, then smoothed using the moving average method, and finally downsampled to 100 units proportionally across the data.

sentences offers a more nuanced interpretation. Based on these, we can see that as the tension in the play increases, the elements of formulaic courtly speech and deception gradually recede into the background. What Maurice Charney called as “free play” of imagination [34] is not so much as true freedom, but as dissimulation (cf. [35]), a performance of social codes that suppress individual emotion. The graph’s peak in positivity is driven by characters whose speech is marked by exaggerated politeness—such as Polonius, Rosencrantz, Guildenstern in Act II, and later Osrick in Act V. These utterances, filled with deferential language and empty rhetorical flourishes, increase sentiment scores. Notably, some of the most positive passages are those that explicitly discuss or parody this kind of rhetoric—for example, Polonius’s advice to Reynaldo on how to subtly investigate Laertes in Paris,³ or Hamlet’s description of theatrical clichés: “The adventurous/ knight shall use his foil and target, the lover shall/ not sigh gratis, the humorous man shall end his/ part in peace, the clown shall make those laugh/ whose lungs are tickle o’ th’ sear, and the lady/ shall say her mind freely, or the blank verse shall/ halt for ’t.” This latter also reinforces the play’s meta-theatrical dimension, drawing a parallel between courtly and stage performance as versions of dissimulation. Accordingly, the gravedigger scene (even more humorous and witty than the previous episodes!) marks a low point in the sentiment curve because it directly confronts the superficiality of social behavior and exposes the harsh, underlying realities (death).⁴

³„You, laying these slight sullies on my son,/ As ’twere a thing a little soiled i’ th’ working,/ Mark you, your party in converse,/ him you would sound, Having ever seen in the prenominate crimes/ The youth you breathe of guilty, be assured/ He closes with you in this consequence:/ “Good sir,” or so, or “friend,” or “gentleman,” / According to the phrase or the addition/ Of man and country—”

⁴See e.g. Hamlet talking about whose skull is seen in the grave: „Or of a courtier, which could say ‘Good morrow, sweet lord! How dost thou, sweet lord?’ This might be my Lord Such-a-one that praised my Lord Such-a-one’s horse when he went to beg it, might it not? (...) Why may not that be the skull of a lawyer? Where be his quiddities now, his quillities, his cases, his

Figure 4: Mean genre-specific sentiment values (DCT smoothing)

Figure 5: Mean genre-specific sentiment values (SMA smoothing)

All that has been said so far applies only to tragedies and comedies in Shakespeare’s works. While histories have previously aligned closely with tragedies in terms of formal properties—forming a joint category distinct from comedies—they diverge markedly in this case. This distinction is evident in some (but not all) of the individual examples shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 and becomes striking when

tenures, and his tricks? Why does he suffer this mad knave now to knock him about the sconce with a dirty shovel and will not tell him of his action of battery? Hum, this fellow might be in ’s time a great buyer of land, with his statutes, his recognizances, his fines, his double vouchers, his recoveries. Is this the fine of his fines and the recovery of his recoveries, to have his fine pate full of fine dirt?”

examining the mean values of a genre in Figure 4 and Figure 5. Histories follow a different trajectory from the other two genres. When the plays are projected into a two-dimensional space based on their downsampled SMA values (see the PCA plot in Figure 6), we observe a blend of genres, while some histories appear clearly separated; particularly *Richard III*, *Henry VIII*, and both parts of *Henry IV*.

This separation may stem from the fact that, while these plays portray tragedy-like disintegrating communities, they do so through different dramaturgical patterns. In tragedies as well as in comedies, characters are often driven by misfortune, whereas the histories tend to depict the ascent—and eventual triumph or fall—of greatness. In the different sentiment arcs, most notably, the distinct individual destinies are reflected.

At the same time, these differences may also arise from the varying roles that communities play within each genre. In tragedies, as tension builds, social codes and dissimulation tend to break down—as illustrated above in the micro-analysis of *Hamlet*. Characters become increasingly candid about their goals and desires previously hidden behind layers of social performance; or are forced into such exposure by the unfolding plot (beyond *Hamlet*, consider Lady Macbeth’s monologues, which reveal her husband’s crimes). In some histories, by contrast, although dense character networks do not form and society remains fragmented, social norms are preserved—at least in language. For instance, the concept of honor, both in military and moral sense, remains central throughout *Henry IV Parts 1 and 2* (see [36]). These plays depict power struggles within an intact rhetorical and social framework, whereas in tragedies like *Othello*, *King Lear*, and *Macbeth*, the protagonists are often consumed by passion or madness by the end.

Moreover, while histories represent internal conflict within a community, the idea of a community—England—remains a constant, framing the action as part of a shared national fate. In addition to individual destiny, this vision of collective unity—conveyed through appeals to national identity and rhetorical stability—may help explain the upward sentiment trends observed in the arcs.

3.2. Semantic Changes

In this section, following Boyd et al. [4], I investigate whether there are groups of words that form coherent grammatical or semantic units, which occur frequently enough in Shakespeare’s texts to analyze them statistically, and whose changing frequency over the course of the plays—and across genres—reveals interpretable patterns. Based on preliminary experiments, I focus on the following word groups:

1. Definite determiners that help specify nouns and/or anchor meaning in context: *the, this, that, these, those, yon, yonder*.
2. Possessive pronouns: *my, your, his, her, our, their, thy, thine, mine, yours, hers, ours, theirs, its*.
3. Modal verbs, adverbs, conjunctions related to condition and possibility: *can, could, if, may, maybe, might, perhaps, should, unless, would*.
4. Semantic category of ‘Sexuality and Intimate Love’. This group is based on the *Enhanced Shakespearean Corpus* developed by the Encyclopedia of Shakespeare’s Language project, which provides texts from the First Folio annotated with semantic tags using the USAS Semantic Tagset [37]. I extracted all words tagged as S3.2 (‘Relationship: Intimate/sexual’) and then manually cleaned the resulting list to correct for misclassifications—mostly those caused by character names, which had a disproportionate influence on the semi-automated tagging: *bawd, bed, bedfellow, chastity, consummation, copulation, court, doxy, embrace, embraces, embracing, gay, harlotry, hug, kissing, kisses, lechery, lecherous, love, lover, lovers, loves, mate, mated, minx, paramour, paramour, pandar, prostitute, seduce, seduced, seducing, sleeping, spinsters, suitor, sweet-heart, virgin, virgins, wooer, wooers*.
5. Semantic category of ‘Bodily motion’. Also based on the *Enhanced Shakespearean Corpus*; for this group I queried the words with M (‘Movement, Location, Travel and Transport’) tags and then cleaned the list manually: *abroad, barge, base, borne, bring, bring, brings, brought, car, carriages, carry, chariot, cities, come, countries, countrymen, course, depart, dispatch, enter, estate, fall, fell, fetch, flight, fled, fore, follow, followes, forth, forward, fro, go, going, goes, gone, ground, hang,*

Figure 6: PCA plot based on the sequential sentiment values in Shakespeare's plays.

harbours, held, heres, hence, hid, hither, holds, lay, leapt, left, march, meet, met, motion, north, outward, past, passe, place, ports, pound, presence, quick, region, return, rise, run, send, set, shake, ship, sit, sits, stand, stands, stay, steward, still, stood, territory, thence, throw, thrust, top, transport, verges, walked, went, wherein, yielder, yielding, yields, yonder.

For the analysis, I divided the plays into scenes. If a scene contained fewer than 100 words, it was merged with the following scene (or with the preceding one in the case of the final scene). I then calculated the relative frequency of each word group in every scene. To smooth the resulting curves for a play, I calculated the moving average of scores (SMA) with a context window of 4. Finally, the values were standardized using z-score normalization. This procedure is very similar to the sentiment analysis in the previous section, where SMA smoothing was applied. However, in this case, scenes—*not* sentences—serve as the base unit of analysis, due to the smaller size of the semantic lexicons.

The results for each play across the five categories are provided in [Appendix B](#), while the genre-specific values are displayed in [Figure 7](#). For this, since Shakespeare's plays vary significantly in length, I normalized the progression of each play to a common scale (0-1). Then linear interpolation was applied to map each play's SMA trajectory onto a shared sequence of 100 evenly spaced points, effectively standardizing their structure. This process allows us to average over interpolated values across all plays within a genre, producing continuous and comparable genre-level trends. The method preserves each play's full trajectory while enabling cross-play aggregation without distorting temporal structure due to length variation.

What these genre-specific arcs reveal, first and foremost, is that comedies often resemble tragedies in their linguistic and thematic development (histories, in most cases, do not show a consistent trend,

Figure 7: Interpolated SMA values of the five semantic categories by genre.

which makes the presence of such trends in the other genres all the more striking). Clear differences in the interpolated values across genres are observed only in definitive determiners and possessive pronouns. This finding reinforces the results discussed in the previous section: in some semantic fields and their progression, comedies and tragedies do not diverge significantly. Both genres show a gradual marginalization of explicit references to sexuality, a decline in the expression of possibility or conditionality, and a growing emphasis on general bodily movement. Tragedies and comedies thus appear to unfold not only through similar sentiment and dramaturgical structures, but also through comparable patterns in discourse development.

This general observation is qualified by two important considerations. First, genre-level trends might conceal intra-genre variability. It is therefore important to examine individual play trajectories as well (Appendix B). For example, most of the trends in Figure 7 are more clearly pronounced in a larger subset of comedies than tragedies, while a smaller number of comedies displaying opposite tendencies serve to balance out this trend in the average. Second, similar patterns in language use unfold within fundamentally different social contexts. In tragedies, a disintegrating network leaves increasingly little room for intimate contact between characters—many of whom are dead by the end—while the momentum of the plot often drives them into irreversible actions. In contrast, comedies typically culminate in socially cohesive endings and fulfilled romantic unions. Yet, the thematic presence of explicit sexuality diminishes over the course of the plays, and the narrative openness typical of comedies—unlike the fatalism of tragedies—is not accompanied by a corresponding increase in conditional or speculative expressions in character speech.

These processes can be linked to the power dynamics in comic communities. As Joel Fineman observes, Shakespearean comedies encapsulates rather than resolve psychic disturbances of a mainly sexual origin,⁵ in order to establish stable differences between characters and organise them into a

⁵Marta Stranzky speaks about the “absorption and not suppression of subversive behaviors” [38, p. 13] which is a similar—but more positive—formulation to “encapsulate”. However, both means that comedies tame these behaviors (like shrews), incorporating them into a unifying social order.

unified order with externally determined identities [39, pp. 71–72, 82–87]. In other words, individual desires are canalized into a communal structure. The decline in explicit sexual expression can be explained by this normalizing attempt of comedies. Of course, behaviors perceived as deviant from the point of view of the majority society (e.g. homosexuality, gender roles that offend patriarchy, interchangeability of people) are often preserved in dramas; however, they are not explicitly expressed, but through the ambiguity of allusion or wordplay.

Fineman sees conditionality also as an imagined subversion of social order grounded in fixed differences;⁶ the decline of words in the Conditional group may therefore signal again the construction of a normalizing order. Conditional sentences erode stable, bounded identities—however, they do so within hypothetical, protected contexts. In this way, conditionality plays a role both in subversion and taming deviance: it allows imagined transgression without direct consequences. The decreasing use of such expressions, then, suggests not only a stabilizing of identity but also a reduction in even the imaginative space for subversion. That said, conditional phrasing can still carry weight at the end of a drama. For instance, Bertram’s speech at the end of *All’s Well That Ends Well* frames his conversion in conditional terms—“If she, my liege, can make me know this clearly, / I’ll love her dearly, ever, ever dearly” (V.3)—which casts a shadow over the supposed resolution. His use of “if” subtly undermines the unconditional nature expected in a comic conclusion, leaving the ending ambiguous.

What is particularly striking, then, is the tension in comedies between these linguistic tendencies and the plots’ resolutions, which often culminate in dense character networks. It seems that dense relationships and happy endings do not necessarily lead to happy communities (see the previous chapter), in which the chances for diverse opportunities (see category of Condition) and for individuals to fulfill their desires according to their own needs (Sexuality) are increasingly reduced.

This is reinforced by the fact that, in comedies, things and characters become increasingly specified (see the ‘Definitive’ category in Figure 7) and less often described through possession (see ‘Possessive’). Both tendencies relate to the stabilization of identity. Definitive determiners serve to fix meaning, narrowing possible contexts and focusing on the specific rather than the general. Regarding possession, it is worth recalling David Hawkes’s detailed overview of terms like ‘property’ and ‘to possess’ in Shakespeare’s time. Their meanings range from spiritual and sexual possession [40, pp. 167–168] to emerging capitalist notions of property [pp. 165–166] and what Hobbes calls “possessive individualism”—the idea of the individual as the proprietor of their own person or capacities [p. 163]. These connotations all point to the undermining of externally fixed identity. This applies equally to devil possession or sexual deviance, as well as to a market economy based on property, where social relations are not predetermined but constantly evolving through exchange. Similarly, Hobbes’s concept of the individual as “self-owner” reflects a view of identity as self-possessed rather than externally fixed. The observed increase in definitive determiners from the second half of the plays, coupled with a decrease in possessive pronouns from the beginning, may suggest that comedies progress toward normalization, an externally fixed identity, while limiting possibilities and individual desires.

So far in computational drama analysis, the study of character networks has usually leaned toward a Habermasian interpretation: comedies represent “good” communities, where open, multi-directional communication prevents the consolidation of power in the hands of a single individual; tragedies, by contrast, often feature one or two central figures who control or distort the network’s flow of information, enabling manipulation on a grand scale. However, comedies are also not free from manipulation, as the results of this section suggest. Rather than stemming from a dominant individual, as in tragedies, manipulation in comedies often operates as an invisible force of a community. In this context, a Foucauldian framework may be more apt: power is dispersed, anonymous, and productive—manifest not through command but through the regulation of what can be said, done, and desired. The dense networks typical of comedies may thus conceal mechanisms of homogenization and discipline. They

⁶“Correspondingly, complementing the developing transformation of a nurturing mother into a whoring arbitrariness, we find in *Troilus and Cressida* that the ‘If,’ the conditional upon which Shakespeare predicates the fantastic status of his comedies, is articulated only as an indictment of its own hypotheticals. In *As You Like It*, the admission of ‘if’ placed mixed differences, male and female, within protected imaginary space. Even in *Hamlet*, where the ‘if’ is itself imaginary, placed within the frame of a play within the play (...), there is still an almost formulaic reserve about the expression of maternal guilt.”[39, p. 97]

promote consensus and stability but also suppress deviance or resistance. Unlike in tragedies, where heroes often resist this form of normalization—Richard III, for instance, embraces villainy as a refusal to conform. The regulation of bodies and behaviors in comedies may also be reflected linguistically, as seen in the increased use of Motion-related vocabulary (often in the imperative mood: come and go), which could suggest not just action-driven plots but subtle social disciplining.

From this point of view, comedies have a carnivalesque function: the erosion and reinforced restoration of social order (as the Duke returns at the end of *Measure for Measure* – see [41, p. 129]),⁷ in which ideological constructs appear as universal values. “Master and servant, husband and wife may exchange roles in a comedy, but they never escape the tyranny of social roles” [44, p. 140]. The violent nature of this process is best seen at the end of *A Midsummer Night’s Dream*, where, in order for marriages that integrate into the social order to be established, Demetrius must remain under the influence of the external spell. But we can also mention *As You Like It*, following Stephen Greenblatt’s analysis of Rosalind: “We should add that the unique qualities of that identity—those that give Rosalind her independence, her sharply etched individuality—will not, as Shakespeare conceives the play, endure: they are bound up with exile, disguise, and freedom from ordinary constraint, and they will vanish, along with the playful chafing, when the play is done. What begins as a physiological necessity is reimagined as an improvisational self-fashioning that longs for self-effacement and reabsorption in the community.” [43, pp. 90-91]

4. Conclusion

All of this illustrates that the concept of a narrative arc is not absolute; rather, it depends on the analytical perspective from which it is defined and rendered operational. Different methods produce different representations. In this paper, I have argued for a multifaceted approach that integrates various methods to enable more nuanced interpretations. The analysis began with genre-specific trends in character network density, which revealed a clear pattern: Shakespeare’s comedies tend to exhibit increasingly dense networks of relationships, while tragedies and histories often portray the gradual disintegration of communities.

Several important insights emerge from the analysis of changes in sentiment values, which, however, do not fully correspond to emotions as we understand them today. Most notably, many of Shakespeare’s plays follow a similar dramaturgical arc characterized by a steady rise in tension and the misfortune of characters that is only can be resolved in the end of the plays—broadly confirming Freytag’s model of dramatic structure. However, some histories remarkably diverge from this pattern. Unlike tragedies, some histories tend to preserve a general sense of community and adherence to social norms, even amid political and social disintegration. This continuity may help explain the different sentiment arcs in certain plays—such as *Henry VIII* and *Henry IV Parts 1 and 2*—as reflected in the relative decline of explicitly negative language in characters’ dialogue, despite the fact that history is overall the most emotionally negative genre [33]. Furthermore, while tragedies and comedies often revolve around the repeated misfortunes of characters, histories frequently center on the rise of a central figure. This narrative focus on ascent rather than collapse may contribute to their distinct sentiment trajectories.

In tragedies, communal structures are less preserved both in terms of character networks and conceptual coherence. By contrast, in comedies, the emergence of increasingly dense networks can be understood—to a limited extent, as we have seen—as the formation of a “community of being.” Yet the development of such communities is not portrayed as a straightforwardly joyful process. In terms of sentiment values, only the very end of comedies shows a significant divergence from the trajectory of

⁷See also C. L. Barber influential study on the *Twelfth Night*: „Just as the saturnalian reversal of social roles need not threaten the social structure, but can serve instead to consolidate it, so a temporary, playful reversal of sexual roles can renew the meaning of the normal relation. One can add that with sexual as with other relations, it is when the normal is secure that playful aberration is benign” [42, p. 245], and Stephen Greenblatt’s comment: “The concrete individual exists only in relation to forces that pull against spontaneous singularity and that draw any given life, however peculiarly formed, toward communal norms. The concrete individual exists only in relation to forces that pull against spontaneous singularity and that draw any given life, however peculiarly formed, toward communal norms.” [43, p. 75]

tragedies. Like tragic plots, the path toward resolution in comedies is marked by difficulty and tension.

However, the communities that eventually form in comedies not only resist overt manipulation and support a shared public space—where individual speech acts can be validated—but also function as instruments of power. Linguistic patterns underscore this process: the marginalization of non-normative desires and alternatives (indicated by the decline in Sexuality- and Conditionality-related expressions), the stabilization of identities (shown in the increase of Definitive determiners and the decline of Possessive pronouns), and the rise of discourse tied to bodily regulation (reflected in the proliferation of Motion-related terms) all point to a normalizing and disciplining function embedded in comic communities. From this perspective, the tragic hero can be seen as a figure of resistance, standing against these invisible, disciplinary forces, even at the cost of communal disintegration. Unlike the comic characters who submit to the collective order, Shakespeare’s tragic protagonists insist on their singularity, often leading to the collapse of the social fabric around them.

5. Appendices

A. Most positive and negative sentences according to the *syzhet* dictionary around the peak of the sentiment graphs in *Hamlet*

Table 1: Positive sentences at the beginning of Act II

#	Sentence	Score	Speaker
1	And there put on him What forgeries you please — marry, none so rank As may dishonor him, take heed of that, But, sir, such wanton, wild, and usual slips As are companions noted and most known To youth and liberty.	2.20	Polonius
2	You, laying these slight sullies on my son, As ’twere a thing a little soiled i’ th’ working, Mark you, your party in converse, him you would sound, Having ever seen in the prenominate crimes The youth you breathe of guilty, be assured He closes with you in this consequence: ’Good sir,’ or so, or ’friend,’ or ’gentleman,’ According to the phrase or the addition Of man and country — Very good, my lord.	2.70	Polonius
3	At ’closes in the consequence,’ at ’friend, or so,’ and ’gentleman.’	1.80	Reynaldo
4	At ’closes in the consequence’ — ay, marry — He closes thus: ’I know the gentleman.’	1.60	Polonius
5	This is the very ecstasy of love, Whose violent property fordoes itself And leads the will to desperate undertakings As oft as any passions under heaven That does afflict our natures.	1.70	Polonius
6	If it will please you To show us so much gentry and goodwill As to expend your time with us awhile For the supply and profit of our hope, Your visitation shall receive such thanks As fits a king’s remembrance.	2.20	Queen
7	Thanks, Rosencrantz and gentle Guildenstern.	1.60	King
8	Thanks, Guildenstern and gentle Rosencrantz.	1.60	Queen
9	Heavens make our presence and our practices Pleasant and helpful to him!	2.95	Guildenstern
10	I assure my good liege I hold my duty as I hold my soul, Both to my God and to my gracious king, And I do think, or else this brain of mine Hunts not the trail of policy so sure As it hath used to do, that I have found The very cause of Hamlet’s lunacy.	2.45	Polonius

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#	Sentence	Score	Speaker
11	Whereon old Norway, overcome with joy, Gives him three-score thousand crowns in annual fee And his commission to employ those soldiers, So levied as before, against the Polack, With an entreaty, herein further shown, That it might please you to give quiet pass Through your dominions for this enterprise, On such regards of safety and allowance As therein are set down.	2.30	Voltemand
12	I have not art to reckon my groans, but that I love thee best, O most best, believe it.	1.85	Polonius
13	But what might you think, When I had seen this hot love on the wing (As I perceived it, I must tell you that, Before my daughter told me), what might you, Or my dear Majesty your queen here, think, If I had played the desk or table-book Or given my heart a winking, mute and dumb, Or looked upon this love with idle sight?	1.70	Polonius
14	If circumstances lead me, I will find Where truth is hid, though it were hid, indeed, Within the center.	1.50	Polonius
15	Excellent well.	1.80	King
16	Conception is a blessing, but, as your daughter may conceive, friend, look to 't.	2.15	Hamlet
17	My excellent good friends!	1.75	Hamlet
18	Which dreams, indeed, are ambition, for the very substance of the ambitious is merely the shadow of a dream.	1.60	Hamlet
19	But let me conjure you by the rights of our fellowship, by the consonancy of our youth, by the obligation of our ever-preserved love, and by what more dear a better proposer can charge you withal: be even and direct with me whether you were sent for or no.	3.25	Hamlet
20	What a piece of work is a man, how noble in reason, how infinite in faculties, in form and moving how express and admirable; in action how like an angel, in apprehension how like a god: the beauty of the world, the paragon of animals — and yet, to me, what is this quintessence of dust?	3.60	Hamlet
21	Man delights not me, no, nor women neither, though by your smiling you seem to say so.	1.75	Hamlet
22	Why did you laugh, then, when I said 'man delights not me'?	1.50	Rosencrantz
23	To think, my lord, if you delight not in man, what Lenten entertainment the players shall receive from you.	1.80	Hamlet
24	He that plays the king shall be welcome — his Majesty shall have tribute on me.	1.70	Hamlet
25	The adventurous knight shall use his foil and target, the lover shall not sigh gratis, the humorous man shall end his part in peace, the clown shall make those laugh whose lungs are tickle o' th' sear, and the lady shall say her mind freely, or the blank verse shall halt for 't.	4.75	Hamlet

Table 2: Positive sentences in Act V

#	Sentence	Score	Speaker
1	"Rashly – And praised be rashness for it: let us know, Our indiscretion sometime serves us well When our deep plots do pall; and that should learn us There's a divinity that shapes our ends, Rough-hew them how we will – That is most certain."	3.15	Hamlet
2	"I sat me down, Devised a new commission, wrote it fair – I once did hold it, as our statist do, A baseness to write fair, and labored much How to forget that learning; but, sir, now It did me yeoman's service."	1.50	Hamlet
3	"An earnest conjuration from the King, As England was his faithful tributary, As love between them like the palm might flourish, As peace should still her wheaten garland wear And stand a comma 'tween their amities, And many suchlike ases of great charge, That, on the view and knowing of these contents, Without debatement further, more or less, He should those bearers put to sudden death, Not shriving time allowed."	4.75	Hamlet
4	"Your Lordship is right welcome back to Denmark."	1.70	Osric
5	"Sweet lord, if your Lordship were at leisure, I should impart a thing to you from his Majesty."	2.45	Osric
6	"Nay, good my lord, for my ease, in good faith."	1.50	Osric
7	"Sir, here is newly come to court Laertes – believe me, an absolute gentleman, full of most excellent differences, of very soft society and great showing."	3.10	Osric
8	"What imports the nomination of this gentleman?"	1.60	Hamlet
9	"Three of the carriages, in faith, are very dear to fancy, very responsive to the hilts, most delicate carriages, and of very liberal conceit."	1.85	Osric
10	"If it please his Majesty, it is the breathing time of day with me."	1.50	Hamlet
11	"Let the foils be brought, the gentleman willing, and the King hold his purpose, I will win for him, an I can."	2.40	Hamlet
12	"He does well to commend it himself."	1.55	Hamlet
13	"My lord, his Majesty commended him to you by young Osric, who brings back to him that you attend him in the hall."	1.90	Lord
14	"The Queen desires you to use some gentle entertainment to Laertes before you fall to play."	1.55	Lord

Table 3: C. Negative sentences at the beginning of Act V

#	Sentence	Score	Speaker
1	"For here lies the point: if I drown myself wittingly, it argues an act, and an act hath three branches – it is to act, to do, to perform."	-1.50	Gravedigger
2	"Argal, she drowned herself wittingly."	-0.80	Gravedigger
3	"But if the water come to him and drown him, he drowns not himself."	-1.30	Gravedigger
4	"Argal, he that is not guilty of his own death shortens not his own life."	-1.50	Other Gravedigger
5	"If this had not been a gentlewoman, she should have been buried out o' Christian burial."	-1.10	Gravedigger

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#	Sentence	Score	Speaker
6	"Now, thou dost ill to say the gallows is built stronger than the church."	-0.90	Gravedigger
7	"Cudgel thy brains no more about it, for your dull ass will not mend his pace with beating."	-1.95	Hamlet
8	"How the knave jowls it to the ground as if 'twere Cain's jawbone, that did the first murder!"	-1.55	Hamlet
9	"Why does he suffer this mad knave now to knock him about the sconce with a dirty shovel and will not tell him of his action of battery?"	-2.80	Hamlet
10	"The very conveyances of his lands will scarcely lie in this box, and must th' inheritor himself have no more, ha?"	-1.00	Hamlet
11	"'Tis for the dead, not for the quick; therefore thou liest."	-1.00	Hamlet
12	"How absolute the knave is!"	-1.05	Hamlet

B. SMA graphs for the relative frequencies of predefined word groups in scenes.

Figure 8: Words related to condition

Figure 9: Definitive determiners

Figure 10: Semantic category of 'Bodily Motion'

Figure 11: Possessive pronouns

Figure 12: semantic category of 'Sexuality and Intimate Love'

C. Examples of Iván and Judit Fónagy's graphs demonstrating changes in dramatic tension (1971)

Figure 13: Tension-graphs based on new and answered questions in scenes - from [20]

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author used OpenAI's Chat-GPT-4 in order to: grammar, stylistics and spelling check, LaTeX preparation, as well as code review. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the publication's content.

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A. Online Resources

The codes for analysis can be found here:

Constellations of Characters and Dramaturgical Structures: A Computational Analysis of Ludvig Holberg's Comedies

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Abstract

In this paper, we will use computational methods (conducted in RStudio, <https://github.com/UllaKallenbach/digital-dramaturgy-25>) to analyse character constellations, theatrical presence and temporality in the corpus consisting of Danish-Norwegian playwright Ludvig Holberg's 37 TEI-encoded comedies (<https://holbergsskrifter.dk>).

The spectator's point of view, theatrical conventions and the three-dimensionality of the stage is our dramaturgical points of departure for developing a new digital drama analysis. In this paper, we will demonstrate how different digital statistical and visual analyses can contribute to a data-assisted analysis of both individual texts and the canon of Holberg's works, asking whether we can detect specific patterns of dramaturgical structures. More broadly, this will contribute to the discussion of how a computational approach to dramaturgy may enhance analyses of plays and dramaturgical patterns for researchers as well as theatre practitioners.

We will take our point of departure in our dramaturgical framework of different levels of presence, defined as physical presence, verbal and imagined presence (Kallenbach, U., & Lawaetz, A. 'Levels of presence in the drama text: Between close and distant reading'. *Orbis Litterarum*, 78, 401–420. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oli.12399>). We will pay particular attention to different structures, configurations, transitions and progressions in temporal structures and character constellations and discuss the applicability of different data visualisations.

Our study of dramaturgical structures in Holberg's comedies, on the one hand, aims to facilitate comparative analyses with other DraCoR corpora in the intersection of theatre studies and digital humanities, and, on the other hand, to question how a future digital dramaturgy could be developed.

Keywords

dramaturgy, dramatic rhythm, Ludvig Holberg, digital drama analysis, Danish drama

1. Introduction

This paper investigates constellations of characters in dramaturgical structures through computational analysis using the corpus of Dano-Norwegian playwright, author, and professor Ludvig Holberg's (1684–1754) corpus of 37 comedies. Studies that conduct social network analyses have favoured speech patterns, spoken interactions and the condensation of plot structures, but have a tendency to overlook the performative, embodied presence of the actors and the temporality of the dramaturgy, i.e. the performative durational context. Our paper thus seeks to include the theatrical potential in the digital analysis of drama.

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Working from the hypothesis that embodied and relational presence is historically conditioned, and tied to e.g. spatial, dramaturgical and behavioural conventions, we focus in particular on theatrical conventions of character.

In this paper, we accordingly attempt to include both verbal and embodied presence as well as the spectator's perspective. Our contribution thus aims to nuance the way we understand networks of characters/actors and presence in drama. We thus follow Varela's statement, with reference to Caplan (2017), that "By most definitions of theater, even the most minimal productions require at least a performer and one spectator. 'As scholars of a collaborative art form, we are always dealing with relational data, for theater artists almost never work in isolation'" [1]

Although there has been a rise in digital drama analysis on Scandinavian languages, especially the works on Henrik Ibsen [2], this study is among the first working with the corpus of Ludvig Holberg (Frank Fischer shared a social network analysis of Holberg's comedies as part of this seminar: <https://humanities.ku.dk/calendar/2018/october/the-social-networks-of-holbergs-comedies/>).

As this has been a pilot project, the visualisations are not yet fine-tuned. The project has a data-assisted approach as defined by Varela [1], which means that we use digital methods to reinterpret the understanding of Ludvig Holberg's comedies and test hypotheses for further analyses of drama, and in particular comedy.

2. Data and project design

Our article builds on the pilot project *Danish Theatre Archives in the age of digitalization in research and in education* (2020-2023), which had as its objective to develop and test methods of digital drama analysis using the corpus of Holberg's comedies as a test case.

The Norwegian-born Holberg is considered the founding father of professional Danish-Norwegian playwriting, making his debut in the first Danish-language theatre in Copenhagen in 1722.

The Holberg dataset consists of 37 comedies, of which two are revised versions and also includes a posthumously published libretto. The plays were published between 1723 and 1754, the vast majority before 1731 [3].

Our study was conducted in Rstudio using the TEI-encoded corpus of comedies to develop a range of codes for statistical analyses of drama as well as a number of data visualisations. The comedies are available in original and modern spelling, and the pilot project has used modern spelling variations of the texts exclusively. We use the TEI-encoding to distinguish spoken text from stage directions and speakers, thus making it possible to discern speaking characters from mute characters mentioned in stage directions and names of characters mentioned in the spoken text.

3. Dramaturgy and the analysis of plays

Our point of departure for our analysis is a dramaturgically conditioned point of view that focuses on the play in performance in a theatrical context. This involves an attention to performance space, embodied presence of performers and spectators, and temporality, both in terms of the duration of performance and the historical context of e.g. conventions of genre and character.

Traditionally, drama analysis has centred on how to analyse the composition of the plot and the construction and development of character. Analyses of plot, following Aristotle, have tended to focus on the construction of a dramatic conflict, on turning points (*anagnorisis*, *peripeteia*) and on how narrative arcs build a rising tension developing towards a climax [4]. Thus, Gustav Freytag's influential study of drama (1863) introduced a five-part plot structure developing from exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, to resolution [5]. Others, such as Julien Greimas, have focused on character relations, analysing their different structural functions as actants [6].

Digital drama analysis is based on a statistical analysis of a play or the digital traces of performance. As an example of a structural mathematical approach, Solomon Marcus' analysis of constellations of characters, including manually developed plot charts, is rooted in an understanding of the complexity of the theatrical situation, consisting of what he frames as *die Szenestruktur des Stückes*, which also includes a *Raumstruktur* and takes the spectator as its starting point [7]. He uses this structure for developing plot charts and mathematical analyses of character constellations.

Several scholars have worked with social network analyses, including Franco Moretti, Mark Algeewitt, Frank Fisher and Peer Trilcke, building on speaking-in-turn or co-occurrence principles [8], [9], [10]. Network visualisations are a core feature of the DraCor interface.

Temporality is a challenge in social network analyses, but the IntNetViz study, has attempted a visualisation of the dynamics of character networks in a scene-by-scene development of networks, but conversely omits the temporal overview [11].

Our interest has centred on how we can integrate performative perspectives in our analysis and are thus interested in how the potentials of a spectatorial approach in which "the embedded theatricality and scenic, spatial implications are keys to unlocking an implicit aesthetic experience of the drama text" [12]. We have thus focused on how digital drama analysis can incorporate historical conventions and the relation to how "the drama text is [...] directed towards a collective of live spectators, theorized in drama and performance analysis as 'implied spectators'" [13]. Kallenbach has analysed how implied spectators might contribute to the performance by imagining. This involves various acts of ascribing to the performance, different modes or points of view of imagining, and rhythmic dynamics that condition the theatrical experience [13].

Digital analysis of drama is at a tipping point where it moves from an exclusively text-oriented approach to a more diverse and multi-modal approach that includes the analysis of a broad range of different archival traces, as seen in the work of Clarisse Bardiot [14].

In our article, "Levels of presence in the drama text: Between close and distant reading", we have operated with three levels of presence that condition how characters are present to spectators in performance: physical (embodied onstage presence of the actors); verbal (that the voices of actors are heard, on- or off-stage), and imagined (whereby characters gain presence via direct or indirect references). Furthermore, we have operated with three aspects of character: character (the individual, fictional character), role (the dramaturgic function), and mask (the theatrical convention, in Holberg's case, his application of *commedia dell'arte* stock character gallery) [15].

Levels of stage presence are highly relevant to the study of comedy. Comic potentials thus often lie in discrepancies between what the spectator sees and hears, or in what Manfred Pfister has described as "discrepant awareness" between what characters know and what spectators know [16].

3.1. Eighteenth-century comedy and theatrical conventions

The Eighteenth-century stage was a performative space in which both actors and audience took part. Some spectators were seated on the stage, and there was a blurring of fictive and real spaces, such as in Holberg's *Mascarade*, in which part of the performance is dedicated to a fictive masquerade. The theatre space, in which the comedy was performed, also served as a location for real-life masquerades that the spectators attended. While audience members could certainly participate imaginatively, it is also possible that they joined the actual action unfolding. A digital analysis focused on word counts would not be able to detect such dramaturgically crucial scenes. Similarly, in the play *Kilderejsen*, the entire second act is a mute pantomime. It thus seems highly important to develop digital methods for drama analysis that take into account non-verbal performative aspects.

This is also the case for physical onstage comedy or scenes where characters are eavesdropping while hiding, which may escape a digital analysis that only takes into account the verbal, spoken presence.

Working with 18th-century comedy, it has been relevant to place a particular focus on genre and stock characters, such as the commedia dell'arte young lovers or servants. Such conventions are also found in the plays of e.g. Molière (who, along with Plautus, was a main inspiration for Holberg), Pierre Marivaux, Carlo Goldoni and Carlo Gozzi.

Holberg was very familiar with the European theatrical landscape, and while he drew inspiration from French and Italian comedy, he had travelled Europe extensively (Holberg's journeys have been traced by Kallenbach as part of the project *Artistic Exchanges*, see <https://artex.au.dk/journeys?searchTerm=Holberg>).

Holberg's characters

Studying Holberg's characters is challenging. While the cast lists in the printed plays signal a tight cast, the total number of characters in his plays is significantly different.

Figure 1 Printed cast list in *Den Politiske Kandestøber* https://holbergsskrifter.dk/holberg-public/view?docId=skuespill%2FDen_Politiske_Kandstoeber%2FKandst.page&toc.depth=1&brand=&chunk.id=castlist

For example, in the cast list of Holberg's first comedy, *Den politiske Kandestøber* (Figure 1), only six main characters are mentioned, but the statistical analysis (Table 1) reveals that 43 different characters are appearing in play (name- and spelling variations excluded through a close reading since Holberg's characters are not stable, but change names, characteristics etc.).

Table 1

Title	Total number of characters	Acts	Publication [17]	Performance [18]
<i>den politiske kandestøber komedie</i>	43	5	1723	1722
<i>den vægelsindede komedie</i>	19	5	1723	1722
<i>jean de france eller hans frandsen komedie</i>	13	5	1723	1722
<i>jeppe på bjerget eller den forvandlede bonde</i>	20	5	1723	1722

<i>mester gert westphaler eller den meget talende barber komedie</i>	23	5	1723	1722
<i>nytårsprolog til en komedie allerunderdanigst præsenteret af den hele danske bande 1723</i>	10	1	1723	1723
<i>barselsstuen komedie</i>	43	5	1724	1723
<i>den 11. juni</i>	27	5	1724	1723
<i>det arabiske pulver komedie</i>	15	1	1724	1724
<i>julestue komedie</i>	19	1	1724	1724
<i>maskerade komedie</i>	12	3	1724	1724
<i>mester gert westphaler eller den meget talende barber komedie i 1 akt</i>	15	1	1724	na
<i>kilderejsen komedie i 3 akter</i>	12	3	1725	1724
<i>melampe tragikomedie</i>	21	5	1725	1724
<i>uden hoved og hale komedie</i>	15	5	1725	1724
<i>ulysses von ithacia eller en tysk komedie</i>	10	5	1725	1724
<i>jacob von tyboe eller den stortalende soldat komedie</i>	14	5	1725	1725
<i>diderich menschengræk komedie i 1 akt</i>	13	1	1731	1724
<i>henrik og komedie i 3 akter</i>	9	3	1731	1724
<i>den pantsatte bondedreng komedie i 3 akter</i>	23	3	1731	1726
<i>den stundesløse komedie i 3 akter</i>	27	3	1731	1726
<i>pernilles korte frøkenstand komedie i 3 akter</i>	13	3	1731	1727
<i>de usynlige komedie i 3 akter</i>	7	3	1731	1747
<i>den honnente ambition komedie i 3 akter</i>	13	3	1731	1747
<i>erasmus montanus eller rasmus berg komedie i 5 akter</i>	12	5	1731	1747
<i>hekseri eller blind alarm komedie i 5 akter</i>	47	5	1731	1750
<i>det lykkelige skibbrud komedie i 5 akter</i>	25	5	1731	1754
<i>den vægelsindede komedie i 3 akter</i>	18	3	1731	na
<i>don ranudo de colibrados eller fattigdom og hoffærdighed komedie i 5 akter</i>	12	5	1745	1752
<i>den danske komedies ligbegængelse med thaliæ afskedstale</i>	4	1	1746	1727
<i>plutus eller proces imellem fattigdom og rigdom en heroisk komedie i 5 akter</i>	26	5	1753	1751
<i>husspøgelse eller abracadabra komedie i 3 akter uden aktricer</i>	11	3	1753	1752
<i>den forvandlede brudgom komedie i 1 akt uden aktører</i>	6	1	1753	1882
<i>sganarels rejse til det filosofiske land komedie i 1 akt hvori skæmtes med de gamle filosofiske sekter</i>	16	1	1754	1751
<i>philosophus i egen indbildning komedie i 5 akter</i>	6	5	1754	1754
<i>republikken eller det gemene bedste komedie i 3 akter</i>	13	3	1754	1754
<i>artaxerxes et heroisk skuespill udi tre acter.</i>	7	3	1754	na

Table 1 shows a great variation in the number of characters in the plays and with no apparent tendency over time. It also reveals that there is no pattern in the use of one, three or five act-comedies. As is evident, there is a discrepancy between year of first performance and year of publication. Our corpus and codes use the year of publication as sorting marker.

Even though the inspiration for Holberg’s plays is often claimed to derive from Italian and French comedy as mentioned above, his use of more than 40 characters in some of his plays is unusual in this theatrical tradition. Shakespeare’s cast lists exhibit similar patterns.

Our code allows us to trace and analyse not only individual characters in the comedies, but also the development of the main types, or masks, of stock characters, comparable to the *commedia dell’arte* gallery.

4. Analysis

Comedies are composed for a range of voices, the characters. Therefore, it is interesting to explore how the playwright uses the characters over time in his work. This applies both to the sole pieces and across the entire corpus. In our previous study, we focused on Holberg’s three pairs of stock characters – the male and female servants, the young lovers, and the parents. We analysed how they appeared throughout Holberg’s comedies and in which ways they were scenically present [15]. One finding in this study concerned speech distribution. Here, we surprisingly discovered that the female servant, mostly named Pernille, statistically had the most frequent spoken lines, while the male servant, mostly named Henrik, and the most famous of Holberg’s characters, spoke more words. This informed us of a discrepancy in dramatic rhythm, which suggested that Pernille spoke often, but briefly, while Henrik had longer, but fewer, speeches.

Table 2 Word and line count of the main female and male servants

Speaker	Words	Lines	Plays
<i>Pernille</i>	28.088	3.634	17
<i>Henrik</i>	42.073	2.068	17

In addition to the dramaturgical functions of the characters and their rhythmic presence, the different speech patterns could also indicate different capacities of the actors for which the parts were written. If a speech pattern changes significantly, this could, for instance, indicate that a new actor/actress has been an inspiration.

In this paper, we will focus on these servants, Henrik and Pernille, and their masters, Leander and Leonora (also spelled Leonore). We have used only these main names, while a future study could include name variations/masks (the male servant, for example, also appears as Harlekin, and the young male lover is sometimes named Leonard).

Specifically, we will look at three visualisations of the presence and temporality of these characters. Figure 2 shows side-by-side bar charts of all plays in which these character names appear in highlighted colours. All other characters are shown in grey. Figure 3 visualises the speech distribution scene by scene in a single play with colour codes for all characters. And Figure 4 is a plot chart showing verbal, embodied and imagined presence in each scene of a single play. Additionally, we have included a side-by-side bar chart of stock characters grouped by gender in Figure 5.

Figure 2: Scene by scene verbal presence of the male and female servants (Henrik and Pernille) and young lovers (Leander and Leonora) in Holberg’s comedies.

From Figure 2, we can see that the four stock characters do not appear consistently, neither in the corpus, nor in the individual plays. Altogether, these four stock characters appear under these names in 26 out of the 37 comedies.

Contrary to what one might expect, they do not appear as a regular “ensemble”. Rather, the characters seem to appear as dominant characters in dedicated plays. Anomalous patterns could point to radical dramaturgic structures, such as in *Den pantsatte Bondedreng*. In this play, Leander appears in only scene I.1, and Pernille in four of five scenes in act I, but not in acts II-III. Leander is never mentioned by name again, while Pernille is mentioned once in II.4. Leander and Pernille are thus utilised not as active characters, but as plot functions that signal, to the contemporary audience, a well-known gallery of characters and plot structure.

All four characters appear in *Henrik og Pernille*, *Mascarade*, *Republikken*, *Pernilles korte Frøkenstand*, *Det Lykkelige Skibbrud*, and *Kilderejsen*.

The characters do not seem to appear consistently throughout these plays, but have periods of absence, and they seldom appear altogether in the same scenes. This may signal generic features of comedy, in which the servants act as go-betweens as complications between the young lovers unfold in the plot (e.g. mistaken identities, misunderstandings, etc.).

A derived hypothesis could be that this inconsistent and asynchronous appearance is a generic feature, which could be applied to detect comedies in a larger corpus. Henrik appears as the most consistently present character, while Pernille appears as a main character in dedicated plays. One caveat is that this visualisation does not include mute scenic presence, but we will be able to see this in Figure 4.

In Figure 3, we can delve into a single play, in this example *Henrik and Pernille*, and see the distribution of the four stock characters, as well as a gallery of other classic Holberg stock characters:

Jeronimus (here Leonoras father), Magdelone (here an old woman), Arv (the second servant), and Notarius (a notary). In this play, Henrik and Pernille are masquerading as their masters Leander and Leonora, who are secretly engaged to be married. When Henrik and Pernille meet, they each believe the other to be of higher social rank and thus a desirable match, and they become engaged. Leander and Leonora then believe each other to have been unfaithful – until all is resolved and the two couples finally marry.

Figure 3 Bar chart showing verbal presence and speech distribution, scene by scene in Henrik og Pernille (1731)

While Figure 2 clearly signalled that the four stock characters were not simultaneously present, this is less clear in Figure 3. Figure 3, however, more clearly signals the temporal rhythm of the play. Holberg’s scenes are defined by new constellations of characters, and their entrances and exits. Short scenes thus indicate movement and increased stage business, while longer scenes may indicate time for reflection or rising tension within a character constellation. Figure 3 thus visualises key scenes, the unfolding of the plot, and the increasing tempo towards the final scene in which all characters finally come together. One important point of caution of a scene-by-scene analysis marked by entrances and exits is, as Marcus’ study also underlines, the dynamics within the scenes, due to the difficulty in knowing when a character is leaving the stage during a scene [7].

To get a better sense of the character constellations, the plot chart in Figure 4 shows us both embodied, verbal and imagined presence. This becomes significant in its demonstration of the importance of physical/non-verbal presence. Scenes II.3 (Henrik, Leander and a silent Pernille) and II.7 (Leonora, Leander, and a silent Henrik) are thus the only scenes in which the main characters interact in cross-gendered constellations before the concluding scene.

Figure 4 Levels of presence in *Henrik og Pernille* (1731)

Moreover, we can see that the imagined presence of the characters follows distinct patterns. Pernille is mentioned by name solely in the second half of the play, while Leonora is mentioned only in the first part. Leander’s name is mentioned, with Leonora’s, in the first scene, but then only from the second half of Act II onwards. Henrik is mentioned by name from the middle of Act II to the middle of Act III. Future analyses may, especially with tagged manuscripts that also account for other naming patterns (e.g. ‘my master’ or ‘my maid’), investigate patterns of imagined presence and detect generic variations.

Gendered structures become visible in Figure 5, in which the main stock characters are grouped by gender. This visualisation suggests that there is an overweight of scenes in which the genders appear separately.

Figure 5 Stock characters grouped by gender.

5. Composition of Holberg’s plays

Our analyses demonstrate firstly that it is crucial to make use of a range of different statistic analyses and visualisations in order to grasp the theatrical complexity. Our initial statistical analysis of speech rhythms is in the line and word count for Henrik and Pernille in Table 2 is, for example, not detectable in the visualisations. Conversely, the temporality and gender constellations are detectable – and in different degrees or foci – in the different graphs.

The visualisations make evident that the genders are structurally organised separately, and that the imagined presence may be crucial to making connections between the characters – or indeed fictive worlds as in the case of *Den pantsatte Bondedreng* – in the minds of the spectator.

A continued focus theatricality, the spatial and spectatorial context and the multimodality of plays is thus crucial for future studies, especially with a view to making these tools relevant for theatre practitioners, such as the plot chart, which is a common practical tool in theatre productions developed by hand.

In our analysis, we have focused solely on the key stock characters, but what might an analysis of temporality and functions of characters in Holberg’s entire corpus reveal?

Figure 5 does not give any clear indication of Holberg working consistently in his composition of his plays in terms of temporality and the composition of scene length. Nor is it possible to track a change in the use of one, three and five-act structures as a stylistic change over time. The second acts, however, tend to be slightly shorter. Holberg includes monologues across the entire corpus. Potentially, a further investigation of those might reveal which stock characters typically perform the monologues. Another point of interest could be the longer scenes: Who is present, and are the scenes placed at similar points in the dramaturgy? In an attempt to get an overview of the composition of

the comedies by Ludvig Holberg, we have manually coded his 667 characters in social groups. A study of this will require further investigation.

Currently, 18.000 Danish plays dating from 1748 to today are being digitised at the Royal Danish Library (under PI Lawaetz), which should finally make large-scale studies of Danish-language drama possible, and our development of our codes for this corpus is ongoing.

Acknowledgements

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See: <https://kulturarvscluster.kb.dk/projekter/danske-teaterarkiver-i-digitaliseringens-tidsalder-i-forskning-og-undervisning>.

The dataset was generously made available to us by Society for Danish Language and Literature.

Declaration on Generative AI

The author(s) have not employed any Generative AI tools.

A. Online Resources

The dataset of Holberg's comedies can be found at holbergsskrifter.no. TEI-encoded files are available upon request.

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Small Large Language Models for Digital Humanities Tasks – The Bechdel-Wallace-Test on the DraCor as a Model Case

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Abstract

We study the topical composition of women’s dialogues in European drama using the TEI-encoded DraCor corpora. Building on the Bechdel–Wallace Test (BWT), we operationalize the first two criteria deterministically and pose the stricter semantic question for criterion (3): when two women speak, is the main topic a man? We present a reproducible pipeline based on compact open-weight LLMs: Gemma 3-4B (instruction-tuned) for multilingual synthetic edge cases and summaries, and Qwen 3 (reasoning variant) for final topic labels with auditable rationales. Topic is encoded through a contradiction-aware, four-point rating scheme applied both to all-female scenes and to female-to-female exchanges embedded within mixed-gender scenes (identified from TEI speaker metadata).

Across the French corpus (1,940 plays) and additional German, Hungarian, Italian, English, Dutch, Swedish, Romanian, Classical Greek/Latin, and Calderón collections, the analysis yields consistent patterns: (i) dialogues between two women are predominantly about men (e.g., ≈83% in French); (ii) including mixed scenes increases BWT pass rates heterogeneously across corpora; (iii) periodization matters—French drama from 1650–1700 shows elevated female presence without commensurate gains in non-male topics; and (iv) an inverted-BWT baseline for male–male talk indicates a persistent asymmetry that cannot be explained by cast proportions alone. We discuss threats to validity (metadata, segmentation, literalism) and provide practical guidance for running small models locally with transparent prompts and stored reasoning.

The results suggest that small, open-weight models—when engineered for audibility—are competitive for scholarly annotation at scale while offering advantages in privacy, reproducibility, and ecological footprint.

Keywords

Bechdel–Wallace Test; DraCor; TEI; topic labeling; multilingual NLP; reasoning models; open-weight LLMs.

1. Introduction

The Bechdel–Wallace Test (BWT)¹ offers a reproducible, falsifiable procedure for assessing one dimension of gender representation: (1) the presence of at least two women (often, named), (2) a conversation between them, and (3) the absence of men as the topic of that conversation. While the BWT can be operationalized at scale for structured corpora, it leaves open a crucial semantic problem: when two women do converse, what is the main topic of their exchange? Answering this question requires topic identification under the constraints of historical drama, multiple languages, and heterogeneous dramaturgical conventions.

This paper addresses that problem for the TEI-encoded DraCor corpora. We adopt a scene-level approach that distinguishes all-female scenes from female-to-female exchanges embedded in mixed-gender scenes. The first two BWT criteria are resolved deterministically from TEI metadata; the third criterion (topic) is tackled with compact, open-weight large language models (LLMs) engineered for audibility.

Earlier computational strategies—topic models, distributional heuristics, and feature-based classifiers—provide coarse topical sketches but do not reliably establish non-topics, which is decisive for BWT (3). Recent LLMs are multilingual and instruction-following, but concerns remain regarding cost, reproducibility, and interpretability, especially in scholarly settings. We therefore investigate

¹ [1] provides a short introduction to the BWT.

whether small models—runnable on commodity hardware—can deliver stable, human-interpretable labels across languages and periods.

1.1. Research questions.

- RQ1: How frequently do all-female scenes and female-to-female exchanges occur across DraCor corpora and periods?
- RQ2: Conditional on such a dialogue occurring, how often is its main topic a man (vs. not a man), and how does this differ by corpus and period?
- RQ3: Can a contradiction-aware labeling scheme, implemented with small reasoning-capable LLMs, align model decisions with human judgments for edge cases (e.g., indirect reference, generic male talk, brief spousal mentions)?
- RQ4: How do results change when mixed-gender scenes are included, and what baseline is suggested by an inverted BWT applied to male–male dialogues?
- RQ5 (LLM): Can compact open-weight models running locally achieve agreement with intuitive human understanding of BWT topic labelling?
- RQ6 (LLM): What are the accuracy–latency–resource trade-offs between (a) a small instruction-tuned model with simulated reasoning (multi-prompt) and (b) a small reasoning model?
- RQ7 (LLM): How good are results for annotations based on context?
- RQ8 (LLM): Do stored reasoning traces measurably improve auditability and error correction (e.g., faster adjudication, clearer provenance) compared to models without explicit reasoning output?

1.2. Contributions.

1. A reproducible, TEI-aware pipeline that operationalizes BWT (1)–(2) deterministically and addresses BWT (3) via compact open-weight LLMs with stored rationales.
2. A contradiction-aware, four-point rating scheme for topic determination, with tailored prompts for two-woman, multi-woman, and mixed-gender scenes.
3. A multilingual analysis across major DraCor corpora (French, German, Hungarian, Italian, English, Dutch, Swedish, Romanian, Classical Greek/Latin, and Calderón), quantifying topic distributions and period effects.
4. An expectation baseline via the inverted BWT and a discussion of threats to validity (metadata errors, segmentation granularity, model literalism) relevant for corpus-scale humanities annotation.
5. An empirical assessment of small LLMs under local deployment, comparing instruction-tuned vs. reasoning variants on accuracy, stability, and runtime/compute costs, and offering practical parameter guidelines for reproducible humanities annotation.

The remainder of the paper reports data and scope (§2), descriptive findings (§3), methodological design (§§4–9), results for mixed-gender scenes and author gender (§§10–12), periodization with a French case study (§13), expectation modeling (§14), limitations (§15), and practical guidance (§16).

2. Data and Scope

2.1. Corpora

We processed all DraCor corpora and generated scene-level data for the entire platform. For reasons of space, this paper reports detailed results for the following collections; unless otherwise stated, results are aggregated per collection:

- French (1,940 plays; largest corpus).
- German, Hungarian, Italian (medium-sized; overlapping periods).
- Calderón (Spanish; 201 plays by Pedro Calderón de la Barca).
- English (pre-Calderón) and Dutch (earlier periods; sparse female–female scenes).
- Swedish, Romanian (smaller; suitable for author-gender analysis).
- Classical Greek, Classical Latin, and Shakespeare (period/canonical baselines).

2.2. Units and Operational Definitions

- Speaker identification. Speakers are taken from TEI `<sp>/<speaker>` metadata. Gender follows cast-list information. Allegorical roles are treated according to their encoded gender. The gender of the authors was extracted from Wikipedia, using SPARQL and the provided references in the TEI.
- All-female scene. A scene in which two or more speakers are female and no male speakers appear in that scene.
- Two-woman scene. An all-female scene with exactly two female speakers.
- Female–female exchange in mixed scenes. Within a scene containing multiple genders, we extract stretches of consecutive female-addressed-to-female turns (at least two adjacent turns). Addressees are inferred from explicit vocatives/stage directions or from local conversational context (cf. §10).
- Topic labels. The semantic question for BWT (3) is encoded through the six statements and four-point rating scheme described in §7. For summary-based variants and language pivoting, see §9.
- Named-character condition. We accept the TEI naming conventions. Aware of the historical variation over the corpora, we do not enforce the “named women” predicate in the main analysis, as it would be hard for some corpora to distinguish between “real” women and for example allegorical roles.

2.3. Inclusion and Exclusion

- We include all lowest-level TEI `<div>s` with scenic character (not just canonical scenes) in preprocessing—this covers prologues, epilogues, interludes, choruses, etc., whenever encoded at the lowest structural level.
- Topic labels for BWT (3) are applied to units that contain dialogue (≥ 2 turns). Units without dialogue remain in structural counts but are not topic-labeled.
- Units with uncertain/missing gender for any speaker are excluded from all-female counts but may contribute to mixed-scene analyses when female–female stretches can be isolated unambiguously.

2.4. Pre-processing and Quality Control

- Scene extraction (XSLT). Scenes were extracted via XSLT, taking the lowest-level TEI `<div>s` with scenic character.
- Per-scene enrichment. Each extracted scene was augmented with the cast-list information (gender and role metadata) of the participants of that scene, pulled from the TEI header of the corresponding play.
- LLM-ready text. In a second step, scenes were converted into a compact plain-text format to reduce tokenization overhead and facilitate LLM processing.
- Categorization for downstream tasks. Scenes were partitioned into: (i) exactly two women; (ii) all-female (>2 women); (iii) mixed-gender with ≥ 2 women and consecutive

female-to-female turns. Additionally, for the inverted BWT (conducted for the French corpus only), we collected scenes with exactly two men.

- A set of artificial data was created for controlled quality checks during prompt engineering and workflow adaptations.
- All LLM-output was validated and the Call repeated a maximum of 3 times, if validation failed.
- Provenance tracking. For LLM labeling, we store prompts, model identifiers, temperature/output settings, and (for Qwen) reasoning traces to support audit and adjudication. Information for dialogues that failed in labeling procedures are preserved.
- Reproducibility. The project repository is not yet public; scripts, results and configurations will be released. Until then, materials are available upon request.

2.5. Scope and Limitations

The study focuses on scene-level topicality rather than global plot semantics. Mixed-scene extraction can surface trivial female–female snippets; we therefore report results for all-female scenes and mixed-scene exchanges separately and discuss implications in §§11–12. Corpus composition (period, genre, author mix) varies across collections; comparisons are interpreted with caution. A very small number of calls (less than 2%) to the LLM did not produce valid results in repeated tries, some scenes were therefore not included in the research.

3. Descriptive Findings

This section summarizes headline corpus-level descriptives; detailed breakdowns and sensitivity checks are reported later (§§11–14).

3.1. French corpus (n = 1,940 plays)

- On average, 1.4 all-female scenes per play are observed.
- In total, 2,786 all-female scenes occur; 83% involve exactly two women.
- All-female scenes are unevenly distributed across plays: 41% of plays have any all-female scene; 40% have at least one two-woman scene. Among plays with any all-female scene, 97% include at least one two-woman scene.
- 11% of plays include an all-female scene with more than two women; among plays with any all-female scene, 29% include such larger female groups.
- For dialogues between two women, 83% of scenes are primarily about an absent man. Only 14% of plays contain at least one all-female scene not about men; among plays with any all-female scene, roughly one third include at least one such non-male-topic scene.

Figure 1: Visualization of the proportions of plays passing the BWT based on all female dialogues, the number of plays with at least one two-women-scene, and the number of plays with scenes with more than two females talking among themselves.

3.2. German, Hungarian, Italian

- At least one two-woman scene occurs in 34% (German), 31% (Hungarian), and 53% (Italian) of plays.
- At least one scene where women talk about something other than men appears in 15% (German), 16% (Hungarian), and 15% (Italian) of plays.
- Share of two-woman scenes whose main topic is men: 59% (German), 52% (Hungarian), 85% (Italian), compared to 83% in French.

Figure 2: Proportions for the German corpus: percentage of plays passing the BWT, percentage of plays having a two-women-scene, percentage of plays with a all-female-scene.

Figure 3: Proportions for the Hungarian corpus: percentage of plays passing the BWT, percentage of plays having a two-women-scene, percentage of plays with a all-female-scene.

Figure 4: Proportions for the Italian corpus: percentage of plays passing the BWT, percentage of plays having a two-women-scene, percentage of plays with a all-female-scene.

3.3. Calderón corpus (201 plays, single-author)

- Only 30 plays (15%) lack a scene where two or more women talk about something other than a man—the reverse of the French profile.
- 67% of plays contain two-woman scenes; 48% contain all-female scenes with larger casts.
- Focus on marriage/partnership is comparatively rare: 31% of female–female talks (vs. 55% in French). Discussions at a more abstract/theoretical level without a specific man are more frequent (Calderón 17% vs. French 10%).
- Female participants are often allegorical (personified virtues/vices/aspects), which may increase indirection.

Figure 5: Proportions for the Calderón corpus: percentage of plays passing the BWT, percentage of plays having a two-women-scene, percentage of plays with a all-female-scene.

3.4. Other languages (high level overview)

- English: female–female scenes are rare—only 9% of plays contain a two-woman scene; only 3% have any women-only scene not about a man. The corpus is entirely before the age of Calderón.
- Dutch: ~8% of plays include women speaking not about men, while ~31% include a two-woman scene of any topic. Half of the corpus is before the age of Calderón.
- Swedish (68 plays): a majority of female-authored works and a high BWT pass rate—more than half the plays pass when mixed scenes are included; 29% pass on all-female scenes alone.
- Romanian: including mixed-gender female-to-female exchanges triples BWT passes (3 → 10 plays; 12% → 36%).
- Classical Latin and Shakespeare (English and German translations): female–female scenes are rare and almost never about non-male topics.
- Classical Greek and Swedish: in mixed scenes, women who converse among themselves are about as likely to discuss men as in all-female scenes (see §9).

Figure 6: Proportions for the Swedish corpus: percentage of plays passing the BWT, percentage of plays having a two-women-scene, percentage of plays with a all-female-scene.

These descriptive patterns motivate the methodological core that follows: determining what a dialogue is about at scale, across languages and periods.

4. The Key Methodological Problem: Topic, Not just Presence

Counting women and identifying scenes with at least two female speakers is straightforward from TEI structure and metadata. The difficult step is topic determination for BWT (3): given a female–female exchange, decide whether the main topic is a man. This is a problem of aboutness, not mere mention. A scene can contain male names without being about a man, and conversely a dialogue can be about a man without overt reference (indirection, metaphor, role titles).

4.1. Why standard method fall short

Topic models, embeddings, or keyword heuristics sketch² what is present lexically but do not establish non-topics reliably (absence, subordination, indirection). Moreover, multilingual historical drama adds variability in naming conventions, allegory, and genre constraints that require contextual, discourse-level judgments.

² [2] and [3] provide good examples of research based on traditional computational approaches.

In practice, many Bechdel assessments rely on single-pass human judgments—e.g., community labels on [bechdeltest.com](https://www.bechdeltest.com) or one-annotator designs discussed in the literature (e.g. [1]). This limits inter-rater reliability and provides a noisy, lower-bound comparator for LLM outputs.

4.2. LLMs for topic as aboutness

Instruction-following LLMs can integrate lexical cues with pragmatic signals (anaphora, adjacency, rhetorical role) across languages. However, they tend toward literal surface criteria, risking false passes/fails in edge cases (e.g., concealed male reference). Our design therefore (i) decomposes the decision into contradictory statement pairs (§7), (ii) forces a non-neutral choice on a four-point scale, and (iii) preserves reasoning traces to support adjudication and error analysis.

Problem statement (BWT 3). Given unit consisting of female–female turns, determine labels for statements 1–6 (Section 7). A dialogue fails BWT (3) if (3) (main topic is a man/men) is rated more strongly than (4) (main topic is not a man/men); it passes if (4) dominates. Statements (1)/(2) encode topical presence vs. alternative topics; (5)/(6) capture marriage/heterosexual partnership and covert male topics.

This framing turns BWT (3) into a structured, auditable labeling problem compatible with small LLMs and multilingual scene segmentation.

5. Models and Rationale

We employ two compact, open-weight LLMs that run on standard university laptops (CPU-only or with modest GPUs) and can be scaled horizontally (multiple machines in parallel).

- Gemma 3 (4B, instruction-tuned): used to generate multilingual synthetic dialogues (edge cases; §6) and, experimentally, to produce short, content-preserving summaries (§9). Efficient at prompt-following; no explicit reasoning traces³.
- Qwen 3 (reasoning variant, 8B): used for the final topic labels. Mixture of Experts model. Provides a documented reasoning trace that improves transparency during development and audit. Slower and more memory-hungry per call than Gemma 3, but yielded the most stable labels in our pipeline. Also used for Annotation of addresses in dialogues⁴.

5.1. Deployment and Defaults

- Local execution. Both models were run locally for throughput experiments and proof of concept. For the complete analysis of the larger corpora several Colab instances with L4 GPU (cf. §8) were run in parallel.
- Batching. Scene units are processed with batch size 1 to preserve per-scene rationales; parallelism is achieved across machines/processes.
- Sampling. We use moderate temperatures (0.8) for the reasoning model to avoid degenerate, truncated rationales (§8). Outputs are capped to short formats (ratings + compact rationale).
- Prompts. Three prompt templates target: (i) two-woman dialogues, (ii) all-female scenes with >2 women, (iii) mixed scenes with isolated female–female exchanges (§7). Further prompts for annotation and synthetic dialogues.

³ Cf. model card: <https://huggingface.co/google/gemma-3-4b-it>

⁴ Cf. Model card: <https://huggingface.co/Qwen/Qwen3-8B>

5.2. Rationale for small models

Small models substantially lower operational cost and facilitate privacy-preserving local processing. Open weights enable inspection and domain adaptation and allow projects to archive frozen versions for long-term reproducibility. While flagship models can improve peak accuracy, our results indicate that, with an engineered pipeline and explicit rationales, compact models are competitive for this labeling task and better suited to auditable, corpus-scale scholarly workflow.

6. Designing Edge Cases and Human–Model Comparisons

To stress-test topic labeling for BWT (3), we designed six borderline scenarios that probe typical sources of ambiguity. Each scenario was realized as multiple fully developed dialogues (varied styles, genres, moods, and languages represented in DraCor), generated with Gemma 3-4B-IT. The scenarios are:

- Two women discuss a male child, but not an adult man.
- Two women discuss a man, then pivot to a trivial, everyday topic by the end.
- Two women discuss a single non-male topic throughout, but briefly mention their husbands in the final exchange.
- Two women talk only about a man, but do so indirectly via symbols, euphemisms, or substitute objects.
- Two women discuss several acquaintances of both genders without focusing on any particular individual.
- Two women discuss romantic relationships (assumed heterosexual) but never refer to a specific man.

6.1.1. Evaluation protocol.

Commercial systems (o3-mini, 4o, Claude 3, Gemini) were first asked to state the BWT and then to judge each dialogue. This was repeated several time for some of the dialogues. Human annotators (classroom setting) provided single-pass judgments after a short introduction to the BWT; some plots were intentionally varied in style and language across participants to probe robustness (cf. §4.2 for implications of single-pass baselines).

6.1.2. Findings.

Variation in style and language did not materially affect judgments for either humans or LLMs. All groups treated “male children” as distinct from adult men for BWT purposes. The major divergence was interpretive stance: systems tended to apply the criteria literally (surface cues), whereas human readers judged according to the intended aboutness of the scene. In scenario 4, for example, human readers unanimously judged a failure (the dialogue is about a man, albeit obliquely), while systems often judged a pass (no explicit male mention). This motivates our contradiction-aware labeling scheme in §7.

6.1.3. Validation routines

The artificial dialogues were expanded to include texts about marriage, texts that clearly fulfill the BWT criteria and texts that clearly not do so in representative numbers and translated in all the

languages of the DraCor. The resulting test set was used to evaluate every change on prompts or workflows to make sure, routines used on the corpora were providing only expected results⁵.

7. From Principles to Practice: A Labeling Scheme

To align LLM outputs with human expectations, we formulated six statements—four primary and two auxiliary—to be rated for each candidate dialogue. The primary pair (1 vs. 2) and the main-topic pair (3 vs. 4) are deliberately overlapping and partially contradictory to expose uncertainty and force a decision.

7.1. Primary statements

- The dialogue has a certain man/men as a topic, or deals with men in general.
- The dialogue has other topics than a certain man/men or men in general.
- The main topic is a certain man/men or men in general.
- The main topic is not a certain man/men or men in general.

7.2. Auxiliary statements

- A main or major topic is male–female relations, marriage, or partnership.
- The dialogue rarely mentions a man directly, yet covertly (symbolically or by indirection) a man/men are an important topic.

7.2.1. Rating scale (no neutral option):

2 = fully matches; 1 = partly matches; -1 = doesn't completely match; -2 = doesn't match at all.

A neutral mid-point was intentionally omitted. In earlier pilots, “neutral” bled together several distinct cases—lack of understanding, minimal trace evidence, inapplicability, true tie between extremes—yielding ambiguous signals. The four bins force the model to commit, making downstream interpretation simpler.

⁵ On the relevance of synthetic data cf. [4] pp. 210 – 224 and [5] pp.381 - 383. [5] gives detailed descriptions of how to apply LLM/ Foundation models pp. 383 – 395.

Figure 7: Swedish corpus. The color in the heatmaps encode the number of scenes that confirm with the combination of values for statement 1 (a man/ men is/are a topic in this talk) and statement 3 (the man / men is are the main topic of the talk). Statement 3 cannot be true if statement 1 is not also true – therefore no results in the corresponding quadrant.

7.2.2. Decision rule

Let $s_k \in \{2, 1, -1, -2\}$, where 2 denotes the strongest match and -2 the strongest mismatch. A unit passes BWT (3) iff $s_3 < 0$ and $s_4 > 0$. In all other cases, the unit fails BWT (3). This results in a small number of scenes, where no main topic can be identified, which might be interpreted as wrongly attribute the BWT fail status. A deeper look into the statements 1 and 2 could clear up these cases.

Figure 8: German corpus: Heatmap of the two statements crucial to the BWT. The second quadrant (statement 3 negative, statement 4 positive) marks the scenes, passing the BWT.

7.2.3. Dialogue types and prompts.

Three prompt templates were needed for reliable results:

- Two-woman dialogues (straightforward).
- All-female scenes with more than two women (requires disambiguating topical focus vs. side chatter).
- Mixed-gender scenes where at least one female–female exchange occurs. Here, female lines addressed to female addressees are emphasized, and the model is instructed to ignore lines by or to men except as necessary for context. §8 discusses caveats of this isolation approach.

- **Figure 9:** Heatmap giving a more detailed view of BWT for the German corpus: Only scenes with more than two women talking in plays from 1850 to 1900 are considered, 8 such scenes pass the BWT.

8. Implementation Details and Model Behavior

8.1. Deterministic steps (criteria 1–2).

The first two BWT criteria do not require LLMs. Cast lists yield the count of female roles (criterion 1). Scene segmentation plus speaker metadata yield counts of scenes with more than one female speaker (criterion 2). These were implemented with XSLT and Python.

8.2. Final criterion (topic).

Qwen 3 (reasoning) judged statements 1–6 for each scene or female–female exchange, outputting both ratings and a compact rationale. Ratings use the signed four-bin scale $s_k \in \{2, 1, -1, -2\}$ (Section 7). Outputs are serialized as csv and validated against a simple schema; on validation failure we re-prompt once with a stricter format instruction. The reasoning transcript proved especially valuable for debugging prompts, auditing corner cases, and explaining. On a Colab instance with an L4 GPU, per-dialogue analysis typically finished in under a minute, while taking at least 3 times as long on a standard Laptop.

8.3. Temperature and output control.

Labeling is commonly done with low temperature and short outputs to prevent rambling. However, for a reasoning model, overly low temperatures can cripple the useful exploratory steps and produce repetitive, prematurely truncated rationales as output length limits are hit. In practice, moderate temperatures preserved coherent reasoning while keeping answers concise.

8.4. Gemma 3 for labeling?

Without explicit reasoning, Gemma 3’s label quality was inconsistent: the model overweighted late text, occasionally hallucinated, and sometimes drifted from the required output format. A pragmatic workaround was to simulate simple reasoning via a three-step prompt chain per statement: (a) gather evidence and note missing information; (b) evaluate each rating; (c) choose the most likely rating. This improved accuracy substantially—but at a steep cost: 18 calls per dialogue (three prompts × six statements) versus one Qwen 3 reasoning call. On a CPU-only laptop, a single dialogue could take 30–60 minutes end-to-end. For this project, Gemma’s main role remained data generation (edge cases); summarization/translation were used only experimentally (9).

9. Summaries, Translation, and Multilingual Coverage

Both models advertise coverage of 100+ languages (per their model cards), including all DraCor languages. In the main analysis, we did not use summaries or translations. We conducted a small exploratory experiment solely to assess whether these tactics might be advisable in other projects.

9.1. Findings from the experiment (small test set):

9.1.1. Summaries:

Scene summaries produced with Gemma 3 and then labeled by Qwen 3 showed no detectable quality loss relative to labeling the full text.

9.1.2. Translation (e.g., Ukrainian → English):

We observed no improvement in label quality compared to labeling the original language directly.

Given the limited scope of this experiment, we treat these results as preliminary and do not deploy summary-first or pivot-language translation in the present study. They are mentioned here to inform potential strategies in other settings

10. Mixed-Gender Scenes: Who Talks to Whom?

When a unit contains only two speakers who are both female (i.e., an all-female two-person scene), we can safely assume they address each other. In mixed-gender scenes, however, sub-conversations and intermittent participation are common. For the BWT we therefore isolate female-to-female exchanges inside mixed scenes.

10.1. Operational Rule

10.1.1. Candidate windows.

Within mixed scenes, we identify stretches with ≥ 2 consecutive turns by women. These spans are treated as candidate windows for female-to-female exchanges.

10.1.2. Prompt focus via highlighting.

In the dialog text sent to the LLM, these candidate windows are visually highlighted, and the prompt explicitly instructs the model to focus only on the highlighted passages and to ignore surrounding turns (by or to men) except when strictly necessary for context.

10.2. Empirical behaviour

Empirically, the highlight-and-focus prompting led the models to respect window boundaries and minimize bleed-through from adjacent mixed-gender talk. In a limited sub-corpus experiment, we additionally had the LLM insert addressee annotations per turn within mixed scenes: monologues and asides were marked accordingly, and group addresses were resolved where possible, otherwise retained as group-directed. Interestingly both models were able to identify addressees not only, when openly addressed by the speaker, but also from more subtle context information. Only the Qwen 3 was able however, to reliably provide fully annotated dialogues of good quality.

An extract from such an annotated dialogue is provided from a Calderón play cal000015 showing both the potential, but also the limits of this approach:

La Discreción (->Discreción)⁶: Yo, que tantas penitencias hice, mil veces dichosa, pues tan bien las he logrado. Aquí dichoso es quien llora confesando haber errado.

El Rey (->Autor): Yo, señor, ¿entre mis pompas ya no te pedí perdón? Pues ¿por qué no me perdonas?

El Autor (->Hermosura, Rey, Labrador)⁷: La hermosura y el poder, por aquella vanagloria que tuvieron, pues lloraron, subirán, pero no ahora, con el Labrador también, que aunque no te dio limosna, no fue por no querer darla, que su intención fue piadosa, y aquella reprehensión fue en su modo misteriosa, para que tú te ayudases.

This richer annotation is not used for the main results but demonstrates a feasible path for more fine-grained future analyses (e.g., addressee networks, aside frequencies).

10.3. Caveat

Extracting female-to-female stretches from mixed scenes can yield trivial or inconsequential exchanges (e.g., brief asides). Such snippets may formally satisfy the BWT but obscure the richer signals in all-female scenes. We therefore report results both ways when possible and discuss substantive differences (§11–12).

11. Results by Author Gender (Swedish case study)

11.1. Corpus Profile

The Swedish corpus comprises 68 plays with a majority of female-authored works. This composition makes it suitable for examining author-gender effects under the same operationalization used elsewhere in the paper.

11.2. Key findings

11.2.1. BWT pass rates.

When mixed-gender scenes (with isolated female–female exchanges) are included, more than half of Swedish plays pass the BWT; based on all-female scenes alone, 29% pass.

⁶ La Discretion is talking to herself, which is correctly annotated.

⁷ El Autor addresses only persons (personifications) that are present in the scene, while La Hermosura is, el poder is not.

11.2.2. Scene-level topic asymmetry.

Plays by female authors contain more scenes in which women talk about something other than men than plays by male authors—about a 35% relative increase overall. The difference is most pronounced in all-female scenes with > 2 women.

11.2.3. Play-level passes (all-female basis).

The scene-level asymmetry translates into an ≈33% relative increase in play-level BWT passes for female-authored plays when only all-female scenes are considered.

Figure 21: Numbers of plays that pass the BWT based on all-female scenes in the Swedish corpus for authors of two genders. Only plays that contain such a scene are displayed. The ratio of plays that pass is higher for female authors.

11.2.4. Effect of mixed scenes.

Including mixed scenes yields 15 additional passes overall. These newly passing plays are disproportionately male-authored, which equalizes the play-level pass rates across author genders—even though female-authored plays still exhibit more non-male-topic exchanges at the scene level.

11.3. Interpretation and caveats

The Swedish corpus highlights how methodological choice (all-female only vs. mixed) can change conclusions about author-gender effects: scene-level differences persist, but play-level passes converge when mixed scenes are counted. Given the small sample size and potential confounds (genre mix, period, venue), these results should be interpreted cautiously and corroborated with additional controls.

12. All-Female vs. Mixed Scenes Across Corpora

12.1. Aggregate patterns

It is statistically expected that mixed-gender scenes outnumber all-female scenes and that opportunities for female–female exchanges are more frequent within mixed scenes. In several corpora (e.g., Romanian, Swedish, Classical Greek), women who converse within mixed scenes are about as likely to be talking about men as in all-female scenes. By contrast, in Classical Latin and Shakespeare, female–female scenes are extremely rare and almost never about non-male topics.

12.2. Effect on BWT pass counts

Including mixed scenes can substantially change BWT pass counts. In Romanian, only 3 plays pass using all-female scenes alone; including mixed scenes with clear female-to-female exchanges raises this to 10 plays (12% → 36%). The Calderón corpus is exceptional: while mixed scenes do add passes, a majority of plays already pass based on all-female scenes alone (§3.3). These contrasts underscore both the analytic value and the methodological risk of mixing scene types.

13. Periodization: The French Corpus Over Time

Because it is large and spans centuries, the French corpus supports a temporal analysis. We summarize the main tendencies and briefly note how expectations were modelled.

13.1. Method note (expectations)

We estimate the expected number of two-woman scenes under a cast-list-based null: for each play and period slice, let f be the share of female roles in the cast list. Combining with the observed scene inventory (counts of two-person same-gender scenes) yields an expected baseline for two-woman dialogues. Comparing observed vs. expected counts gives an over/under-representation factor.

13.2. Patterns over time

- 1650–1700 features a higher percentage of plays passing the BWT (all-female basis) than periods before or after. Casts are smaller than 1600–1650 but include a higher female role share ($\approx 40\%$). Despite this, women remain underrepresented overall by the first BWT criterion.
- Same-gender scenes are quite frequent before 1550, but this largely reflects male-only interactions (women being largely absent). Same-gender scene counts rise again 1650–1700.
- Using cast-list-based expectations, the baroque era yields nearly one expected two-woman scene per play; the expected number drops sharply 1750–1800 and again after 1850. Comparing expected to observed counts reveals that until the 19th century two-woman scenes are more frequent than expected (e.g., $3.5\times$ overrepresentation for 1600–1650; $\geq 2.5\times$ from 1550–1750). Conversely, male–male scenes are underrepresented relative to cast proportions in the same window—even though they remain far more numerous in absolute terms.

- **Figure 32:** Stacked bars on a time line show the increase in same sex scenes of two participant from 1600 – 1850 and the relative decrease of all female scenes of such kind.

- **Figure 43:** Barplot on a time line show the expected numbers for two-female scenes. Compared numbers with figure 12.

13.3. Implications

These patterns complicate simple narratives: increases in female casting do not automatically translate into more non-male topics in women’s conversations, and historical peaks in women’s presence need not coincide with peaks in BWT passes. The divergence invites closer study of institutional and generic factors that may decouple presence from topic independence.

14. The Inverted Bechdel Test and Expectation Modelling

14.1. Definition

We compute an inverted BWT for men as a baseline: the share/amount of male–male dialogues whose main topic is not women. This provides a period-specific expectation for how often same-gender dialogue could be about non-opposite-gender topics in the absence of bias.

From 1550–1800, the inverted BWT yields on average more than one such scene per play, with a peak around 1700–1750. For women over the same span, the mean is about one scene per five plays; only 1800–1850 rises to one in three plays.

Figure 54: Stacked bars on a time line show the ratio of plays in the French corpus, that pass the BWT and the inverted BWT.

14.2. Expectation models

We use two simple expectation models to transfer or normalize the inverted baseline to the female case (applied to two-person same-gender dialogues):

Model A — Ratio transfer (male \rightarrow female). Let r_m be the period-specific ratio of male–male dialogues not about women to all male–male dialogues. The expected number of female passes is $E_A = r_m * N_f$, where N_f is the number of female–female dialogues.

Model B — Same-gender normalization. Let r_{sg} be the ratio of non-opposite-gender topics across all same-gender dialogues (male and female combined). The expected female passes are $E_B = r_{sg} * N_f$.

These expectations are not causal models; they offer null-style baselines against which observed female outcomes can be compared.

14.3. Results

Both models over-predict non-male-topic talk among women relative to observations. Based on two-person same-gender dialogues, the inverted BWT is passed by $\approx 36\%$ of plays, with peaks $> 60\%$ (1550–1600) and $\approx 50\%$ (1600–1650; 1700–1750). The persistent gap between expected and

observed female rates indicates a pronounced asymmetry that the BWT reveals but does not, by itself, explain.

Figure 65: The number of plays passing the BWT divided by the expected values for plays passing the BWT shows clear signs of a bias.

15. Limitations and Threats to Validity

- Metadata errors: Mis-gendered roles or ambiguous names propagate into counts. Manual spot checks are essential.
- Scene segmentation: TEI <div> granularity varies; long scenes with multiple conversational threads may challenge topical coherence.
- Mixed-scene extraction: Isolated female-to-female snippets can be trivial; requiring a minimum token/turn threshold helps.
- Language variation: Archaisms, verse, and allegory (e.g., Calderón’s allegorical figures) may increase indirection, testing statement 6.
- Hardware constraints: Reasoning models are slower; batching and summary-first pipelines mitigate costs but may introduce compression artifacts.
- Causal inference: Observational differences (e.g., author gender or period effects) should not be over-interpreted without controlling for genre, venue, and sub-corpus composition.

16. Practical Guidance for Scholars

- Pre-specify the rules. Fix the statement set (1–6), the signed rating scale (2/1/–1/–2), the decision rule (pass iff $s_3 < 0$ and $s_4 > 0$), and tie-handling before labeling. Keep a changelog of any revisions.
- Do the deterministic part first. Resolve BWT (1)–(2) from TEI with scripts; keep stable scene IDs so labels, rationales, and figures are traceable to source.
- Provide testing routines for the reliable consistency of the prompts and workflows.
- Windowed labeling for mixed scenes. Extract and highlight candidate windows (≥ 2 consecutive female turns) and instruct the model to consider only the highlighted text.

Exclude asides and unresolved group addresses; document the minimum window length used.

- Prompts and outputs. Use three prompt templates (two-woman; all-female >2; mixed). Cap outputs to ratings + compact rationale. Serialize to structured data.

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Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author used Chat-GPT-4 in order to: Grammar and spelling check. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the publication's content.

Agentic DraCor and the Art of Docstring Engineering

Evaluating MCP-empowered LLM Usage of the DraCor API

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Abstract

This paper reports on the implementation and evaluation of a Model Context Protocol (MCP) server for DraCor, enabling Large Language Models (LLM) to autonomously interact with the DraCor API. We conducted experiments focusing on tool selection and application by the LLM, employing a qualitative approach that includes systematic observation of prompts to understand how LLMs behave when using MCP tools, evaluating “Tool Correctness”, “Tool-Calling Efficiency”, and “Tool-Use Reliability”. Our findings highlight the importance of “Docstring Engineering”, defined as reflexively crafting tool documentation to optimize LLM-tool interaction. Our experiments demonstrate both the promise of agentic AI for research in Computational Literary Studies and the essential infrastructure development needs for reliable Digital Humanities infrastructures.

Keywords

Model Context Protocol, MCP, Large Language Model, LLM, Claude, Evaluation, Computational Literary Studies, Computational Drama Analysis, DraCor

*there is software that ... treats other web sites as just
... another function it can call to get things done*
Aaron Swartz (2013): A Programmable Web

1. How to Do Things With MCP Servers. Introduction

1.1. Making DraCor machine-actionable

According to its own claim, the API-driven DraCor platform aims to make literary corpora “machine-actionable” (Börner and Trilcke, 2023, p. 7), showcasing the concept of “Programmable Corpora” (Fischer et al. 2019; Börner and Trilcke 2023; Börner et al. 2025; cf. Swartz 2013). That is, machines would interact with corpora through program code, as exemplified by the Python and R wrappers “pydracor” and “rdracor” (Sluyter-Gäthje et al., 2023).

Now, DraCor is gaining a new dimension with the current third wave of AI evolution, known as the transition to “Agentic AI” (Huang, 2025). In the agential paradigm, machines are currently being enabled to more or less autonomously perform concrete actions. A much-promising development in this direction is the “Model Context Protocol” (MCP) introduced by Anthropic (2024), which enables a Large Language Model (LLM) to do various things with the help of a server and the functionalities implemented there (Hou et al., 2025). What can be understood as agential empowerment of LLMs means, in Anthropic’s current concept, that MCP enables the LLM to “perform actions through your server.” (Anthropic, 2025a) In this sense, servers can “expose executable functionality to clients” via the MCP; these functionalities are called “tools.” (Anthropic, 2025b) These “tools are designed to be

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model-controlled, meaning that tools are exposed from servers to clients with the intention of the AI model being able to automatically invoke them (with a human in the loop to grant approval)” (Anthropic, 2025b).

Against the backdrop of this concept of “dynamic tool invocation”, it is the infrastructural expansion in the form of an MCP server that promises to make DraCor “machine-actionable” in the full sense of the word. This will enable LLMs to interact with DraCor and its API more or less autonomously. The way to achieve this is to empower LLMs to use tools specifically tailored to DraCor.

1.2. An Example

Let’s play through an example: Have you ever asked yourself: “What is the most quantitatively complex German-language play by a female author?”¹ Probably not. It may even be a research question that no one has ever asked. So let’s pose the question to one of the current generative AI systems, such as ChatGPT or Claude: Usually, the system will perform a series of web searches and give an “interesting” but empirically more or less unfounded answer. The result becomes a matter of interpretation: for example, in a test in mid-July 2025, ChatGPT (“4o”) suggested that Elfriede Jelinek’s “Die Schutzbefohlenen” (2013) was the most quantitatively complex play; Claude (“Sonnet 4”), on the other hand, suggested “Sapientia” by Hrotsvitha of Gandersheim (10th century).

Both models gave good, albeit predominantly qualitative reasons. However, if the question is posed to an agentic empowered LLM (in this case “Claude Sonnet 4”) that can access the DraCor API with the help of tools, something fascinating happens: Once the model – using a tool that allows to request information from the DraCor API `corpora` endpoint – has gained an overview of the corpora in DraCor, it searches (analyzing data provided by a different tool for a different API endpoint) for female authors in the German-language drama corpus (“GerDraCor”), then it identifies network metrics that can be understood as indicators of complexity. On this basis, it creates a ranking of 20 plays, sorted according to what the model postulates as a “complexity score” (using the formula `network size x ln(edges)`). Using data from the DraCor API, this formula and some further API queries, Claude² finally arrives at this result³:

[...]

Based on my comprehensive analysis of the DraCor German Drama Corpus, the most quantitatively complex play written by a woman in German-language drama is “Pfeffer-Rösel oder Die Frankfurter Messe im Jahre 1297” by Charlotte Birch-Pfeiffer.

Here are the key complexity metrics that establish this play as the most complex:

Network Complexity:

- 40 characters - the highest network size among female-authored plays
- 323 network edges - an extremely high number of character interactions
- Complexity score: 231.11 (calculated as $network\ size \times \ln(edges)$)

Structural Complexity:

¹Cf. the documentation at

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/0_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

²Claude Sonnet 4 (claude-sonnet-4-20250514), Desktop Version (“Claude for Mac”, Version 0.11.6), 2025-07-14, Style: Normal, Extended Thinking: off, Web Search: on, using DraCor MCP Server (Börner, 2025a), v1.0.0-alpha.2, <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp/releases/tag/v1.0.0-alpha.2>. Unfortunately, this version of our MCP server no longer works with the current versions of Claude Desktop (“Claude for Mac”, version 0.12.55). Rapid development cycles of AI tools pose a challenge to reproducibility and may require specific combinations of versions. For current compatibility information and installation instructions, consult the DraCor MCP Server repository README: <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp>.

³The text cited here is from the chat. The documentation of the chat (cf. footnote 1) differs from this conversational text, though the results are the same. – By the way, despite numerous attempts, we were not able to get the LLM to choose the way of processing and to provide the answer reported here again.

- Average degree: 16.15 (characters interact with many others on average)
- Network density: 0.414 (41.4% of all possible character connections are realized)
- Multiple acts and elaborate staging with crowd scenes, imperial court scenes, and complex social hierarchies

[...]

Of course, this conclusion can be debated: The complexity measure used by the agentic enabled LLM only represents a very limited aspect of literary complexity. And neither the play by Jelinek nor the one by Hrotsvitha of Gandersheim, which were suggested by the non-agentic LLMs, are currently part of GerDraCor, for example. And even when we stick to our actual corpus, the answer is wrong: Claude missed the most complex play of a female writer in GerDraCor. With a complexity score of $91 \times \ln(2010) = 692.14$, Lilly Braun's play "Mutter Maria"⁴ (1913) would have been the correct answer according to its own metric.

However, none of these objections is decisive at this point. What is more important is that the approach of the LLM, the strategy it chooses to solve the task and also its answer are committed to the empirical paradigm of CLS – even if the LLM operates erroneously in this paradigm, e.g., because it used an inadequate method to identify all female authors in the corpus. The answers we received from the non-agentic enabled LLMs, on the other hand, primarily follow the hermeneutic-interpretative paradigm of traditional literary studies. Against this background, in our research we – at least implicitly – work on and reflect on the possibility that the use of AI architectures (such as an MCP server) could be a way of merging the empirical paradigm that CLS have developed over the past decade with the hermeneutic machine LLMs tend to be.

1.3. About the following article

As the example already illustrates, we have recently been experimentally implementing an MCP server for DraCor, inspired by an MCP prototype proposed by Stijn Meijers (Meijers, 2025). As far as we can see, this is the first ever implementation of an MCP server for Computational Literary Studies (CLS). With a very recent release date in November 2024, it is not surprising that current status descriptions of AI in the CLS do not yet know anything about the MCP (Bode and Bradley 2025, Akazawa and Gius 2025). But even a search for the term "Model Context Protocol" in Google Scholar only returned over 400 hits as of July 2025.

In the course of this paper, we present first insights from our implementation by describing the DraCor MCP prototype developed by Ingo Börner 2025a (chapter 2). We then attempt to evaluate the performance of the interactions between humans, LLM, MCP server and DraCor API (our "agentic chain of actions", fig. 1) through a series of experiments (chapter 3). We also want to gain a better understanding of how good these systems are. Where do they go wrong, and what kinds of mistakes do they make?

Our approach to evaluation attempts to take into account the fact that our "agentic chain" is a complex, non-deterministic and, in this respect, potentially fragile and, in any case, multifaceted form of human-machine interaction. In particular, we are interested in how the LLM behaves when using the tools provided by the MCP server: Does it pick the right tool? Does it utilise the tool correctly, efficiently, appropriately? How does it combine tools? As we learned during our experiments, these questions only refer in small parts to aspects of LLM behaviour that can (currently) be formalised and, in the best case, evaluated automatically. On the contrary, it seems more appropriate to pursue an evaluation grounded in something akin to behavioural research: What we have been able to observe and describe so far is, most of all, the interaction of the LLM with our MCP server. This is what we aim to evaluate.

In the light of these considerations, we will only occasionally select a quantitative-formalised approach in the evaluations of the experiments discussed in chapter 3. Instead, we will attempt to develop

⁴<https://dracor.org/id/ger000573>

Figure 1: The agentic chain of DraCor MCP pipeline

qualitative-phenomenological descriptions of tool behaviour. One aspect of our phenomenological method is that we will occasionally try to create (through prompts or other parameterisations) slightly varying situations for the tool behaviour of the LLM, mimicking Edmund Husserl’s method of “eidetic variation” (Husserl, 2012).

From the perspective shaped by developing digital tools for computational research using DraCor, particularly the DraCor API, we are led to ask whether we are gaining reliable co-workers in the AI agents that are ever more joining us in our work. Are LLMs, empowered by MCP servers for tool use, perhaps the interface of the future for working with resources such as DraCor? How do LLMs operate with the DraCor API? How do they use tools to work with DraCor? To what extent is the DraCor API becoming a resource predominantly (mis)used by LLMs, rather than one being employed through carefully crafted, purposeful queries?

Before presenting our initial attempts to address these questions from the perspective of research in CLS infrastructures, we have to include two disclaimers.

First, it is important to emphasize that our test setups depend on various factors: On the capabilities of the LLM, for sure, but at the same time also on the MCP server prototype that we have built (and which could certainly be built differently), on the possibilities and the limitations of the DraCor API – and also on the prompts with which we test, whereby prompt engineering, i.e. the optimization of the prompts, is explicitly not the goal of our test setup.

Second, our technical setup is currently inadequate. While the goal would be to conduct the experiments via API access to an LLM and based on a public MCP server, the following setup, as explained in chapter 2, is based on a locally running (but publicly available) MCP server and the desktop chat interface of Anthropic’s Claude model. It is our goal to gradually develop the technological stack further over the next few months and to work on an advanced infrastructure (including, among other things, the possibility of high-frequency re-runs of the experiments and better documentation) for the final version of this paper.

2. Implementing the DraCor MCP Server

The DraCor MCP Server⁵ (Börner, 2025a) is implemented using the Python package `fastmcp`⁶, which provides a framework for creating Model Context Protocol (MCP) servers through decorated Python functions. At its core, the implementation approach emphasizes comprehensive documentation as the primary mechanism for LLM interaction, i.e. tool discovery and use. Each tool is essentially a Python function decorated with `@mcp.tool()`, where the docstring⁷ serves as the crucial interface documentation that provides the LLM with information on the tool’s purpose, parameters, and expected usage patterns.

The DraCor MCP Server’s design principle assumes that the quality and comprehensiveness of tool documentation is crucial for the LLM’s ability to effectively utilize the available functionality. This approach reflects a broader understanding that in MCP architectures, documentation is not merely auxiliary information but becomes an active part of the system’s user interface. The extensive docstrings, combined with type annotations and parameter descriptions, form a semantic contract between the tools and the LLM, enabling autonomous tool selection and parameter passing.

Beyond the 47 core tools currently defined, the DraCor MCP server also defines two resources, though the current implementation primarily focuses on tools due to the limitations of Anthropic’s Claude Desktop⁸ interface. Two key resources are maintained: a list of corpora fetched via Distributed Text Services (DTS, cf. Almas et al. 2023), (`DraCor:resource_corpora_via_dts`) and a corpus registry JSON file⁹ containing comprehensive metadata about all available corpora, including their development status and availability (`DraCor:resource_corpus_registry`). In Claude Desktop the resources need to be manually added to the context of the chat.

2.1. Direct API Endpoint Wrappers

The largest category consists of tools that provide direct wrappers around DraCor API endpoints, offering unfiltered access to the underlying REST API functionality. These tools maintain a one-to-one correspondence with API endpoints, preserving the full data structure and metadata provided by the DraCor system. Examples include `DraCor:get_corpus`, `DraCor:get_play_metadata`, `DraCor:get_play_characters`, and `DraCor:get_spoken_text`. Similarly, Wiki-data integration tools like `DraCor:get_plays_with_characters_by_wikidata_id` and `DraCor:get_author_info_from_wikidata` provide access to external identifier-based search and author information retrieval.

A subset of tools in this category provides selective access to specific API endpoints rather than complete endpoint wrapping. The DTS integration tools such as `DraCor:get_citable_units_via_dts` and `DraCor:get_plaintext_of_citable_unit_via_dts` exemplify this approach, offering access to fine-grained textual segments, e.g. acts and scenes, and citation capabilities while implementing selective exposure of the DTS endpoint functionality. This category of tools represents the foundational layer of functionality, ensuring that all core DraCor capabilities remain accessible through the MCP interface.

2.2. Helper Tools

A significant subset of tools addresses the practical limitations of working with large-scale corpus data in LLM contexts. These “helper tools” implement data filtering, chunking, and pagination strategies. Tools such as `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata_paged_helper`,

⁵The discussed version is 1.0.0-alpha.2, see <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp/releases/tag/v1.0.0-alpha.2>.

⁶<https://gofastmcp.com>

⁷<https://peps.python.org/pep-0257/#what-is-a-docstring>

⁸<https://claude.ai/download>

⁹<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-registry/blob/main/corpora.json>

`DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper`, and `DraCor:get_corpus_contents_paged_helper` exemplify this category.

The design strategy behind these tools recognizes that simple data retrieval strategies often fail when working with corpora containing hundreds of plays and extensive metadata, e.g. the “metadata table”¹⁰ for corpora like FreDraCor. The helper tools implement flexible selection of batch sizes and prioritize essential metadata fields. In the docstring, annotations include a reference to the respective API wrapper tool and vice versa.

```
"""Get extended metadata of all plays in a corpus

Data is retrieved from the endpoint /corpora/{corpusname}/metadata
If the data on the plays does not fit into the context use the tool `
    get_corpus_metadata_paged_helper` instead,
which allows for retrieving metadata on the plays in batches.

Args:
    corpus_name (str): Identifier of a corpus, e.g. `ger`, `rus`, `als`
"""
```

Listing 1: Docstring of the function that implements the tool `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata`

```
"""Get metadata on all plays in a corpus in batches

Data is retrieved from the endpoint /corpora/{corpusname}/metadata, but in batches.
This normally times out; that is a problem of the API

Args:
    corpus_name (str): Identifier of a corpus, e.g. `ger`, `rus`, `als`
    items_per_page (int): Number of play metadata to retrieve in a batch. Defaults to
        50.
    page (int): Number of page of the results to retrieve in a batch request. Defaults
        to 1 - the first 50 plays.
"""
```

Listing 2: Docstring of the function that implements the tool `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata_paged_helper`

Interestingly, despite the theoretical usefulness of these pagination capabilities, empirical observations suggest that language models rarely make use of batch request features. Instead, they tend to prefer processing complete datasets when possible, and often fail beyond recovery. We will come back to this later.

2.3. Search and Discovery Tools

The DraCor API’s limited native search functionality necessitated the implementation of specialized search tools within the DraCor MCP server. Tools such as

`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_author_helper`, `get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper`, and

`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_year_normalized` provide essential discovery capabilities that extend beyond the basic API functionality. The implementation assumes that the LLM will frequently need to locate specific plays based on partial information, author names or titles of works

¹⁰<https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/fre/metadata>

rather than the exact DraCor identifiers. This category of tools tries to transform the DraCor system from a purely identifier-based access system into a discovery platform based, among others, on entities.

2.4. Administrative and Database Management Tools

The DraCor MCP server includes a complete set of administrative tools that provide write access to the underlying eXist-db database, enabling corpus management and the addition and removal of plays. Tools such as `DraCor:add_corpus`, `DraCor:load_corpus_from_repository`, `DraCor:add_play_to_corpus`, and `DraCor:remove_play_from_corpus` implement the full range of database modification operations available via the DraCor API. Additionally, this category includes quality control tools such as `DraCor:validate_xml_file`, which serves as a helper for ensuring that content meets DraCor’s encoding standards before uploading it to local instances.

While these administrative capabilities are typically restricted in production environments, they prove invaluable for local development and research environments, particularly when used in conjunction with Docker-based DraCor instances (Börner and Trilcke, 2024, pp. 25–31). The implementation of these tools within the MCP framework demonstrates the potential for LLM-mediated database administration, though it also raises important considerations about access control and operation safety that must be carefully managed in production deployments.

2.5. Documentation and System Information Tools

A set of tools provides access to various resources of DraCor system documentation, enabling the LLM to access and relay information about the system’s capabilities, data structures, and encoding standards. Tools such as `DraCor:get_api_feature_list`, `get_openapi_specification`, `get_table_of_contents_from_odd` fall into this category.

This documentation-focused approach recognizes that effective use of a complex Digital Humanities system requires not just data access but also contextual understanding of the data structures, encoding practices, and analytical possibilities (cf. Börner 2025b). By making documentation programmatically accessible, these tools enable dynamic help systems, i.e. supporting users in encoding TEI files, understanding API responses, etc.

2.6. Frontend Access and DraCor Research Integration

A distinctive category of tools provides access to information and functionalities that are primarily available through the DraCor frontend interface, bridging the gap between the API-driven MCP server and the web-based user interface. Two tools exemplify this category: `DraCor:get_dracor_based_research` and `DraCor:get_links_to_playdata_helper`.

The `DraCor:get_dracor_based_research` tool provides programmatic access to the comprehensive list of publications that utilize DraCor resources in their research, information that is typically accessed through the DraCor website’s research documentation.¹¹ This tool enables the LLM to provide users with relevant academic context and citations, supporting literature reviews and helping researchers understand how DraCor data has been employed in scholarly work.

The `get_links_to_playdata_helper` tool generates direct links to various DraCor frontend features and external analytical tools, including the Download Tab (Börner and Trilcke 2023, pp. 75–76) for accessing play data in different formats, and the Tool Tab (Börner et al. 2025, pp. 103–106) which provides connections to external services such as the CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard, Voyant Tools, and Gephi Lite. This tool effectively extends the MCP server’s capabilities beyond direct data access to include guided access to the broader DraCor ecosystem and its integrated external tools.

¹¹<https://dracor.org/doc/research>. The MCP Server provides access to the underlying YAML file <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-frontend/blob/main/public/doc/research.md>.

These tools recognize that while the MCP server provides comprehensive API access, the DraCor frontend offers additional visualization, analysis, and export capabilities that complement the programmatic access to the data via the API. By providing structured access to these frontend features, the tools enable seamless workflow integration between conversational AI interaction and traditional web-based digital humanities tools.

2.7. A (First) Step Back: Some Challenges

Several significant implementation challenges shaped the final architecture of the DraCor MCP Server. The most prominent challenge involves managing the tension between comprehensive data access and practical usability within limited LLM context windows and processing constraints. The solution involved implementing multiple access strategies for the same underlying data: direct access tools for complete datasets, filtered tools for essential information only, and paginated tools for incremental access.

Another critical design decision involved the balance between tool specificity and generality. While highly specific tools provide optimal user experience for common tasks, they also make tool selection for the LLM much harder. The implemented solution favors a moderate level of tool specificity, providing dedicated tools for common operations while maintaining more general tools for edge cases and exploratory workflows.

The administrative tools present perhaps the most complex implementation challenge, requiring careful balance between functionality and safety. The current implementation assumes a trusted environment with appropriate access controls managed at the infrastructure level, but production deployments would require additional authentication and authorization mechanisms integrated into the MCP framework itself.

3. Experiments

As the documentation in Chapter 2 makes clear, the DraCor MCP Server prototype we developed is a multi-faceted test system that for example also includes admin tools for the DraCor ecosystem. In the following evaluation (which will certainly be the first in a whole series of evaluations), we want to focus on those tools that directly enable the LLM to interact autonomously with DraCor’s knowledge resources, i.e. those that are potentially most relevant for research. In our experiments, we therefore concentrate on prompting queries that we expect will trigger the use of tools from the groups “direct API endpoint wrapper” (chapter 2.1), “helper tools” (chapter 2.2) and “search and discovery tools” (chapter 2.3). For all experiments, we used the setup already mentioned above,¹² with Claude Sonnet 4 as LLM.

As initial explorations have shown that even queries of medium complexity can lead to very long sequences of tool invocations (which on the one hand are very demanding to evaluate and on the other hand often cannot be evaluated at all because the maximum length for conversations in the LLM is reached), we have – for this very first evaluation – tried to formulate queries that are as simple as possible. At the same time, we wanted the queries to cover a certain spectrum of research questions, epistemic objects to which they are directed and, finally, ways of writing prompts. Against this background, we determined that we wanted to learn about and evaluate (and in a sense: look at the essence of) LLM’s ability to use tools through queries, which we (eidetically) varied with regard to the following aspects:

- **scope:** we target queries on data about a play, a corpus or several corpora
- **terminological variation:** queries can be in (more or less) “normal” language or use specialised terms from drama research or literary theory

¹²Claude Sonnet 4 (claude-sonnet-4-20250514), Desktop Version (“Claude for Mac”, Version 0.11.6), 2025-07-14, Style: Normal, Extended Thinking: off, Web Search: on, using DraCor MCP Server (Börner, 2025a), v1.0.0-alpha.2, <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp/releases/tag/v1.0.0-alpha.2>.

- **DraCor specificity variation:** DraCor itself has its own language: corpora have names (and abbreviations), plays have short titles (we call them “slugs”), and identifiers, values and features have their own labels etc.; this DraCor-specific language can be used explicitly in queries
- **canonicity variation:** we expect an LLM to ‘know’ more about canonical texts than about little-known texts; we therefore vary our queries selectively so that we specifically ask queries about almost unknown texts¹³

Table 1
Experiments

ID (Set-No.)	Prompt	Scope	Terminology Variation	DraCor Specificity Variation	Canonicity Variation
1-1	What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod?	play	0	0	0
1-2	What is the number of dramatis personae in Dantons Tod?	play	1	0	0
1-3	What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod in GerDraCor?	play	0	1	0
1-4	What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod (buechner-dantons-tod) in GerDraCor?	play	0	1	0
1-5	What is the number of characters in Der Nollhart?	play	0	0	1
2-1	What is the mean number of characters in French Drama?	corpus	0	0	-
3-1	Which drama corpus has the highest mean number of characters?	corpora	0	0	-
3-2	Which drama corpus covers the widest time range?	corpora	0	0	-
4-1	How does the percentage of female speakers in German drama change over time?	corpus	0	0	-
4-2	How does the mean percentage of female speakers in Swedish drama change over time?	corpus	0	0	-
4-3	How does the gender distribution in Swedish drama change over time?	corpus	1	0	-
4-4	How does the percentage of female speakers in ItaDraCor change over time?	corpus	0	1	-
5-1	Who is the most important character in Emilia Galotti?	play	0	0	0
5-2	Who is the protagonist in Emilia Galotti?	play	1	0	0
5-3	Which character is quantitatively most dominant in Emilia Galotti?	play	1	0	0
5-4	Who is the protagonist in Die entführte Dose?	play	1	0	1

¹³As a proxy for the classification as “non-canonical”, we take the existence or non-existence of an article on the play in the German-language Wikipedia. There are no Wikipedia articles on either “Der Nollhart” (experiment 1-5) or “Die entführte Dose” (experiment 5-4 as of July 2025).

Table 1 lists the queries that we have prompted during our experiments and notes which of the variations listed above are active in each instance. We have grouped the queries into 5 sets:

- **set 1:** queries that target data for one play (5 variants)
- **set 2:** queries that target statistics for a corpus (1 variant)
- **set 3:** queries that target a comparison of statistics for multiple corpora (2 variants)
- **set 4:** queries that target the combination of data for one corpus (4 variants)
- **set 5:** queries that target the application of a literary concept (“protagonist”) on one play (4 variants)

For each experiment, first the query was prompted. The result of this first query was then evaluated. In addition, a documentation prompt was entered,¹⁴ which resulted in an artefact in the form of a Markdown file documenting the experiment.¹⁵ Each query was then run a further 4 times using the ‘Retry’ function (‘With no changes’). The outputs were analysed for the reliability score (see below).

A research discussion on the evaluation of MCP servers is just emerging. Recently, Gao et al. (2025) proposed a multi-dimensional benchmark with the MCP-RADAR, but the paper (and the associated code) - like almost all publications on MCPs - is currently still without review. For this reason, we orient our evaluation on the conceptual thoughts on LLM agent evaluation by Vongthongsri (2025), as these were developed in close connection with the already published LLM benchmark framework DeepEval (provided by Confident AI).

For evaluating the tool usage of so called “tool calling agents”, Vongthongsri suggests looking at two aspects: “**Tool Correctness**, which determines whether the right tools were called, and **Tool-Calling Efficiency**, which evaluates whether the tools were used in the most efficient way to achieve the desired results” (Vongthongsri, 2025). While these aspects focus specifically on tool use, with regard to the entire agentic workflow, the aspect of **Task Completion**, among others, also needs to be evaluated. Taking these aspects as a starting point, we define the following evaluation criteria:

- **Correct Answer:** If the LLM comes to an answer and this answer is correct, we confirm “task completion”. As a reference for evaluating the correctness of the answers, we have carried out the necessary queries and calculations ourselves.¹⁶
- **Tool Correctness:** If the LLM decides to use a tool (tool decision) and also uses the tools with which the query can be handled, we attest “tool correctness”.
- **Tool-Calling Efficiency:** For some queries there are several ways of processing. It also happens that the LLM first chooses a path that does not lead to the result and then looks for a new path. We evaluate this behaviour as “tool-calling efficiency”. If the LLM chooses the shortest processing path, we assign the value ‘5 = perfect’. We deduct one point for each dead end and for each more complicated processing path up to the value ‘1 = very bad’.

In view of the volatility in the choice of processing paths noted during testing and the subsequent unreliability of the tool use, we add reliability score.

¹⁴The text of the documentation prompt is: “Document the entire chat in a Markdown file. Include a header with relevant metadata (e.g., settings used). For each step, provide information about the tools and DraCor API endpoints involved. Do not summarize. Focus on documenting the steps taken and the data used to answer the initial question. Simply record the conversation and all tool usage and analyses performed.” – As our experiments show, there is still some room for optimisation here as part of the prompt engineering. In particular, the requested metadata should be specified more precisely and the format should be more formalised. There is currently still too much variance in the documentation generated.

¹⁵Cf. the repository on

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/tree/0d64119d69563627e0af7b873bd5506c1784690f/2025_cda-preprint_documentation

¹⁶Cf. the Jupyter Notebook by Henny Sluyter-Gäthje:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp/blob/main/evaluation/MCP-Evaluation_Paper-Version.ipynb

- **Tool-Use Reliability:** As outlined above, we repeated the first experiment, which formed the basis of the evaluation, four times (retry with no changes). If the basic solution (Tool Correctness) and the result (Correct Answer) are identical, we certify a reliable repetition. The maximum value is therefore 5/5 (always the same general processing path and the same answer after 5 attempts)

In the following, we document each experiment individually. At the end, we provide a summarised overview in Table 2.

3.1. Number of Characters of a Play

1-1 What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; one data point; can be processed by using two tools

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpora` –
`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper` –
`DraCor:get_play_characters`

Correct Answer: yes (“103”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 4 (minus 1 for not using the information provided by

`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper`
 but using `DraCor:get_play_characters` as an additional tool)

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/0d64119d69563627e0af7b873bd5506c1784690f/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/1-1_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: The model uses internal ”knowledge” to pick the German drama corpus. The model does not understand the value for ”network size”, which can be taken from the response received by `DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper`, as a value for the number of characters. So it counts the list containing the play’s characters in the response of the `/corpora/corpusname/plays/playname/characters` endpoint provided by the tool.

1-2 What is the number of dramatis personae in Dantons Tod?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; one data point; using terminology variation (“dramatis personae”); can be processed by using two tools

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpora` –
`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper` –
`DraCor:get_play_characters`

Correct Answer: yes (“103”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 4 (minus 1 for not using the information provided by

`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper`
 but using `DraCor:get_play_characters` as an additional tool)

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/0d64119d69563627e0af7b873bd5506c1784690f/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/1-2_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: Same as 1-1

1-3 What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod in GerDraCor?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; one data point; using DraCor specificity variation (“GerDraCor”); can be processed by using one tool

Tool Chain Used:

`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper` -
`DraCor:get_play_characters`

Correct Answer: yes (“103”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 4 (minus 1 for not using the information provided by

`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper`
but using `DraCor:get_play_characters` as an additional tool

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/0d64119d69563627e0af7b873bd5506c1784690f/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/1-3_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: Same as 1-1

1-4 What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod (buechner-dantons-tod) in GerDraCor?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; one data point; using DraCor specificity variation (“GerDraCor”; “buechner-dantons-tod”); can be processed by using one tool

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_play_characters`

Correct Answer: yes (“103”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 5

Tool-Use Reliability: 1/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/0d64119d69563627e0af7b873bd5506c1784690f/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/1-4_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: Strangely enough, Claude makes counting errors when repeating the processing of the query: Although it obtains the same character list with 103 entries as in the first call, it returns the results “101”, “93”, “100”, “93” in the four repetitions. According to the LLM, the cause of the problem is that it did not actually count, but answered the question using its internal ‘knowledge’ despite having the data from DraCor.¹⁷

¹⁷The specific wording of the response is: “The cause of my error was that I made an assumption and stated a number without actually counting the entries in the character list. I should have either 1. Counted the entries systematically, or 2. Used code to count them programmatically. Thank you for the correction - this is a good reminder to be more careful with data

1-5 What is the number of characters in Der Nollhart?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; one data point; canonicity variation; can be processed by using two tools

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpora` -
`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper` -
`DraCor:get_play_metadata`

Correct Answer: yes (“14”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 4 (minus 1 for not using the information provided by

`DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper`
but using `DraCor:get_play_metadata` as an additional tool)

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/0d64119d69563627e0af7b873bd5506c1784690f/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/1-5_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: Claude uses a similar approach to 1-1, but relies on a different tool (`DraCor:get_play_metadata`) to retrieve data on the characters. Interestingly, a second tool is used, because the result of the documentation prompt suggests that Claude already considered the value of the network size as an indicator of the number of characters (“Network size: 14 (indicating 14 characters)”), but still relied on counting the objects in the response of the second tool used to arrive at its final correct answer.

3.2. Mean Number of Characters of a Corpus

2-1 What is the mean number of characters in French Drama?

Comment on the Query: scope: corpus; two data points; can be processed by using one tool

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpus` -
`DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper` -
`DraCor:get_corpus_metadata` -
`DraCor:get_corpus_metadata_paged_helper` -
`DraCor:get_corpora`

Correct Answer: yes (“9.19”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 3 (minus 1 for the choice of a more complicated processing path; -1 for the fact that the more complicated path leads to a dead end)

Tool-Use Reliability: 2/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/2-1-1_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

analysis and to verify counts rather than making assumptions. The DraCor API returned a complete list of all 103 characters in the play, and I failed to count them accurately.”

Notes: FreDraCor is currently the largest corpus in DraCor, which poses some problems. The easiest way to process the query is to use `DraCor:get_corpora` to load basic corpus metadata, including the number of plays and the number of characters in the entire corpus. In the end, this is also the path that the model chooses. Before that, it tries to fetch the corpus metadata via various metadata tools, but either fails due to the file size (“Data exceeded maximum length limit (1,048,576 characters)”) or cancels the plan to batch process the paged metadata. It is astonishing, though, that in the experiment documented, the processing path using the information in `DraCor:get_corpora` is used after all. However, the choice of this path is not very stable: this path was only chosen in 2 out of 5 cases. More frequently, Claude chooses a sampling approach as an alternative processing path. In an experiment also documented here, using this way (and the corresponding tool chain) Claude came to the following conclusion based on a sample of 320 plays: “The mean number of characters in French drama is approximately 7.44 characters per play.”¹⁸

3.3. Comparison of Mean Number of Characters and Time Range of Publication Dates in Different Corpora

3-1 Which drama corpus has the highest mean number of characters?

Comment on the Query: scope: corpora; 26 (corpora) x 2 data points; can be processed by using one tool

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpora`

Correct Answer: yes (“GerShDraCor: 39.39 characters per play”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 5

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/3-1_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: Nothing to note. Straightforward and reliable way of processing the query.

3-2 Which drama corpus covers the widest time range?

Comment on the Query: scope: corpora; 26 (corpora) x 2 data points; can be processed with 27 API calls

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpora` – `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata` – `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata_paged_helper` – `DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper` –

¹⁸https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/2-1-2_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

```
DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper -  
DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper -  
DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper -  
DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper -  
DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper -
```

Correct Answer: partly, i.e. 0.5 (answer is “French corpus spans 727 years”; “French” is correct, “727” is wrong – “847” is the correct answer)

Tool Correctness: partly, i.e. 0.5 (it uses the right tool, but uses it improperly)

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 3 (minus 2 for two dead ends, one due to response size errors, the another one due incorrect tool use)

Tool-Use Reliability: 2/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/3-2_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: While this query can be processed in a simple Python script with 13 lines of code, for example, it is practically unanswerable for Claude in the current setup. There are two reasons for this: Claude cannot process the metadata files (`DraCor:get_corpus_metadata`) for medium and large corpora due to their size (“Response exceeded maximum length (1,048,576 characters”); at the same time, Claude refuses to use batch processing to process all pages of the paged metadata that it could retrieve for medium and large corpora using `DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper`. After these two approaches proved to be dead ends for Claude itself, it again chooses a sampling approach, whereby it quickly switches to always retrieving the first page and the last page using `DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper`. In doing so, it makes the assumption that the data sets are ordered chronologically, i.e. that the oldest play can be found on the first page and the newest play on the last page. However, this is a false assumption; the paginated list is not in chronological order. As a result, the sample created by Claude does not capture the time range of the corpus, or at best only by chance. In addition, it does not query the metadata for all corpora. Accordingly, the result is wrong. On top of this, Claude regularly chooses other ways of processing that also do not lead to correct results. So the reliability of the chosen approach is also low.

3.4. Percentage of Female Speakers over Time

4-1 How does the percentage of female speakers in German drama change over time?

Comment on the Query: scope: corpus; 737 (plays) x 2 data points; can be processed using two tools

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpus` -
`DraCor:get_corpus_metadata` -
`DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper` -
`DraCor:get_play_characters` - `DraCor:get_play_characters` -
`DraCor:get_play_characters` - `DraCor:get_play_characters` -
`DraCor:get_play_characters`

Correct Answer: no (see documentation)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 4 (minus 1 for the metadata dead end)

Tool-Use Reliability: 2/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/4-1_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: Claude's problem of reading the metadata files for medium and large corpora via `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata` is known from the previous experiments ("Response exceeded maximum length"). We have also already noted that Claude then unfortunately regularly chooses a more or less informed sampling approach that is never valid from a scholarly point of view. In this case, Claude uses `DraCor:get_play_characters` to retrieve data for five selected plays. The result is inadequate considering the variety of plays in the corpus.

4-2 How does the mean percentage of female speakers in Swedish drama change over time?

Comment on the Query: scope: corpus; 68 (plays) x 2 data points; can be processed using two tools

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpus` - `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata`

Correct Answer: yes (see documentation)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 5

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/4-2_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: Nothing to note. Straightforward and reliable way of processing the query.

4-3 How does the gender distribution in Swedish drama change over time?

Comment on the Query: scope: corpus; 68 (plays) x 2 data points; terminology variation ("gender"); can be processed using two tools

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpus` - `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata`

Correct Answer: yes (see documentation)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 5

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/4-3_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: The question is more open than 4-2 as it is not only tailored to female characters but to the comparison of the gender. It also does not specify the basis on which the gender

distribution should be analyzed. Claude analyses the characters as well as the authors of the plays in SweDraCor. It also combines the two aspects by analysing how many female and male characters there are per female and male author. All in all, a straightforward and reliable way of processing the query.

4-4 How does the percentage of female speakers in ItaDraCor change over time?

Comment on the Query: scope: corpus; 157 (plays) x 2 data points; using DraCor specificity variation (“ItaDraCor”); can be processed using two tools

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpora` – `DraCor:get_corpus_metadata` – `DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper` – `DraCor:get_play_characters` – `DraCor:get_play_characters` – `DraCor:get_play_characters`

Correct Answer: no (see documentation)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 4 (minus 1 for not using the metadata file)

Tool-Use Reliability: 2/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/4-4_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: Again, Claude refuses to process the metadata file. The workaround via `DraCor:get_minimal_data_of_plays_of_corpus_helper` and `DraCor:get_play_characters` then makes sense, but it’s quite cumbersome and again Claude chooses a sampling approach that does not lead to reliable results. In the case of repetitions, Claude sometimes (i.e. three times) chooses a more efficient processing path in which it actually analyses the metadata file, but even then, not all plays in the corpus are taken into account.

3.5. Catch the Protagonist

5-1 Who is the most important character in Emilia Galotti?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; number of data points depends on the operationalisation; four tools could be relevant

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_play_characters` – `DraCor:get_play_metrics`

Correct Answer: yes (“Marinelli” – however, this depends on the interpretation, which Claude also states itself from time to time)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 5

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/5-1_

DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: The model pulls data from endpoints that are important for the answer. It would be conceivable to obtain additional data via `DraCor:get_play_metadata` and `DraCor:get_spoken_text_by_characters`. This is not done. When it comes to the repetitions, in some cases Claude uses the `Dracor:get_play_network` tool either in addition to or as an alternative to `DraCor:get_play_metrics`. The result remains the same.

5-2 Who is the protagonist in Emilia Galotti?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; number of data points depends on the operationalisation; using terminology variation (“protagonist”); four tools could be relevant

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_play_characters`

Correct Answer: yes (“Emilia” – however, this depends on the interpretation)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 5

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/5-2_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: In this case, Claude limits itself to the data provided by `DraCor:get_play_characters`. Although this approach makes sense, it lacks dimensions that could be introduced by using other tools. Nevertheless, the answer is based on plausible arguments. The effect of terminological variation should be highlighted here. Claude reliably distinguishes between the most important character (which is primarily defined on a quantitative basis) and the protagonist, whose status is primarily based on qualitative arguments. Again, there is almost no variation in the repetitions.

5-3 Which character is quantitatively most dominant in Emilia Galotti?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; number of data points depends on the operationalisation; using terminology variation (“quantitatively most dominant”, cf. Pfister 1991: 165); four tools could be relevant

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_play_metadata` – `DraCor:get_play_metrics` – `DraCor:get_spoken_text_by_characters`

Correct Answer: yes (“Marinelli”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 5

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/5-3_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: In this case, Claude makes use of diverse data and thus endeavours to

make a complex, multi-perspective judgement. The additional use of the tool `DraCor:get_spoken_text_by_characters` should be emphasised in particular, as it adds a further dimension that supports the argumentation. However, in the case of three repetitions, Claude restricts itself to the `DraCor:get_play_metrics` tool; in the case of one repetition, it also uses `DraCor:get_play_characters`. However, the answer remains identical, even if it is less extensively backed up with data.

5-4 Who is the protagonist in Die entführte Dose?

Comment on the Query: scope: play; number of data points depends on the operationalisation; using terminology variation (“protagonist”); canonicity variation; four tools could be relevant

Tool Chain Used: `DraCor:get_corpora` - `DraCor:get_plays_in_corpus_by_title_helper` - `DraCor:get_play_characters` - `DraCor:get_play_metadata`

Correct Answer: yes (“Foppendorf”)

Tool Correctness: yes

Tool-Calling Efficiency: 5

Tool-Use Reliability: 5/5

Documentation:

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/blob/da9d4230bdb36584469bb26eec40469e2694a27e/2025_cda-preprint_documentation/5-4_DraCor-MCP-Paper_2025-07.md

Notes: A multi-perspective approach to determine protagonism; not all relevant tools are used. The result is nevertheless unquestionable.

4. Overall Results and Discussion

Table 2 aggregates the results of the experiments.

In the end, the overarching interpretation of the results of the experiments depends on what you expect from a system like the one tested. One may be impressed that LLMs can now conduct autonomous research actions which include retrieval of necessary data through an MCP Server (or comparable architectures). But one may also expect such interactions, which always suggest to impart knowledge, to bring a maximum of correctness and reliability – which they do not. In fact, this seems to describe the current state of our system quite well: It seems to be a promise of an infrastructure of the future, but one that is currently still too limited, too unsound, too unwieldy to be considered an infrastructure.

Let’s look at the numbers: 13 out of 16 answers were correct. Incorrect answers were due to problems with processing large amounts of data (and, possibly, and erroneous implementation of a tool)¹⁹, not due to incorrect processing paths (resp. incorrect tool usage).

11 out of 16 answers could be reliably repeated. This is good. However, it also indicates a considerable degree of volatility in certain query settings. And we have not yet been able to identify patterns as to when LLM tool use becomes unreliable - and when it is reliable. This is certainly a major problem when it comes to building future infrastructures for Computational Literary Studies, for example.

Tool correctness, in contrast, is high: in 15 out of 16 experiments, the LLM (also) used the correct tool. This does not mean that it hasn’t used the wrong tools on its processing path. At some point, however,

¹⁹Cf. <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp/issues/8>

Table 2
Results

ID	Prompt	Correct Answer	Tool Correctness	Tool-Calling Efficiency 1 = very bad 5 = perfect	Tool-Use Reliability (X out of 5)
1-1	What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod?	1	1	4	5/5
1-2	What is the number of dramatis personae in Dantons Tod?	1	1	4	5/5
1-3	What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod in GerDraCor?	1	1	4	5/5
1-4	What is the number of characters in Dantons Tod (buechner-dantons-tod) in GerDraCor?	1	1	5	1/5
1-5	What is the number of characters in Der Nollhart?	1	1	4	5/5
2-1	What is the mean number of characters in French Drama?	1	1	3	2/5
3-1	Which drama corpus has the highest mean number of characters?	1	1	5	5/5
3-2	Which drama corpus covers the widest time range?	0.5	0.5	3	2/5
4-2	How does the mean percentage of female speakers in Swedish drama change over time?	1	1	5	5/5
4-3	How does the gender distribution in Swedish drama change over time?	1	1	5	5/5
4-4	How does the percentage of female speakers in ItaDraCor change over time?	0	1	4	2/5
5-1	Who is the most important character in Emilia Galotti?	1	1	5	5/5
5-2	Who is the protagonist in Emilia Galotti?	1	1	5	5/5
5-3	Which character is quantitatively most dominant in Emilia Galotti?	1	1	5	5/5
5-4	Who is the protagonist in Die entführte Dose?	1	1	5	5/5

it (also) used the correct tool. Even then, errors could still occur (see the scores for “Correct Answer”), since even if the LLM used the correct tool, this doesn’t indicate that it used the tool correctly.

Only in half of the cases (in 8 out of 16 experiments) were we able to assign the maximum score of 5/5 for tool efficiency. The mean value is 4.375. The lowest value is 3. That is not so bad. In other words, it is not the case that the LLM is wildly trying out all available tools. However, it is not uncommon for it to initially use the wrong tool or choose a more complicated processing path. From an end user’s point of view, it is particularly disappointing that the LLM does not seem to build up any specialised “tool knowledge”. There is something annoying about watching the LLM repeatedly use a tool that is unsuitable for the task at hand - even though it has already done this incorrectly dozens, if not hundreds of times before. As long as dedicated “tool use knowledge” – i.e. the development of a memory with experiential knowledge of which tool is good or not for which task – does not soon become a

component in LLM architectures, we believe that this problem can be addressed in particular through comprehensive and carefully curated docstrings (as descriptions of the possible uses of tools, their limitations, their skilful handling, their idiosyncrasies, and the tricks needed to use them wisely, etc.). We will come back to this idea of docstring engineering later.

While the lack of ‘tool use knowledge’ that we frequently noticed in our experimental setup could be an architectural problem of the current LLM systems, two other problems have their roots in the restrictions on performance of the actual LLM interfaces. These interfaces we currently use to interact with the major commercial LLMs are geared towards the average customer. As a result, the reason for most of the errors and problems in our experiments was,

- first, the very fast reaching of the “maximum length limit” for data and,
- second, the refusal of the LLM to process batch queries.

Both tasks are actually computationally trivial. The resources required are minimal. Basically, it would be trivial even for Claude to produce a code artifact that solves these tasks computationally. But LLMs, like Claude, are a commercial mass product that works with extremely severe limitations, especially in terms of computing capacity. This considerably restricts the LLM’s ability to act as a research assistant. The tactics apparently (in whatever way) implemented in Claude to use a sampling approach for computationally intensive activities are inadequate, and this not only because Claude does not master any valid sampling methods out of the box, as far as we see.

In addition to these conclusions (some of which relate very generally to the current status of the LLMs), we can derive some further insights from the specific setup of our experiments. Here, the domain-specific tasks that our MCP server has to process needs to be mentioned. In order to better understand the way in which the MCP server processes these domain-specific tasks, we have made some variations to our queries. On these variations, we can make the following observations:

- The use of terminology (e.g. “protagonist” or “gender”) makes a difference in individual cases, but in any case leads to different answers. The extent to which LLMs have a kind of terminological knowledge, also with regard to literary studies, is still to be researched (cf. Jannidis et al. 2025).
- The use of DraCor-specific vocabulary increases the efficiency of tool use. Simply put, the LLM knows much faster what exactly is meant when using the “dialect of the resource”. Here we see great potential for docstring optimisation. Furthermore, this observation indicates that working with MCP servers could also be conceptualized as a problem of translation involving specialised languages.
- Finally, it should be noted that when using the DraCor MCP server, there is no noticeable difference between processing queries for canonical plays and non-canonical plays. In contrast, it can be stated without the MCP server that at least in one experiment, queries on non-canonical plays yielded no results at all,²⁰ whereas the LLM was able to provide substantial information on the play when the MCP server was switched on.

While these observations do indeed provide initial insights into the use of MCP servers with CLS resources and infrastructures, it remains fundamentally questionable how stable these findings will be in view of the extremely rapid development in the field of LLM architectures. Irrespective of this, the observations and findings also point to a whole series of desiderata. From an experimental point of view, this includes 1) the professionalisation of the experimental setup (use of Claude’s API, use of a web-based MCP server, more transparent repetition of queries); 2) the further development of the documentation of the experiments, whereby a stricter formalisation should be implemented here,

²⁰Please compare the following chat with the documentation of experiment 5-4:

Query: “Who is the protagonist in Die entführte Dose?”

Answer: “I’m not familiar with a work titled “Die entführte Dose” (The Kidnapped/Abducted Can/Tin). This doesn’t appear to be a well-known German literary work or film that I can identify from my knowledge.”

which, if possible, also enables the automated evaluation of the outputs; 3) the algorithmisation of the evaluation mentioned above, which can hardly be evaluated manually, especially where it becomes a more complex process analysis (“agentic chains”), and collective systematic benchmarking as practiced by NLP/AI community. Finally, 4) it would be interesting to run test strategies against the DraCor API, for example based on XML or TXT files of the plays and linked to the question of how text data behaves in relation to API responses.

5. Outlook: Towards the Art of Docstring Engineering

If we return from the experiments to what was there at the beginning, namely a rapid prototype of an MCP server for Computational Literary Studies resources developed on the basis of DraCor, then at the end of the experiments we must first and foremost realise that our prototype has the potential, but also the need, to be developed further, to be refined, to be extended, to be improved. We will work on that in the next months.

From our point of view and based on the current state of performance of the systems we have tested, this will require something that we have – in the title of this paper – somewhat cheekily labelled as the “art of docstring engineering”. We have already indicated what we mean by this at the beginning of chapter 2. We base this claim on a strong suspicion that docstrings, as stated in chapter 2, “form a semantic contract between the tools and the LLM”. This suspicion arose in the course of building the MCP and conducting the experiments, namely that LLM almost exclusively uses the docstrings of the tools on our MCP server as the basis for deciding which tool(s) to use and the way in which to use them. Of course, the first task of the “docstring engineering” ahead of us is to empirically substantiate our suspicion. As a next step, we therefore envisage a series of experiments in which we use a “docstring variation method” to test what effect docstrings actually have on the tool usage of the LLM.

If these tests confirm our suspicions, we currently expect that four design principles or challenges will be the focus of our “DraCor MCP Docstring Engineering”:

- Docstring Engineering must both clearly identify the simple and unambiguous functions of MCP tools and keep options open for the creative (scholarly) use of these tools.
- It is also against this background that design approaches for docstrings need to be developed that characterise both the functional specificity of a tool as well as its possible embeddedness in agentic chains (‘workflows’?) in which it is connected to other tools, data, artefacts and scripts etc.
- Docstring Engineering has to systematically deal with the performance limitations of current LLM systems.
- It could make sense to document an expanding set of evaluated and reflected best practices (e.g. of entire workflows) for the use of a DraCor MCP-enabled LLM for our scholarly (and our non-scholarly) users – and via the MCP server also provide this documentation to the LLM as context, so that the LLM always already has ideas on how tools can be used meaningfully (and in the best case: creatively).

Docstring engineering might be the issue at hand that helps us tackle at least some of the current challenges in working with agentic systems.

In the end, we believe the potential is remarkable: agent-enabled LLMs, cleverly instructed by the art of docstring engineering, are already beginning to empower humanities scholars without coding skills to interact computationally with the resources of the literary tradition. It might be up to us to make sure that these agents stop talking nonsense.

Data Availability

- DraCor Data can be found here: <https://github.com/dracor-org>
- Documentation of the conversations with Claude can be found here: https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/tree/main/2025_cda-preprint_documentation

Software Availability

- The code repository for DraCor API can be found here: <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api>
- DraCor MCP Server can be found here: <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp> For our experiments in this paper, we used DraCor MCP Server (Börner, 2025a), v1.0.0-alpha.2, <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp/releases/tag/v1.0.0-alpha.2>. Unfortunately, this version of our MCP server no longer works with the current versions of Claude Desktop (“Claude for Mac”, Version 0.12.55). For up-to-date compatibility information and installation instructions, consult the DraCor MCP Server repository README: <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp>.
- Jupyter Notebook for validation can be found in this repo: <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation>

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Henny Sluyter-Gäthje: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft

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Towards a Computational Approach to News-Bringers in Ancient Greek Tragedy

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Abstract

This paper argues that messenger speeches (*Botenberichte*) in the ancient tragedies of Aeschylus, Sophocles, and Euripides have not received the computational attention that they deserve. I first draw attention to this gap by surveying traditional literary approaches to the genre, showing how the definition of “messenger speech” is already problematic from a qualitative perspective. Next, I present a series of initial inquiries into quantitative and computational approaches to messenger speeches, beginning with a stylometric comparison to Homeric epic and proceeding through topic modeling and, using the editions prepared by DraCor, network analysis. In conclusion, I offer a brief discussion of these preliminary findings and potential avenues for further inquiry.

Keywords

tragedy, messenger speeches, Homer, topic modeling, network theory

1. Introduction

The usual history of (so-called) “messenger speeches” in drama begins with Homer: the ancient bard’s narrative *energeia*, to borrow a term from Pseudo-Longinus, is said to animate the off-stage events that news-bringers narrate. Irene J. F. de Jong has perhaps most famously applied a narratological lens to both Homer and tragic messengers, followed a few years later by Barbara Goward and James Barrett their own seminal works on messenger speeches in 2002 [1, 2, 3, 4]. Although de Jong championed the view that messengers are not featureless conduits for the dramatist’s voice but are instead vehicles for bias and selective memory, Barrett then qualified this view by noting that messengers’ narrative effectiveness is inversely proportional to their stage presence: “The messenger’s own body,” he writes, “is implicitly—and explicitly, on occasion—a hindrance, inasmuch as his success as a messenger depends upon his acquiring the invulnerability granted by freedom from bodily constraints” [4, 100]. More recently, Margaret Dickin showed how the roles of messengers in tragedy increased over time and became “vehicles for star-power,” while others, like Felix Budelmann and Evert van Emde Boas, explored how messengers direct the audience’s affective energies [5, 6]. Florence Yoon’s interventions have further disrupted the “category” of messengers by revealing the mistakes of painting with too broad a brush: *angeloi*, messengers proper, and *kerykes*, “heralds,” perform different functions in tragedy [7]. We are clearly on well-traveled ground.

Despite the steady stream of innovative approaches to messenger speeches in tragedy, there have been few attempts to address the various classes of news-bringers from a computational angle. Where such examinations have occurred, they have, to my knowledge—which admittedly might be lacking, please feel free to correct me here!—taken place in the context of broader computational studies of drama, such as the work of Julia Jennifer Beine, Frank Fischer, and Viktor Illmer presented at the DH Conference in 2024; the examination of the chorus by María Teresa Santa María Fernández and Monika Dabrowska; or the early work on social network theory and Greek tragedy by Jeff Rydberg-Cox [8, 9, 10].

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Figure 1: Principal component analysis of stylistometric features from individual speakers in tragedy (various colors) and Homeric epic (yellow). This analysis did not control for metrical differences, as it analyzed running 4-grams.

In this paper, I attempt to start some discussions about the quantifiable natures of news-bringers and their speeches in ancient tragedy. Everything that I write here should be understood as experimental and preliminary—there is a surprising amount of ground to cover. At the same time, I hope that by exploring the ways that we can measure a character’s “messenger-type-ness,” or the extent to which they perform a “messenger function” (to borrow a term from C. W. Marshall [11]), we can shed new light on this often-misunderstood class of dramatic actors and thus better understand how they reflect their culture’s relationship to secondhand information.

2. Epic Style?

In some ways, what prompted this paper was a casual investigation of the *Stylo* package [12] by way of answering the question, “Do tragic messengers really speak with epic diction?” The affirmative answer to this question is usually assumed, but even preliminary results raise important questions.

Although the dimensionality reduction in the analysis that produced the above chart did not account for metrical differences—Homeric epic is in dactylic hexameters, while messengers *usually* speak in iambic trimeters—the strong clustering effect exhibited by meter helps to highlight some of the more interesting outliers. For one, the Tutor from Sophocles’ *Electra* speaks in a style that gravitates towards the Homeric. This result makes sense, however, when we consider that much of his vocabulary—and indeed, much of the scene that he describes—comes straight from the chariot race in *Iliad* 23, even if he delivers the speech in iambs rather than dactyls.

More surprisingly, the Phrygian from Euripides’ *Orestes*—a late tragedy, first performed in 408 BCE—also exhibits a style that leans Homeric, at least compared to other speakers in tragedy. This result is unusual: unlike most of the other news-bringers, the Phrygian *sings* his report in lyric meters. We might have thus expected principal component analysis to reveal him as an outlier in the *other* direction. Perhaps, however, the variations in his lyric meters produced greater overlap with Homeric style than the typical iambs of other news-bringers.

Not to belabor the discussion of a quick and limited experiment, but it bears noting that the decision not to control for meter came from a consideration of the costs of doing so. When comparing tragedy to epic, we are working with surprisingly little data—a little under 250,000 words in tragedy, and about 350,000 words in the Homeric epics (the *Iliad* and *Odyssey*). Approaches that work well for millions of words fail to produce meaningful data on these smaller corpora, and we must consequently take care when employing any lossy data cleaning methods like lemmatization that might otherwise help us control for features like meter.

Further, if, as sometimes seems to be the case, the argument in favor of positively comparing messenger-type speeches to Homeric epic means that the audience was expected to *hear* Homeric speech during a messenger’s report, then meter is an indispensable component of the performance, and something to which any analysis should attend.

Perhaps, in the end, stylometry was the wrong tool to use here, as it mainly confirmed what we could observe simply by paying attention to meter. The tight grouping of tragedy and epic, however, could provide a useful starting point for further inquiry into questions of *tragic* style specifically. As Paschalis Agapitos and Andreas van Cranenberg have shown with Seneca’s *Octavia* and *Hercules Oetaeus*, and as Nikos Manousakis and Efstathios Stamatatos have shown with Euripides’ *Rhesus*, stylometry can offer vital insights into cases of contested authorship [13, 14]. With the Homeric question set aside, we can imagine a study that examines the evolution of choral style in tragedy, for example.

A literary question lurks here too: must we insist that tragedy answer to Homer? I have no ready answer, and I have been known to call tragedy (affectionately) “Homer fan-fiction.” But disabused as we now must be that messengers borrow too much from their epic predecessor, I want to turn to analyses that look at lexis rather than style.

3. What do news-bringers talk about?

In this section, I discuss the use of topic modeling through Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) to extract “topics”—groups of frequently cooccurring terms—from the tragic and epic corpora, as well as from the smaller corpora of speeches in Homer and of messenger-type speeches within tragedy.

For this analysis, I identified messenger-type speeches by manually adding to the list that Barrett compiled in an appendix to his 2002 monograph [4, 223–224]. For speeches in Homer, I relied on the DICES API [15]. The editions used are the latest available from the Perseus Project [16]. After extracting the text for each speaker from the TEI XML, the documents were sentencized, tokenized, and lemmatized using the pre-trained greCy¹ models before finally being written in the CoNLL-U² format. Because greCy occasionally misses stop-words, an additional stop-word filter was applied via a manually curated list before running the following analyses.

¹<https://spacy.io/universe/project/grecy>

²<https://universaldependencies.org/format.html>

These results are preliminary, and the topics are numbered rather than descriptively labeled, so I will refer to them by their (sub-)corpus and the number assigned to them in the plot, e.g., “Tragedy 1,” “Epic 5,” etc.

The tragedy corpus and the messenger sub-corpus contained too few tokens for meaningful results from LDA, which uses TF-IDF vectors, so that terms that appear in fewer “documents”—individual speakers, for these analyses—have proportionally greater weights. This approach already poses some challenges for small corpora, which are exacerbated by the prevalence of hapaxes in this data set. For these reasons, I will mainly focus on the results of the NMF analyses, which are plotted below.

Topics in Homeric NMF model (Frobenius norm)

Figure 2: NMF-based topic modeling of the corpus of speeches in Homer.

As these topics show—and as we should expect—Athenian tragedy and Homeric epic demonstrate a significant amount of lexical overlap. At the same time, notable trends emerge, and the extracted topics by and large make sense: Homer 1, for instance, includes lemmata like μάχη (“war”), ἀργεῖος (“Argive”), θυμός (“spirit”), and μάχομαι (the verb “fight”), representing the martial tenor of the *Iliad*. Tragedy 3 includes ἀγαμέμνων (“Agamemnon”), βάρβαρος (“barbarian”—apt given the frequent accusation of Agamemnon acting in an un-Greek-like manner), γάμος (“wedding” or “marriage”), alongside two terms for a household, οἶκος and δόμος, all terms that cause frequent conflict in various plays.

Inspired by the work of Thomas Koentges in measuring the “philosophical-ness” of the Greek corpus, the top 10 topics from Homer and tragedy were measured proportionally for messenger speeches and, as a control, for tragedy as a whole [17].

Although I do not have space here to discuss these results in detail, we can see at a glance that messengers speak no more “Homericly” than other characters in tragedy, at least in terms of vocabulary. It seems that we will need to find support elsewhere when it comes to the Homeric influence on tragic news-bringers.

Other trends are visible as well: named characters who deliver messenger-type speeches show a slight preference for tragic lexis in those speeches, compared to anonymous news-bringers with names like “Messenger,” “Shepherd,” and “Nurse.” And in tragedy as a whole, the proportion of Homeric vocabulary remains remarkably consistent over the seven decades measured here, even across plays

Topics in Tragic NMF model (Frobenius norm)

Figure 3: NMF-based topic modeling of tragedy.

that do not touch directly on the stories contained in the epics (such as Sophocles’ Theban plays or Euripides’ *Medea*).

4. Audiences

I want to turn now to a discussion of messengers’ audiences in each tragedy. The DraCor documentation includes a helpful tutorial³ describing ways of ranking character centrality. Unsurprisingly, when applied to the tragedies in DraCor, choruses and named characters dominate the centrality rankings: the first character who can even be said to deliver a messenger-type speech is Clytaemestra in Aeschylus’ *Agamemnon*, who by centrality ranking comes in 45th. Talthybius in Euripides’ *Trojan Women* is the highest-ranking herald at 73rd, and the first messenger to appear is the Ἄγγελος (“Messenger”) of Aeschylus’ *Persians* at 79th.

The messenger of *Persians* is an interesting outlier, as he speaks at greater length than any other single messenger in tragedy. To put this in perspective, nearly every named character in Sophocles’ *Trachiniae* delivers a messenger-type speech at some point, and the play consists of nearly twenty-five percent messenger-type speeches (as Jebb surmised over a century ago) [18]. *Persians* consists of nearly seventeen percent messenger-type speech, every line of which is delivered by this single messenger. These plays contain far and away the greatest concentrations of messenger-type speeches, which on average only account for 8.5% of a given tragedy’s lines.

In some ways, this is confirmation of Trilcke et al.’s observations on “small worlds” in more modern plays [19, 7–33]. A central character—usually the chorus in ancient tragedy—connects clusters of other characters in each play’s network, although I am not sure that in the case of the ancient plays we can say that the chorus “[carries] the plot” [19, 22]. There is also the problem of dramatic separation, discussed in greater detail below: the chorus in Greek tragedy typically occupied a distinct part of the performance

³<https://dracor-org.github.io/dracor-notebooks/catch-a-protagonist-in-dracor/catch-a-protagonist-in-dracor.html>

Topics in Messenger NMF model (Frobenius norm)

Figure 4: NMF-based topic modeling of messenger-type speeches in tragedy.

Figure 5: Proportion of each of the top 10 topics from Homer (shades of blue) and tragedy (shades of red) for each messenger in the tragic corpus.

space, the ὀρχήστρα or “dancing space,” while the action of the other actors was concentrated around the σκηνή, a wooden structure that served as a play’s background and main scenery.

In the same volume as Trilcke et al.’s paper, Rebecca Hicke and David Mimmo provide another way of approaching the problems of influence in drama [19, 87–105]. By charting the percentage of words spoken by women (as a group or as specific characters) in each scene of Shakespeare’s comedies, they add a chronological element that is difficult to capture in network analyses. It might be instructive, however, to examine network “snapshots” in ancient tragedy, comparing the graphs at the beginning and end of each episode to determine what changes were introduced and by whom during a given exchange. This approach might also provide a solution to the chorus problem, as their odes take place separately from the main episodes that drive the plot.

Figure 6: Proportion of each of the top 10 topics from Homer (shades of blue) and tragedy (shades of red) for each tragedy.

5. Case Study in Movable Networks: Euripides’ *Andromache*

Wanting to take a provisional stab at modeling a network over time, I have drafted a network visualization using Mike Bostock’s Observable Framework and D3.js [20, 21]. The experiment is visible here: <https://observablehq.com/@pletcher/networks-in-euripides-andromache>. For this initial pass, I encoded the major actions of Euripides’ *Andromache*—that is, I noted where the text indicated an entrance or an exit, as well as where characters engaged in dialogue. Capturing dialogue is particularly important for correctly modeling a network in Athenian tragedy, largely because of the chorus. Aristotle famously criticized Euripides for not integrating the chorus into his drama as well as Sophocles and Aeschylus (*Poetics* 1456a 25–32), meaning that we cannot assume that just because the chorus is “on stage”—itself a problematic descriptor!—that they actively participate in the network of the drama. As I hope to show, recording dialogue as moments when speakers actively speak to each other, rather than moments when they stand next to each other onstage, helps reveal the intricate and shifting influences that are active in tragedy.

Oliver Taplin’s pioneering work on Aeschylean stagecraft sets the scene (as it were) for this experiment. His early description of the challenges of defining “entry” and “exit” is worth quoting at length: “At first sight it might seem obvious that by ‘entry’ we mean the movement which brings an actor in to the field of vision of the audience, and by ‘exit’ we mean the movement which takes him out of it. This is certainly what we mean by the words; but their full range is more complicated. Apart from the small but valid complaints that not all of the actor comes into view at the same moment (apparently the side-entrances at Athens sloped uphill) and that he would not enter or leave the field of vision of all the audience simultaneously (especially not in a theatre of Greek shape), there is the more substantial point that we cannot possibly know at what moment the actor crossed the line between out of sight and in sight of the audience. ...And so in the study of entrances and exits the stage movement which is of interest is not the momentary movement in and out of view, but the prolonged movement across the centre of attention, and back again”[22, 7].

Further complicating matters, the chorus did not enter and exit like the other actors, nor did it do so in the same place. Rather, it danced into the *orchestra* (literally, “dancing-place”) during its *parodos* (“entrance song”) stayed in the *orchestra* during its *stasima* (“stationary” songs)—and left while or shortly after it sang the *exodos* (“exit song”). Its continued presence during the bulk of the tragedy thus complicates “traditional” approaches to network analysis, even before we consider that its “presence” is dramatically attenuated by its literal separation from the rest of the actors, who performed in front of the *skēnē*.⁴ These problems become especially apparent in a drama like *Andromache*, where the chorus

⁴See, e.g., Helene Foley’s “Choral Identity in Greek Tragedy” for a more in-depth discussion and additional bibliography on the chorus [23].

alternates between close engagement with the dilemmas onstage and aloof (and, in this case, frankly misogynistic) reflection on feminine jealousy.

As the following figure shows, redrawing the dramatic network at each “event” helps to visualize when characters coexists in the performance space without addressing each other directly, as during the *parodos*.

Networks in Euripides' *Andromache*

Visualizing interactions by line and type

Figure 7: The Chorus and Andromache are each in their respective performance spaces during the *parodos*, but they are not yet talking to each other.

By contrast, when Peleus enters, the characters engage in a heated *agōn* that involves every speaking character onstage and in the *orchēstra*—seemingly violating the three-actor rule with the singing Child, but I leave that discussion for another day.

Even a quick glance at these two plots reveals a striking difference between reading a dramatic network as the static result of conversations at the end of the drama versus modeling the network as an evolving group of ephemeral events. I intend for further investigation to measure the shifts in centrality and count-based measures of influence, and I welcome discussion about how to quantify this influence over time.

I want to note, too, that *Andromache* presents another, less-frequently encountered problem of mute actors at the end of the play. Scholars have long wondered whether Andromache and the Child re-enter for the final episode and *exodos*, even though they do not speak, as the *dea ex machina* Thetis seems to address them directly [24]. For this experiment, I have not attempted to model mute actors—there are also several slaves and attendants that appear earlier in the play with Menelaus, for example—but I offer this conundrum as a potential jumping-off point for further discussion.

Networks in Euripides' *Andromache*

Visualizing interactions by line and type

Line 545 - Peleus Menelaus Andromache Child Chorus: dialogu

Figure 8: The play's central *agōn* involves every speaking character onstage at some point.

6. Conclusion(s)

By way of conclusion, I want to stress the preliminary and experimental nature of this talk. Much work remains to be done, especially in terms of addressing the challenges of meaningful network analysis within the constraints of ancient tragedy. Nevertheless, a few key themes have emerged in this brief discussion.

First, the tension between Homer and the tragedians provides a productive background for continuing investigation and discussion. The results presented here demonstrate that messenger-type speeches in tragedy lack discernible Homeric lexis, which helps us view these ancient performances in a new light. The embodied and stage-directed actions delivered alongside the words of a messenger-type speech belong to the ephemera of staged performance—we cannot recover them. Nevertheless, and contrary to much earlier work, by emphasizing the need to understand gesture and affect in addition to vocabulary and diction, we position messenger-type speeches alongside other dramatic performances, rather than an epic appendage that dramatists have maintained merely for convenience. Moreover, this examination of tragic lexis should also guide further discussion of tragic diction and performance theory, helping to make sense, for example, of the enigmatic roles that props and costumes played alongside the actors who employed them by observing how speech patterns change alongside movement. Taplin has famously tackled many of these questions from a literary and performance studies angle, and we would profitably follow his lead through our own computational engagements with the material [22, 25].

Second, the preliminary topic modeling results presented here ought to be followed by a broader

investigation involving more of the Greek corpus, similar to the work carried out by Koentges [17]. Although constraining the models to the vocabulary available from lemmatized editions of Homer and tragedy helps to narrow the focus and reveal useful groupings, like “Odysseus” and “ship,” an analysis that includes larger swaths of the ancient corpus could profitably reveal connections to history and oratory (for starters) that could not be covered in this study.

Relatedly, I have left questions of Aristophanic comedy to the side. However, given the comedian’s penchant for quoting tragedy—sometimes at length, as he does with Euripides’ *Telephus* and *Helen* in *Thesmophoriazusae*—a more thorough examination of tragic-comic intertexts could help to contextualize the performance culture of fifth-century Athens to an even greater degree.

Finally, the question of tragic networks remains. In addition to the scene co-occurrences analyzed here, I plan to investigate other methods that can better account for tragedy’s idiosyncracies. For example, much tragic “action” occurs off-stage, and it should be possible to study the networks that emerge from narrated interactions as well. One thinks, for example, of J. M. Mossman’s seminal article “Waiting for Neoptolemus,” which discusses the strange non-presence of Neoptolemus in Euripides’ *Andromache*. Further, as noted above, it is important to examine tragedy as a series of events, and not simply as the static network of relationships that emerges at the end of the drama (when many of the characters are dead and/or destitute anyway).

I plan to continue this work between now and the conference in a few weeks, and I hope to offer substantial updates to the studies presented in this brief paper. In the meantime, however, I hope that these provocations towards computational approaches to messenger-type speeches prove useful beyond my own research, and that they demonstrate the need for discussion and debate about how to proceed most effectively.

7. Declaration on Generative AI

The author has not employed any Generative AI tools.

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Modeling Imitatio. Character Alignment and Adaptation Strategies in Early Modern Drama

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Abstract

This paper proposes a computational method to align characters from parallel plays printed in different languages. The aim of this approach is to capture, quantify and compare adaptation strategies in TEI-encoded theatre editions from the Drama Corpora Project (DraCor). It designs and evaluates a reproducible algorithm for measuring the distance between a theatre adaptation and its source. Focusing on character roles, the algorithm automatically aligns characters from parallel plays into pairs of equivalent speakers. The pairs are matched on the occurrences of their speech in the two versions of the plays, by computing the (cosine) similarity of sequences of speech turns. These matchings enable analyses of equivalent speakers and comparisons between entire plays. The proposed implementation of computational character alignment is language-independent and therefore applicable to pairs of parallel plays written in any European language. To demonstrate its value, 25 early modern Dutch plays are compared to their non-Dutch sources, with a specific focus on three Dutch adaptations of *Iphigenia in Aulis* and *Iphigenia in Tauris* by Euripides.

Keywords

computational drama analysis, translation studies, early modern drama, Iphigenia, Dutch theatre

1. Introduction

During the Renaissance, theatrical cultures all over Europe were founded on the poetic ideal of Imitatio. Notoriously hard to define, the term generally refers to a broad range of literary strategies to mimic the style, form, or plot of canonical literary works, such as citation, translation, paraphrase, imitation, analogy, adaptation et cetera [1]. This ideal required poets and playwrights to acquire the knowledge and training needed to read, translate and mimic the literary models from the past. The imperative to imitate was never straightforward and always burdened with ambivalence: mimicking existing works was not meant to be 'slavish' but ideally resulted in a new, personal style. Early modern poets were trained not just to copy but to equal and appropriate the models [2]. Encouraged by that paradoxical goal they revisited the canon of Biblical and classical sources – from Homer and Virgil to Ovid, Sophocles, Euripides, Seneca, Plautus, Terence and many others – and transformed the styles and stories inherited from their predecessors into new adaptations written for the stage. As a result, European traditions in early modern drama developed into collages of variations on canonical narratives from the past.

Besides its preoccupation with transhistorical sources, Renaissance drama was also fundamentally transnational and transcultural. Early modern playwrights borrowed their material not just from the past, but also from contemporary stories travelling across the spatial borders of foreign literary cultures. Due to the increasing availability and exchange of books and information, enabled by the extensive book production and communication networks around Europe, early modern stories could travel faster than ever before. Spanish novella's such as the anonymous *Lazarillo de Tormes* (1554) or *La gitanela* (1613) by Cervantes reappeared on stage in the Dutch Republic, while French and Spanish plays by Molière, Corneille, Calderon de la Barca, and Lope de Vega drew large crowds to theatres all over Europe [3; 4]. Following the poetic ideal of Imitatio, playwrights thus blended story traditions from different origins, reshaping historical and foreign stories into new forms tailored to local traditions and contexts.

In this paper, I propose a formalist approach to this process of reshaping drama across temporal and spatial borders. The aim of this approach is to capture different adaptation strategies through a reproducible computational method designed to quantify the distance between a theatre adaptation and the play – usually written in another language – that provided its source. This quantification focuses on character roles and relies on a procedure that aligns characters from parallel plays into pairs of equivalent speakers, enabling comparisons between the speech texts of those equivalent speakers in different versions of the play. The proposed method is language-independent and therefore applicable to any pair of parallel plays written in a European language. It is however limited to dramatic adaptations of plays, excluding adaptations of texts in other genres, such as Biblical stories or prose novels. This formalist quantitative approach enables literary scholars not only to compare individual plays, but also to reconstruct and quantify the changing function of the poetic ideal of *Imitatio* – to model literary modelling – in the early modern period.

To illustrate the value of the proposed approach, I use early modern Dutch theatre as a case study, for two reasons. First, Dutch literary historians extensively demonstrated that seventeenth-century Dutch theatre was driven by foreign literary influences [5; 6]. French, Spanish and Neo-Latin plays were extremely popular in the Dutch Republic and served as a model for many Dutch playwrights. Secondly, several Dutch translators and playwrights were explicit about their translation choices, which they regularly explain in a separate preface to the printed play. These reflections on their translation strategies reveal their motivations behind specific interventions in the sources, and help us to interpret and contextualise the results of the formalist analyses presented below. I will focus specifically on early modern Dutch adaptations of the ancient myth about Iphigenia, derived from two plays by Euripides.

With its focus on Dutch adaptations of French, Neo-Latin and Greek Iphigenia plays this paper also addresses the need for computational methods that enable comparisons between theatre editions in different languages. The database of the Drama Corpora Project (DraCor) contains large collections of TEI-encoded theatre editions in multiple languages, which has already generated various innovative approaches to early modern drama [7]. However, as we still lack suitable methods to compare plays across linguistic borders, the field of computational drama studies still mostly remains stratified in separate linguistic (and national) literary traditions. There have been innovative comparative studies of multilingual corpora from the DraCor infrastructure, but these approaches are comparative on the corpus level, not the play level [e.g. 8; 9]. The present paper aims to fill this gap with a first attempt to formalise textual distance between dramatic adaptations and their sources. It thus builds upon an earlier attempt by Peverelli and others, who proposed an innovative method to capture the process of *imitatio* by stylometrically analysing the stylistic imitation of one poet (Terence) in Latin, French, Italian and English early modern comedies [10]. Instead of style, the method presented below focuses on the composition of parallel plays published in different languages. Given its reusability on other cases, this method opens up new possibilities to map and quantify the many intercultural and interlinguistic connections in early modern European drama.

2. Case study: the Dutch Iphigenia

The two stories about the (attempted) sacrifice of Agamemnon's daughter Iphigenia in the wake and the aftermath of the Trojan War provided a rich source for Dutch translations and adaptations. The myth originates in two plays by Euripides, *Iphigenia in Aulis* and *Iphigenia in Tauris*, which not only survived in Greek but also in early Latin adaptations (by Ennius for example) [11]. During the Renaissance, several adaptations in Neo-Latin emerged: Desiderius Erasmus significantly increased the accessibility and fame of Euripides with his often reprinted 1506 Latin translation of *Iphigenia in Aulis* [12]. Another Neo-Latin adaptation was published by Caspar Stiblin in 1558 [13]. Vernacular adaptations in English appeared already in ca. 1553 (by Jane Lumley), the 1580s (a lost translation by

George Peele) and in 1700 (by Abel Boyer), in addition to Italian (1551), German (1555, 1584) and several French versions (ca. 1545, 1549, 1640, 1674, 1675) [14].

The first Dutch adaptation of *Iphigenia in Aulis* was published by Samuel Coster in 1617 (twice) and reprinted in 1626 and 1630 (twice) [15]. About sixty years later, in 1678, theatre company Nil Volentibus Arduum adapted Jean Racine's French version of *Iphigenia in Aulis* from 1674, *Iphigénie en Aulide*. Other Dutch translations of Racine's version appeared in 1679 (by Joan Dullaart) and 1800 (by A.L. Barbaz). *Iphigenia in Tauris* was first translated by Joost van den Vondel in 1666, based on a Neo-Latin translation by Franciscus Portus [16]. Two more early modern Dutch versions of this tragedy were put to the press: *Orestes en Pylades, of Iphigenia in Tauris* (1702) by Matthis Bode, based on a French adaptation by François Joseph de Lagrange Chance, and *Iphigenia in Tauris* (1771) by Margaretha Geertruy de Cambon-van der Werken, based on a French play by Claude Guimond de La Touche. Besides these more or less direct retellings, the story about Iphigenia also resonated in plays that followed the more general story model of the sacrificed daughter, such as Coster's *Polyxena* (1619) modelled after Euripides's *Hecuba* and Seneca's *Troades* [17], and Vondel's *Jeptha* (1659), an adaptation of George Buchanan's *Jephtes sive Votum* (1554), which dramatises the story about Jefta from the Book of Judges who ends up sacrificing his daughter to keep his promise to God. Jefta's daughter remains anonymous in the Bible but is named 'Ifis' in Buchanan's and Vondel's dramatic retelling of the story: an allusion to the figure of Iphigenia that reappears in many early modern commentaries on Iphigenia adaptations [18].

The Dutch adaptations of Euripides's plays about Iphigenia offer an interesting example of the historical process of *Imitatio* in early modern drama. Each of the three versions of the Iphigenia story model foregrounded in this paper – by Coster, Vondel, and Nil Volentibus Arduum – demonstrate a different adaptation strategy. Coster completely abandoned the dramatic structure of his source and only used its plot as a flexible guideline for his interpretation. Vondel translated his Neo-Latin source as faithfully as he could and tried to maintain the integrity of the source. Nil Volentibus Arduum, finally, closely followed Racine's model but also deliberately intervened in the structure, characters and plot of the play. This variation in adaptation strategies behind the selected Dutch Iphigenia plays exemplifies the way one story model – the sacrificed daughter Iphigenia – could generate multiple variations, each one tailored to the poetic ideals, literary conventions or political contexts in which they were published and performed.

To understand the differences between these adaptations, a brief description of their individual political-literary contexts is needed. Coster published his *Iphigenia* in 1617 amid one of the most turbulent political controversies in the history of the Dutch Republic. An explosive theological dispute that divided the Reformed Church in two factions, the so-called Remonstrants and the Contraremonstrants, became politically charged after each of the two most powerful men in the country – stadtholder Maurits of Orange and *landsadvocaat* Johan van Oldenbarnevelt – started supporting one of the opposing groups, which nearly turned an academic debate about Calvinist theology into a civil war. Coster's adaptation was read foremost as a critical commentary of this political-religious conflict. Coster's characterisation of the priest Euripylus was widely recognised as a representation of the orthodox Contraremonstrant minister from Amsterdam Jacobus Trigland [19]. In Coster's version, Ulysses uses Euripylus's religious authority among the Greeks to undermine Agamemnon's position as king by forcing him to sacrifice Iphigenia. Sacrificing his beloved daughter was necessary to satisfy Artemis, the goddess who sabotaged the invasion of Troy by blocking the wind and trapping the Greek fleet at the coast of Aulis. Ulysses expects Agamemnon to refuse to obey Euripylus's prophecy, after which Agamemnon's position would become untenable and Ulysses could take over power. In response to this conspiracy, Agamemnon and Calchas the prophet design a counter-plot using a stand-in for Iphigenia to deceive the people into thinking that Agamemnon did in fact sacrifice his own daughter.

Coster's play focuses not at all on Agamemnon's psychological dilemma between the fate of his family and the fate of the Greeks. Instead, Coster's adaptation was read as a pamphlet about the politics of demagogy and the corrupted relationship between state and church, identifying orthodox ministers like Trigland as the evil geniuses whose religious deceit threatened the stability of the state. Besides the large role reserved for Euriphylus, Coster introduced various other characters who are completely absent in Euripides's original: Palamedes, Pretislaus, Nestor and Tersites. In her study of Coster's tragedies, Mieke Smits-Veldt therefore concluded that *Iphigenia* was not modelled after one play specifically, but combined elements and characters from multiple classical sources into a free retelling of Euripides's *Iphigenia in Aulis*. Coster's approach is a typical example of a reader-oriented adaptation strategy: the adapted play's political message was more important than maintaining the integrity of the sources.

The second Dutch *Iphigenia* play, Vondel's 1666 translation of Portus's Neo-Latin translation of *Iphigenia in Tauris*, followed its source more faithfully than Coster's. This second tragedy about *Iphigenia* from Euripides's oeuvre is the story of what happens years after *Iphigenia*'s release from the altar by Artemis, who took her to the land of the Taurens (currently Crimea) to become a priest in the temple of Artemis. When her brother Orestes and his friend Plyades are captured by the Taurens, *Iphigenia* is tasked with the preparation of the sacrifice of these Greek intruders. She discovers that Orestes is among the captives and together they manage to escape and sail back to Greece. Vondel carefully reproduces the plot and structure of this original version of the tragedy. At this stage in his poetic development, Vondel was inspired by Aristotle's poetics, which encouraged him to write tragedies that demonstrated key elements from the Aristotelian theory of drama. His reading of the 1630 Neo-Latin translation of *Phoenissae* by Hugo Grotius convinced Vondel of the quality of Euripides's work and encouraged him to produce a Dutch translation of *Iphigenia in Tauris*, which he considered to be an excellent demonstration of the dramatic function of *agnitio* (the crucial moment when the tragic hero or heroine is confronted by their tragic fate) [20]. Vondel's decision to translate Euripides should therefore be understood in the context of his poetic development and his efforts to introduce Dutch readers into Greek drama by translating the best examples from that tradition. The first Dutch translation of *Iphigenia in Tauris* was above all an exercise in writing and understanding the genre of ancient Greek tragedy. Vondel's approach can be classified as text-oriented, which resulted in a faithful translation.

The third Dutch example in this tradition was published in 1678 by Nil Volentibus Arduum ('Nil'): *Ifigenia*. It was modelled after Jean Racine's 1674 *Iphigénie en Aulide*, an adaptation of *Iphigenia in Aulis*. By then, this theatre society had established an influential position in Amsterdam's literary world after an almost ten-years campaign propagating their controversial dramatic program based on French-classicist ideals and rationalist principles. Nil's members jointly wrote adaptations of (mostly) French plays written by influential contemporaries such as Pierre Corneille, Molière, Phillippe Quinault and the aforementioned Jean Racine. In the preface 'Aan den Leezer' (To the reader) added to reprint of the play from 1683, the anonymous translators of *Ifigenia* present their translation as an alternative to the 1679 edition *Ifigenie in Aulis* by Joan Dullaart, who apparently had been working simultaneously on his translation [21]. They also explain their decision to add a few scenes to Racine's play, in which *Iphigenia* reappears on stage and reunites with her beloved Achilles after the failed attempt to sacrifice her. As this intervention was expected to be appreciated by the public, it would make the play more effective. The poets behind Nil's version thus adapted Racine's play to suit their poetic principles concerning the right composition, optimising the dramatic and emotional effect on the audience. Moreover, they enriched the final scene with a monologue by Kalchas (or Calchas) the priest, who does not appear at all in Racine's version. With this intervention, Nil explicitly connected their adaptation to Coster's famous version of the tragedy, in which Kalchas played a key role.

3. Method: character alignment

The approach to dramatic adaptations presented in this paper is limited to the textual level of plays and focuses specifically on transformations of one formal feature of theatre editions: character roles. The assumption behind this focus is that interventions in the source text always become visible at least on the level of speaking characters from the adaptation, for example because speech turns from the source play are extended ('insertions'), changed ('substitutions'), abbreviated or removed entirely ('deletions') in the target play, or because characters themselves are inserted, substituted or deleted in specific scenes or in the dramatic story world at large. Character roles therefore offer a good place to start for an attempt to quantitatively model the ideal of *Imitatio*, which also means that an analysis of adaptation strategies should not end there. With my focus on character roles I do not mean to deny the importance of the many other intertextual relationships between adaptations and their sources, such as character style (including meter and rhyme), composition (including the play's division in acts and scenes), themes and motives, not to mention possible similarities in non-textual dimensions of the dramatic world created on stage through *mise-en-scène*, *décor*, music, images, clothing, performance style, et cetera. Many of those features are more difficult to capture quantitatively, if they are documented in the sources at all, and therefore require additional approaches that are beyond the scope of this paper.

Given the focus on interventions in character roles, the question at stake could be phrased as: how are the character roles from a source play (written in language X) transformed by the target play (written either in the same language X or in another language Y)? The task required to find answers to that question could be explained as an alignment task, designed to match parallel speakers from 'parallel' plays. After parallel speakers and their speech turns are successfully aligned, further analysis of the differences between their speech becomes possible. For the implementation of this alignment I assume that parallel characters from the source and the target play tend to speak at similar lengths and at similar moments in the play. In other words, parallel speakers can be aligned based on the distribution and length of their speech turns throughout the play. If, for example, Agamemnon has a long monologue in the first scene of the source play, we would expect a similarly long speech turn at the beginning of the target play as well.

Using this assumption – parallel characters from parallel plays tend to speak at similar lengths at similar moments – we can formalise the distribution of lines by speaking characters in the play as a vector of values. This vector could be visualised as a bar code, in which the (darkness of the) bars represent the number of their lines in a given segment of the play, and the empty spaces between the bars represent segments in which they either do not speak or are not present on stage at all. Merging the line distributions of all characters results in a heatmap that first of all illustrates the rationale behind the proposed method for character alignment. The heatmaps in Figure 1 for example, representing the number of lines on a scale between 0 and 120 per scene per character, illustrate that 'Agamemnon' from Racine's French *Iphigénie* and his counterpart 'Agamémnon' from Nil Volentibus Arduum's Dutch adaptation of that play do indeed speak at similar lengths at similar moments in the two versions of the play. Secondly, these heatmaps offer the researcher a tool to inspect the similarities in speech patterns between parallel speakers: Figure 1 also shows that Nil Volentibus Arduum inserted three speakers in their version (Kalchas, Patroklés, and Néstor) and made substantial changes to the speech turns of some characters. For example, the monologue by Ulysse / Ulisses in the last scene of Racine's version was removed in the Dutch adaptation.

Iphigénie by Jean Racine (1674)

Ifigenia by Nil Volentibus Arduum (1678)

Figure 1: Speech patterns by character in Jean Racine’s *Iphigénie* (1674) versus Nil Volentibus Arduum’s *Ifigenia* (1678)

In addition to the visual evidence provided by the heatmaps, the underlying data enables an automatic alignment of characters from parallel plays. Parallel speakers can be matched computationally by ranking the cosine similarity between speech pattern vectors of all potential pairs of characters. In theory, the most similar pair of ‘bar codes’ (i.e. the two vectors of line distributions with the highest cosine similarity) is thus nominated as the most likely pair of parallel characters.

The heatmaps in Figure 1 represent the number of lines by character in each of the 37 scenes of Racine’s *Iphigénie*. However, since adaptations often do not maintain the scene structure of their sources, it makes more sense to segment the play based on a (random) number of windows of equal length. To find an optimal number of windows, the performance of the character alignment task was evaluated for any number of windows between 5 and 75, measured as the percentage of character alignments that were correct (precision) and the percentage of characters that were correctly aligned (recall). When tested on Racine’s *Iphigénie*, the evaluation first of all revealed that the task’s precision and recall remain relatively high (between 90% and 100%) with 20 windows or less, but its recall gradually decreases when the text is segmented into more than 20 (smaller) windows. However, *Iphigénie* is a relatively uncomplicated play with only 10 speaking characters. When applied to more complex plays with a larger character list, such as Shakespeare’s *Macbeth*, the alignment task performs much worse. The low recall in this case can be explained from the large number of minor characters in Shakespeare’s drama: soldiers or messengers who only speak one or two lines in the play are hard to align when the adaptation does not follow its source faithfully. This leads to the circular conclusion that the performance of the alignment task – purposed to measure the distance between the source and the target play – depends on the distance between the source and the target play. However, the correlation between the textual distance between the analysed plays and the number of successfully aligned characters in those plays should be considered a feature, not a bug. After all, when a high number of alignment errors indicates a large distance between the two plays, then the performance of character alignment becomes a distance measure in itself. Moreover, even in cases where minor characters are misaligned, the recall in terms of matched lines (instead of correctly matched characters) remains still relatively high, due to the fact that the play’s major speakers are usually matched correctly.

Figure 2: Performance of character alignment in Nil Volentibus Arduum’s 1678 Dutch translation of Jean Racine’s *Iphigénie* for 5-75 equal windows.

Figure 3: Performance of character alignment in Dorothea Tieck’s 1832 German translation of *Macbeth* (available in the German Shakespeare Corpus) for 5-75 equal windows.

Assuming that 80-100% of all character roles can be aligned correctly using the proposed method for character alignment, it becomes possible to quantify the differences between the source and the target play on multiple levels. To introduce a standardised, quantitative norm for comparing adaptation strategies on the corpus level, I propose to measure the distance between source and target on five levels: number of lines, number of speech turns, number of speakers / speaker groups (that is: (groups of) characters who speak at least one line), number of matched speakers (using a confidence threshold of 95%) and number of matched lines (the sum of all lines spoken by the total number of correctly matched speakers). Averaging the normalised difference between a source play and a target play on each of these five variables – on a scale from 0.0 to 1.0 – results in a single metric enabling comparisons between pairs of parallel plays. Let’s call this metric the ‘Adaptation Index’. The higher a play’s score on the Adaptation Index, the higher the closeness to its source.

4. Corpus: DutchDraCor

To demonstrate the function of the Adaptation Index, the procedure was applied to a selection of 25 early modern Dutch adaptations of Greek, French and Spanish plays, including the three Dutch Iphigenia plays introduced above. Digital editions of these plays were extracted from DutchDraCor, a collection of TEI-encoded early modern Dutch plays integrated in the ‘programmable corpus’ developed by the Drama Corpora Project (‘DraCor’) [22]. The TEI-encoding in these editions was essential to extract speech turns on the character level. For each of the selected adaptations, the

source play was also available in DraCor's Greek, Spanish or French collections, which enabled a computational comparison between the source and the adaptation using character alignment.

Table 1

Corpus description: 25 pairs of parallel plays, ordered by date of the source

Author source	Title source	Author adaptation	Title adaptation
Euripides	<i>Iphigenia in Aulis</i> (405 BCE)	Samuel Coster	<i>Iphigenia</i> (1617)
Euripides	<i>Phoenissae</i> (411 BCE)	Joost van den Vondel	<i>Euripides Feniciaensche</i> (1668)
Euripides	<i>Iphigenia in Tauris</i> (414 BCE)	Joost van den Vondel	<i>Ifigenie in Tauren</i> (1666)
Sophocles	<i>Oedipus Tyrannus</i> (429 BCE)	Joost van den Vondel	<i>Koning Edipus</i> (1660)
Sophocles	<i>Trachiniai</i> (450–425 BC)	Joost van den Vondel	<i>Sofokles Herkules in Trachin</i> (1668)
Pedro Calderón de la Barca	<i>La dama duende</i> (1636)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Het spookend weeuwteje</i> (1670)
François Tristan l'Hermite	<i>Mariane</i> (1644)	Katharyne Lescailje	<i>Herodes en Mariamne</i> (1685)
Jean Magnon	<i>Le Mariage d'Oroondate et de Statira</i> (1648)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Het huwelyk van Orondates en Statira</i> (1670)
Jean de Rotrou	<i>Venceslas</i> (1648)	Katharyne Lescailje	<i>Wenseslaüs, koning van Poolen</i> (1686)
Pierre Corneille	<i>Nicomède</i> (1651)	Katharyne Lescailje	<i>Nicomédes</i> (1692)
Molière	<i>Le Sicilien</i> (1655)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>De schilder door liefde</i> (1682)
Molière	<i>L'Ecole des Maris</i> (1661)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>De listige vryster</i> (1690)
Philippe Quinault	<i>Agrippa Roi d'Albe ou Le Faux Tiberinus</i> (1663)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Agrippa, koning van Alba</i> (1669)
Molière	<i>Le Mariage Forcé</i> (1664)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Het gedwongene huwelyk</i> (1682)
Molière	<i>Le Médecin Malgré Lui</i> (1666)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Fielebout</i> (1680)
Jean Racine	<i>Andromaque</i> (1668)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Andromaché</i> (1678)
Adrien-Thomas Perdou de Subligny	<i>La Folle Querelle ou La Critique d'Andromaque</i> (1668)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>De gelukte list</i> (1682)
Philippe Quinault	<i>Astrate Roi de Tyr</i> (1670)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Astrate, koning van Tyrus</i> (1670)
Pierre Corneille	<i>Ariane</i> (1672)	Katharyne Lescailje	<i>Ariadne</i> (1693)
Jean Racine	<i>Iphigénie</i> (1674)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Ifigenia</i> (1678)
Antoinette du Ligier de la Garde Deshoulières	<i>Genseric</i> (1680)	Katharyne Lescailje	<i>Genseric</i> (1685)
Jean François Juvénon de La Thuilerie	<i>Hercule</i> (1681)	Katharyne Lescailje	<i>Herkules en Dianira</i> (1688)
Pierre Corneille	<i>Cinna</i> (1682)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Cinna</i> (1680)
Philippe Quinault	<i>Roland</i> (1685)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>Roeland</i> (1686)
Joseph Desmarres	<i>Merlin Dragon ou La Dragonne</i> (1690)	Nil Volentibus Arduum	<i>De Amsterdamsche dragonnade</i> (1714)

5. Results

Character alignment was applied to the 25 multilingual pairs of plays listed in Table 1, computing the distance between each adaptation and its source. Figure 4 displays the intertextual distance per pair based on the successfully aligned characters per play, ranking the 25 adaptations based on their score on the Adaptation Index. A score of 1.0 represents a literal line-for-line translation whereas a score of 0.0 would indicate that the adaptation is completely independent from its source in terms of the composition of its character roles. Based on this ranking, adaptations like Lescaillie’s 1693 version of Pierre Corneille’s 1672 French play *Ariane* (Adaptation Index score: 0.99), Vondel’s version of *Iphigenia in Tauris* (414 BCE) by Euripides (0.98), and Lescaillie’s 1688 version of Jean François Juvénon de La Thuillierie’s French play *Hercule* (1681) (0.98) can be qualified as highly literal retellings, if not direct translations. On the other end of the ranking, plays like *De schilder door liefde* (1682) (0.45), *Fielebout* (1680) (0.50) and *Het spookend weeuwtje* (1670) (0.55) can be identified as highly free adaptations with a very limited kinship to their source.

Figure 4: Distance between source and adaptation in 25 early modern Dutch plays, ranked by their Adaptation Index number

The color codes used in Figure 4 illustrate differences between genres represented in the corpus. These differences suggest that comedies or farces (orange) are usually adapted more freely than tragedies (blue). Although larger samples are needed to prove the existence of such genre-based differences in adaptation strategies, the pattern aligns with previous studies showing that early modern playwrights who adapted foreign tragedies were more likely to stay closer to the source than authors who imported farces and comedies from abroad [23]. This relationship between genre and textual distance between source and adaptation confirms that the Adaptation Index can be used to model and quantify patterns in adaptation strategies as a function of (for example) the genre, author, time period, language or cultural context of the source.

Besides these distinctions on the corpus-level, the Adaptation Index can be used to reveal textual distances in individual pairs of plays. Figure 5, 6, and 7 offer a visual representation of the Adaptation Index for each of the Dutch *Iphigenia* adaptations discussed above. These spider graphs offer visual and quantitative support for the fact that in 1617 Samuel Coster produced a very free adaptation of Euripides’s *Iphigenia in Aulis*, with a low Adaptation Index number of 0.64. He changed the composition and the distribution of roles considerably, indicated by a low number of overlap in the number of (matched) speakers and matched lines. In contrast, Vondel’s 1666 version of *Iphigenia*

in Tauris can be qualified as a highly literal translation based on its Adaptation Index of 0.99 with 1.0 scores close to 1.0 across the five variables (see Figure 6). Like Vondel, Nil Volentibus Arduum also closely followed their model, Jean Racine *Iphigénie* (1674), indicated by the play’s Adaptation Index number of 0.95. The relatively large difference in the number of speakers reflects the above discussed intervention in the final act – justified on poetical grounds in the preface discussed above – to introduce characters who are absent in Racine’s source. These individual cases show that the Adaptation Index offers a useful and relatively detailed metric for textual distances between drama adaptations and their sources.

Figure 5: *Iphigenia* by Coster (1617) versus *Iphigenia in Aulis* (405 BCE) by Euripides

Figure 6: *Ifigenie in Tauren* by Vondel (1666) versus *Iphigenia in Tauris* by Euripides (414 BCE)

Figure 7: *Ifigenia* by Nil Volentibus Arduum (1678) versus *Iphigénie* by Racine (1674)

6. Conclusion

Early modern European theatres were fundamentally multilingual and transnational, but so far the key role of translations and adaptations has been neglected in computational drama studies. The field simply lacks adequate computational methods to compare plays across linguistic and cultural borders. This paper addressed that methodological need with a proposal for a new formalist approach to adaptation strategies in early modern drama based on automatic character alignment. It designed, evaluated and applied an algorithm for matching equivalent speakers based on speech turn patterns in parallel versions of the same play (an adaptation and its source). Quantifying the normalised distance between the source play and the target play on five variables, it developed a new metric – the ‘Adaptation Index’ – that enables researchers to formalise and quantify different adaptation strategies on a scale from 0.0 to 1.0. The Adaptation Index thus offers a standardised metric enabling comparative studies of theatre adaptations, both on the corpus level and on the level of individual plays.

Studies on the corpus level could test how adaptation strategies depended on external factors such as source language, genre, or author. The case study from this paper for example suggested that on Dutch stages, foreign tragedies were adapted differently than comedies and farces, providing quantitative evidence of genre-based differences in adaptation conventions. A specific focus on three Dutch adaptations of plays about Iphigenia furthermore revealed how the Adaptation Index could be used to support qualitative readings of individual plays that also take literary and historical-political contexts into account.

These findings for example evoke new questions about the reception of the Iphigenia myths in European drama at large. If one would cast a wider net to a larger selection of plays from the DraCor infrastructure and beyond, the Adaptation Index can support systematic comparisons between translations and adaptations of Iphigenia plays from different languages and literary traditions, such as *Iphigénie* (1640) by Jean Rotrou, *Iphigénie* (1675) by Michel Leclerc, *Iphigénie en Tauride* (1757) by Claude Guymond de la Touche, *Iphigenia in Tauris* (1771, based on Guymon de la Touche) by Maria Geertruida de Cambon van der Werken, *Iphigenie auf Tauris* (1787) by Johann Wolfgang Goethe, and many more. The corpora are already available for such comparative studies, and metrics like the Adaptation Index will help us not only to establish and formalise links between parallel plays in those corpora, but also to reconstruct the function of literary modeling – *Imitatio* – in different literary traditions.

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Declaration on Generative AI

The author has not employed any Generative AI tools.

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A. Online Resources

The corpus used for this study can be downloaded from <https://dracor.org/>.

The code and documentation are available as a user-friendly Jupyter Notebook at <https://github.com/lucasvanderdeijl/>.

Ecologies on stage

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Abstract

In this study we investigate the importance of ecological aspects in German drama. We show how ecological codes—i.e. references to ecological entities and their distribution, density and diversity—are physically brought on stage (through stage directions) and hinted at (through character speech, the “Wortkulisse”¹). Furthermore, we investigate a diachronic and interrelational perspective. Thus, we can show that ecological entities altogether are rarely mentioned in dramatic texts in general. Outliers to this rule tend to appear in two peaks: the first starting around 1775 and ending around 1850 and a much smaller one around 1900. Our research question is how important ecological entities are for German drama and whether physically represented and speech evoked dramatic sceneries differ with regard to their representation. We hypothesize that density as well as diversity of words representing ecological entities is higher in character speech than in stage directions, because the former is not limited to what can be physically brought to the stage. Ecocodes of speech are more complex than ecocodes of the stage. Using GerDraCor and computational tools and methods we contribute not only to the field of computational environmental humanities but also to discussions about the relation between stage directions and spoken text.

Keywords

Ecocriticism, Network analysis, Computational Environmental Humanities

1. Ecologies in Literature

Literary studies that focus on the relationship between humans and their environments are often based on the concept of ecology, as coined by the Jena zoologist Ernst Haeckel in 1866: an ensemble of integrated systems in which everything is interdependent [1]. This perspective gained popularity in the environmental debates of the 1970s, when—stimulated by the Club of Rome’s report—questions of The Limits of Growth [2] became widely discussed in the (post-)industrialized nations. In contrast to Anglo-Saxon literary studies, which has turned its attention to the topic of nature and ecology under the banner of ecocriticism since the 1970s and 1980s, there was initially no significant parallel development in German-language literary studies [3, 12-17].

This changed at the end of the millennium, when more publications tested an ecological perspective on German speaking literature [e.g. 3, 4]. Especially in light of the climate crisis, this literary research has picked up speed [e.g. 5, 6, 7], perhaps most notably in the form of the rise of literary and cultural animal [8] and plant studies [9]. However, theatre and drama as ecological art forms have only recently emerged as research objects [e.g. 10, 11, 12]. The topic of Computational Environmental Humanities has only been taken up in the last ten years. This has resulted in first quantitative case studies on the role of biodiversity in literature [13, 14, 15], questions of agency and personification of nature [16], and sustainability [17, 18]. In addition, quantitative eco-critical perspectives mostly focus on animals and plants or environments while overarching perspectives on the strategies and techniques of literary

¹We use the German term as there is no meaningful translation. What we refer to is the setting or scenery which is built through language.

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‘nature building’ are rare. We address this desiderata by investigating the appearance and interplay of ecological entities within a large corpus of dramas. The diachronic perspective has been of special interest for Langer et al. [13, 14] who found that biodiversity in literature was rising until 1835 and then declining. Although Piper [15] has disproved this finding, there seem to be some interesting breaking points for richness and abundance of ecological entities in English narrative fiction. One lies around 1825 when frequencies of plants and animals rise rapidly in both considered corpora. The other one can be found around 1910. [cf. 15, 11 and figure 8]. Surely, industrialization and urbanisation could play a significant role. As Piper hypothesizes, the data could support the modern idea of attachment of humans to nature and that the effort to keep nature part of storyworlds even if it is less present in the actual surrounding grows [cf. 15, 12]. In this paper we try to connect to this idea by aligning our findings on German drama with the findings by Langer et al. and Piper. Heise points out the relevance of literary analysis for ecological research by stating that even “stable concepts and well-researched facts from the natural sciences are culturally filtered, distorted, and reinterpreted” [19, 9]. She argues that current discourses on the species crisis, species extinction, and thinking about nature and the environment “cannot be isolated from a historical and cultural context.” In a similar line of argument, scientists like marine biologist Antje Boetius and molecular biologist Hans-Jörg Rheinberger assign the arts, and theater in particular, an important role in the ecological discourse, insofar as art can help to communicate and popularize scientific knowledge [20]. Literary texts are thus part of the ecological discourse, but their function is not limited to the mere reproduction of scientific findings: Rather, literature as an art form comments on, transforms and develops these findings according to its own aesthetics and poetics and against the background of genre history. Therefore, we suggest that literary texts cannot be examined 1:1 by using methods of natural sciences and complement approaches of using biological metrics with measures aimed at including cultural context. We argue that the “interconnectedness of all living and non-living things”, which Morton describes as mesh [21, 28] can also be understood as a text structure phenomenon in the realm of literature—a text structure phenomenon which we examine using network analysis.

2. Method and corpus

To analyse ecologies on stage we developed a pipeline of computational methods. We use a transfer-learning-tool called NTEE (Neiss TEI Entity Enricher [22, 23]) to train a classifier to automatically annotate ecological entities. Similar to Langer et al. [13, 14] we use quantitative metrics to measure density and diversity of biological entities in literature. In order to evaluate how entities are distributed throughout the corpus we calculate their cultural presence. We use network analysis to compare common and rarely mentioned species in the overall corpus, stage directions and character speech. Finally, as part of the analysis of our data, we further categorise plant and animal species that appear in the plays.

2.1. Machine learning and automated annotation

We trained a classifier on the automated annotation of animals, plants and habitats using passages of EcoCor [24], i.e. from 31 ecocritically relevant prose texts, from 5 dramatic texts taken from GerDraCor [25] and from 5 travelogues from Projekt Gutenberg. By annotating animals, plants and habitats, we are following the Fauna-Flora-Habitat (FFH) classification system from the European Nature Conservation Directive 92/43/EEC¹. We extracted 5.000 token passages from each of the training texts and used 10.000-token passages from 4 prose texts as well as 3 fully manually annotated dramatic texts as test corpus. The average overall F1-score is 0,8248, the median is 0,8431 (cf. Table 1).

¹The classification of the European Nature Conservation Directive can be found under <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1992/43/oj/eng> [access: July 28th]

Table 1

F1 scores for animals, plants and habitats as well as overall F1 score per test-text and for the whole test corpus

Texts	Animals	Plants	Habitats	Overall
Marlitt Die zweite Frau (1874)	0.6067	0.8242	0.8092	0.7711
Spyri Heidi (1880)	0.7448	0.8764	0.8506	0.8201
Raabe Pfisters Mühle (1884)	0.8067	0.8504	0.8561	0.8431
Löns Tiergeschichten (1906-1916)	0.8398	0.8789	0.8333	0.8475
Schiller Wilhelm Tell (1804)	0.7975	0.75	0.8761	0.8487
Eichendorff Der letzte Held (1830)	0.7769	0.7974	0.8909	0.8466
Raimund Die Zauberkrone (1928)	0.7673	0.7317	0.8529	0.7969
Mean	0.7628	0.8155	0.8527	0.8248
Median	0.7769	0.8242	0.8529	0.8431

2.2. Measuring ecologies in drama

For comparison of distributions of ecological entities in stage direction and character speech we calculate a number of metrics. In line with Langer et al. (2021, 2022) we capture richness and abundance of ecological entities². Additionally, we calculate the density of references to ecological entities in order to normalise the text length. To include cultural presence we measure the distribution of all animals, plants and habitats in the corpus by calculating the percentage of the corpus they are mentioned in. Table 2 shows an overview of the measurements and calculations. All measures are calculated using lemmatized data.

Table 2

Measures and metrics used to analyse ecologies on stage

Metric	Calculation	Reference
Abundance	Number of Tokens	[13]
Richness	Number of Types	[13]
Density	Number of tokens / Number of words in text Relative parameter capturing the percentage of a given corpus an entity is mentioned in (without considering the frequency):	own approach
Cultural presence	sporadic presence: mentioned in 0–20% of texts extended presence: mentioned in 21–40% of texts significant presence: mentioned in 41–60% of texts majority presence: mentioned in 61–80% of texts exceptional presence: mentioned in over 80% of texts	own approach

2.3. Network analysis

The above named metrics show how numerous ecological entities are, how frequent the phenomenon is, and how present different ecology-terms are in dramatic literature. As we are also interested in questions of interconnectedness, we supplement these measurements with a network analysis. We compare networks of ecological entities in stage directions and character speech and thus see how ecologies are modeled in drama. Network analysis shows us whether texts tend to refer to common ecological entities or to rare and specific terms. Additionally, network analysis takes into account that

²We do not capture Shannon Diversity as proposed by Langer et al. [13, 14], because it includes the number of individuals, which we are convinced cannot be extracted by distant reading of literary texts and we also do not calculate beta diversity as we do not use sampling in our study (because the equation of 1.000 word-frames with 1 square metre of earth or landscape does not seem sufficiently convincing).

some entities are mentioned very often in one or several texts and others might show lower frequencies but are mentioned in many different texts.

2.4. Corpus

We use GerDraCor [25] in a downloaded version from March 2025. It includes 732 German dramas in TEI-XML-format. Out of technical reasons we excluded 52 texts. This leaves us with an analysis corpus of 680 texts covering a timespan from 1510 to 1947. Most texts stem from 1750–1950.

3. Ecologies in drama

Based on the number of annotations from all three categories, the corpus can be divided into texts with low, medium and high eco-frequency. As can be seen from Table 3 most texts rarely mention ecological entities (0–100, 53.24%), 30.6% show medium eco-frequency (100–200) and 16.32% (111 texts) include more than 200 references to said entities.

Table 3
Textcorpus grouped by absolute number of annotations

total number of annotations	number of texts
0–100	362
100–200	208
200–300	68
300–400	23
400–500	9
500–600	6
600–1,000	4
2,236	1

Altogether there are 31,438 references to animals (abundance) in the analysis corpus and 5,887 different types are mentioned (richness). Plants show a comparatively low abundance of 20,342 and also a lower richness with 3,811 types. The most frequent references occur to habitats with 32,053 tokens (abundance) but with 3,706 types the lowest richness shows within the habitat-category. On average, German drama includes 47.14 references to habitats, 46.23 to animals and 29.9 to plants. The overall density is 0.00799. From previous and ongoing research we know that German prose texts from 1870–1920 have an average density of 0.0108 [26]. From this comparison and the data in Table 3 we can conclude that the density of ecological entities in German drama is usually low and generally lower than in German prose texts.

As can be seen from Figure 1 none of the lemmatized animal and plant terms reaches a majority or higher presence. Only two animal and plant terms are significantly present. Twelve animal and six plant terms show an extended presence and the vast majority is sporadically present. The pattern is slightly different for habitats. One term is exceptionally present (“world” / “welt”), one shows a majority presence (“land” / “land”), four are significantly present (“garden” / “garten”, “mountain” / “berg”, “field” / “feld”, “forest” / “wald”), five show extended presence and the vast majority is sporadically present.

The diachronic perspective shown in Figure 2 aligns well with the findings of Langer et al. [13] and Piper [15]. Although we work on a different domain and a smaller corpus, it can be seen that references to ecological entities rise between 1750 and 1800 and decline until around 1860. But then the curves rise again, revealing a two-parted wave-like distribution. A look at the three categories differentiated in this study enables a more fine-grained analysis. While the animal-plot on the top left shows a similar pattern of two peaks, the plant-plot in the middle shows a flatter baseline, but also more outliers between 1750 and 1850 and around 1900. The habitat-plot is more scattered altogether, but also shows a slight wave-pattern.

Figure 1: Cultural presence of animal, plant and habitat terms.

Figure 2: Diachronic view of relative frequencies (density) of animals (brown), plants (light green), habitats (dark green) and all categories (blue) with a focus on 1700–1950.

A comparison with data taken from Piper³ [15] reveals the similarity especially with a corpus of around 1,700 texts (Stanford corpus, cf. Figure 3). Although both Piper’s corpora are considerably larger than GerDraCor, the Stanford corpus comes closer (Hathi Trust includes about 300,000 texts). Astonishingly, both German plays and English narratives show the rise in relative frequency of plants and animals shortly after 1800. Both curves show that the frequency for plants stays rather flat afterwards while the animal-curve shows a short decline and then rises up again around 1900 but does not reach the former top values. It is especially striking that the range of the first peak in German plays goes much higher than in English narratives. Top values reach 0.006 and 0.007 whereas top values in Piper’s data do not go beyond 0,0025 (Stanford) or 0,004 (Hathi trust, with top-values around 1960

³In this comparison we focus on animals and plants, because these are the categories taken into account by Piper.

which is beyond the scope of GerDraCor).

Figure 8. Relative abundance of plants and animals in the different fiction datasets.

Figure 3: Comparison of GerDraCor data and English narratives analysed by Piper. The green curve on the top left stands for plants, the brown for animals and the graphic “Frequency of plants and animals in English Fiction 1800–2000” is taken from Piper [15].

A possible explanation could be that in 1775 the first forest reform started in Germany [27, 3]. This reform is closely connected to the history of sustainability as it takes up an idea coined in 1713 by Hanns Carl von Carlowitz [cf. 28, 37]. Carlowitz coins the term “nachhaltig” (“sustainable”) to designate a balance between growth and usage of the forest [cf. 29, 27]. The forest reform is closely associated with Anna Amalia who initiated it [28, 37]. As duchess of Sachsen-Weimar and Eisenach, Anna Amalia is known for being very well connected to artists of her time, especially authors and playwrights like e.g. Wieland [30, 8] and Goethe [31]. It seems plausible that the discourse on sustainable forestry came to artists and playwrights in social gatherings of Anna Amalia’s “Musenhof”. Moreover, the high density of ecological entities between 1800 and 1850 seems to underline the prominent presence of forestry topics in the realistic epoch [32]. Our data imply that in this timeframe “ecology-focused and environmentally relevant ways of thinking and values are finding their way into literature”—not just in prose but also especially in German drama⁴ [33, 375]. For this study the question raised by Piper whether the development of references to ecological taxa can really be interpreted in connection to real-world developments might be answered positively. But the hypothesis of a correlation between Anna Amalia’s eco-political and her cultural influence should be further analysed to rule out the possibility of mere

⁴For the time being our only comparison is with narratives in English, in future research we shall back up this hypothesis with a large scale analysis on German prose texts.

coincidence. Nevertheless, it comes as a surprise that the impact seems to be directly measurable using simple metrics like density of ecological entities. However, it must also be taken into account that peaks in the history of ecologies on stage are mostly caused by an increase of outliers as Figure 2 clearly shows.

3.1. Ecologies on stage

In theatre studies animals are considered as important parts of the staging [12]. Whereas some animals such as dogs can be brought to the limited space of a stage, others like wolves and dolphins can't or at least won't be easily brought on scene. Moreover, stage directions are usually kept very short leaving not much room for the inclusion of references to ecological entities. In GerDraCor ecological entities are referenced with 10,369 tokens (abundance) and 2,467 types (richness) in stage directions. Animals are referenced with 3,390 tokens and 985 types, plants with 3,235 tokens and 731 types and habitats with 3,744 tokens and 751 types. The density is 0.0082.

Having a closer look at the terms used to reference ecological entities in stage directions we see that in the top 20 animal-referencing words (cf. Figure 4), “horse” (“pferd”) shows the highest frequency but is closely followed by “head” (“kopf”) and “feather” (“feder”) two comparatively small body parts of animals that can actually be brought on stage for decoration and scenery. More surprising are terms like “lion” (“löwe”), “crab” (“krabbe”) and “dolphins” (“delfine”).

Figure 4: Top 20 animal-referencing words in stage directions.

The raw frequencies can give a first impression on quantitatively dominant terms used to reference ecological entities but they tell little about how widespread a phenomenon is in a given corpus. Therefore, we extracted the annotated data from the stage directions and built networks. In our networks there are two types of nodes: ecology-terms and text-titles. We cleaned the network-data, i.e. we disambiguated terms to species (e.g. grouping together “horse” and “horses” to “horse”) and deleted false positives. As can be seen in the network visualisation in Figure 5 the center (left) is a relatively small group of more or less connected nodes that show which terms are represented in how many plays. The small representation of the whole network on the top right depicts how many plays show either none or only one reference to an animal-term which is very specific and therefore not connected to the center.

The highest degree of an animal-term node is 74 and it is the term “head”, which means that the highest connected term is only present in 10.88% of texts of the corpus. The term which comes second is “feather” which shows up in 53 texts, i.e. in 7.79% of the corpus. “Horse” as a species is referenced in the stage directions of 44 plays (6.47%) and “dog” (“hund”) in 36 plays (5.29%). The lion as one of the top 20 most frequently named animals is only referenced in the stage directions of 22 plays (3.24%)

Figure 5: Network of animal-references in stage directions.

and the dolphin only in three (0.44%). In stage directions of 280 plays, i.e. 41.78% of the corpus, there has been no animal reference found. In stage directions of 132 plays (19.41%) only one animal-term is mentioned. So, in 61.19% of the corpus there is no or only one single reference to animals in the stage directions. Our data shows that animals play a very small role altogether in this part of the texts.

As the raw numbers show, plants are referenced in a less diverse way as only 731 types are mentioned in the stage directions. As the top 20 frequency list (cf. Figure 6) reveals, the most frequent plant-terms are used much more often than the most frequent animal terms. “Flower” (“blume”) has a frequency of 256 and “rose” (“rose”) of 244 whereas the scale for animal terms does not reach far beyond 100. Flowers, trees (“Baum”, “Bäume”) and parts of plants like leaves (“blatt”) all show in the top twenty list.

Figure 6: Top 20 plant-referencing words in stage directions.

The disambiguated and cleaned network of plant-terms in plays shows a similar yet different pattern

(cf. Figure 7). There are also many texts with no or a very low number of plant-references as the small representation of the whole network on the top right shows. The center shows a network that can be sub-organized according to clusters using a modularity class algorithm. The colors used in the visualization represent especially well connected groups and show that there is a group of plays preferring flowers and one that rather references trees. There is a “rose”-cluster and a “leaves”-cluster.

Figure 7: Network of plant-references in stage directions (colored by modularity class).

The most frequent term “flower” is also the most well connected as it shows up in 133 plays (19.56%). Trees are referenced in 105 plays (15.44%). On the other side of the spectrum 216 texts (31.76%) show zero references to plants and 139 (20.44%) only one. Altogether, 52.2% of the texts show one or less references to plants. All in all, plants are more likely to be included in the stage directions of a play than animals. They seem to be more important for the staging of a setting than animals.

Habitats show a different pattern. Most strikingly the term “garden” (“garten”) shows up disproportionately often in the stage directions of this corpus (cf. Figure 8). Whereas “garden” is mentioned 454 times, the next frequent term “forest” (“wald”) only shows up 161 times. German plays seem to be very often set in gardens and way less often in forests, “caves” (“höhle”) or at the “shore” (“ufer”).

Once again a network-representation shows a more nuanced picture (cf. Figure 9). As seen before, there is a well connected larger network which groups plays according to the habitat-terms they mention. “Garden” is mentioned in 153 plays (22.5%), so it is actually not much more connected than the most frequent plant-term “flower”. It is also noticeable that the area centering the term “garden” in the network is almost building a sub-network. Indeed the modularity classes visualized by the colors show that there are certain areas of the network building around central very frequent habitats. Apart from the “garden-area” there is one for “surrounding” (“gegend”), “forest”, “mountain” (“berg”), “shore” and “cave”. Each of these terms clusters with a group of plays. Plays that feature the term “forest” and plays surrounding the term “cave” overlap, as well as the garden-cluster and the forest-cluster. But there is not much overlap between “shore” and “mountain”, “cave” or “garden”. Along these lines, one could differentiate “garden-plays”, “shore-plays”, “forest-plays” and “mountain-plays” of which the “garden-plays” are the largest group.

A focus on highly frequent and well connected terms tends to imply that a phenomenon is of great relevance for a corpus. But at the same time the visualization shows that there are plays that do not mention habitats or only mention very few of them and therefore build a ring at the margins (see upper

Figure 8: Top 20 habitat-referencing words in stage directions.

right corner). There are 268 (39.4%) plays not referencing a single habitat in the stage directions and 125 (18.38%) featuring only one habitat-term. Altogether 57.78% of the corpus do not or only once reference a habitat in the stage directions. This finding indicates that whereas plants are most often included in stage directions (in 47.8% of the corpus) and animal references are featured in the smallest proportion of the corpus (38.81%), habitats are in the middle being featured in the stage directions of 42.22% of the GerDraCor-plays.

The analysis of ecological entities referenced in the stage directions has shown that there is always a large percentage of plays featuring no or only one reference to the ecological entity class in question. This means that ecologies are not always brought on stage physically. If ecological entities do play a role in stage directions it is mostly the category of plants. Animals are often represented using body parts like heads or feathers. Flowers play the most important role when it comes to ecological entities in stage directions. The habitat named in the largest group of plays is the garden. Forest, mountain and shore are referenced by a much smaller group. This leads us to the conclusion that what is brought to the stage is essentially human-centred and to a large extent culturally (over)coded. The garden is a habitat largely formed by humans. Animals are at least partly referenced through body parts used as collected items such as feathers. It shows that drama is essentially anthropocentric when it comes to the representation of ecologies on scene via stage directions. However, they are only a very limited part of dramatic texts (1,267,725 words in comparison to 10,123,435 words in character speech). We therefore now turn to character speech.

3.2. Ecologies in the “Wortkulisse”

Whereas stage directions most probably include information on how to bring ecologies to the physical space of the stage, character speech builds up a more figurative ecology—this world building via dialogue or monologue has been termed “Wortkulisse” [34, 142-144]. Our starting hypothesis was that density and diversity of ecologies in the “Wortkulisse” is higher than in the stage directions, because there are fewer limits to what can be said and imagined than what can be physically staged—a fact that has been reflected in drama since antiquity by the importance of epic forms like messenger speech and teichoscopy.

The raw numbers seem to speak in favour of this hypothesis. In GerDraCor ecological entities in character speech are referenced with 78,102 tokens (abundance) and 11,511 types (richness), which is much more than can be found in stage directions. Animals are referenced with 29,812 tokens and 5,091 types, plants with 18,874 tokens and 3,320 types and habitats with 29,415 tokens and 3,100 types. The

Figure 9: Network of habitat-references in stage directions (colored by modularity class).

density is 0.0077, which is slightly lower than in stage directions. So the first part of our hypothesis that the density of ecological entities is lower in stage directions can be rejected. The diversity according to abundance and richness indeed seems to be higher in character speech. To get to know more about this second aspect of ecologies in drama we will now have a closer look on the three categories.

There is a considerable overlay between animals mentioned in stage directions and in character speech. Horses and dogs are both prominent as well as birds (“vogel”), lions, snakes (“schlange”), hawks (“adler”) and roosters (“hahn”). Character speech seems to feature less body parts, although “feather” does show up in both top 20 lists (cf. Figures 5 and 10). However, the top frequencies do not tell anything about the distribution of terms throughout the corpus.

The first thing that shows in the network of animal terms in character speech is that there are much less texts gathering at the margins (Figure 11). The center builds a circular form with the most prominent terms “dog”, “horse”, “bird” and “animal” (“tier”) in the middle. Similar to the stage direction animal network, no groups are forming which can be validated using a cluster algorithm.

Whereas the network and the absolute frequencies give the impression that a majority of plays feature dogs, horses and birds in character speech, this turns out to be a misinterpretation of the data. In fact, the term “dog” does only appear in 45.7% of the plays. If the data is disambiguated and terms like “dog” and “dogs” are grouped (as has been done in the network data), dogs can still only be found in 52.9% of the corpus (not counting more specific species like “great dane” (“Dogge”). The term “horse” is mentioned in 44.85% of the corpus and horses in general in 46% of the texts (not counting specific terms like “apple mould” (“Apfelschimmel”).

There are 24 plays that do not mention any animal terms in character speech (3.53%) and 26 (3.82%)

Figure 10: Top 20 animal-referencing words in character speech.

Figure 11: Network of animal-references in character speech.

include only one animal-reference. This means that 7.35% show one or no animal-terms, which is a much smaller proportion than for the stage directions. For the “Wortkulisse” animals seem to play a larger role than for the actual scenery. To some extent this is probably due to the fact that animals are used metaphorically or in other creative ways in the speaker’s text (e.g. “ohrwurm”, “tugendschweinigel”, or “menschenwurm”).

Already at first glance, the network for plants in Figure 13 shows two things. Firstly, there are more plays with only one or no references to plants than there have been for animals. Secondly, similar to the stage direction network the character speech shows a slight tendency to build clusters. There are clusters for some of the most frequent terms shown in Figure 12. i.e. for “rose” (colored in pink),

Figure 12: Top 20 plant-referencing words in character speech.

Figure 13: Network of plant-references in character speech.

“flower” (colored in blue), “leaf” (colored in orange) and “tree” (colored in green) as well as for “wine” (“wein”, colored in grey). Additionally there is a cluster gathering around parts of plants like “fruit” (“frucht”), “branch” (“zweig”), “root” (“wurzel”) and “trunk” (“stamm”), colored in purple. However, the clusters are not as clearly defined as those that have been found in the network for stage directions. Similar to the network for animals in character speech (Figure 11), the circular form of this network gives the impression that the most frequent terms, that also define the clusters, are very central and probably spread widely throughout the corpus. This impression is again misleading. “flower” can only be found in 47.65% of the texts. The second best connected term “tree” appears in 43.1% of the texts. 30

texts (4.4%) do not include any references to plants in character speech and another 30 show only one plant-term. Altogether 8.8% of the texts include only one or no reference to plants, which is again a smaller number than for stage directions.

Figure 14: Top 20 habitat-referencing words in character speech.

Figure 15: Network of habitat-references in character speech.

The habitat-network in Figure 15 looks similar to the animal-network in Figure 11. Again there are few texts that are not connected to the center of the network and again the main network shows a circular shape. The tendency to build clusters is higher than for the plant-network in Figure 13 but clusters are not nearly as well defined as they are in the habitat-network for the stage directions. Most central terms are “world” (“welt”), “land” (“land”), “garden”, “forest”, “field” (“feld”), “mountain” (“berg”), and “ocean” (“meer”). These are also the most frequent (cf. Figure 14) and central terms for the

clusters, but these clusters overlap and don't build groups (cf. Figure 15). Comparing the habitats in character speech with those mentioned in stage directions, one can state that the most connected terms "world" and "land" designate very broad areas. They are also mentioned in large proportions of the corpus ("world": 89%, "land": 70,4%). On the other side of the spectrum there are 9 (1.3%) texts that do not include references to habitats in character speech and 23 (3.4%) that only mention one habitat. Altogether only 4.7% of the character speech texts mention habitats only once or not even one time. In comparison to the animals and plants, one can state that speaking about habitats seems to be more common for German plays than speaking about animals and plants. In relation to the data from the stage directions one can also conclude that whereas plants in comparison to animals and habitats are most often part of the stage directions they are the least dominant in character speech. Plants seem to be seen on stage rather than talked about. They thus form the physically staged storyworld which is then populated by animals and set into relation with the world's habitats through character speech.

The relation of ecologies in different plays shows that references to animals, plants and habitats are optional, especially when it comes to stage directions. A majority of plays does not feature animals, plants and habitats or mentions only one of them. In character speech, ecologies are far more widespread. Only a minority of texts include one or no animal, plant or habitat reference with habitats being the least optional category. However, the evidence shows that it is not necessary to weave ecological meshes into German plays. The diversity, i.e. abundance and richness measured with raw frequencies and distribution measured with cultural presence and analysed in networks, is higher in character speech than in stage directions. The analysis of density and diversity seems to prove that, especially in stage directions, ecologies of German plays are human-centered. However, the data gathered from the automated annotation could only give a first glimpse on this topic. In the next chapter we turn to the analysis of the cultural contexts in the sense of the human-ecology-relation by grouping the annotations according to the question of how closely the referenced entities are connected to human life.

4. Domesticated and wild Ecologies in Drama

In order to find out which kind of animals and plants occur particularly frequently in our corpus, and how they relate to human life, we further categorized the annotations (Figure 16 and 17). One common feature is the high weighting of wild animals (Figure 16). Wild animals such as lions, foxes, ravens, worms, and mice⁵ are very common in both modes and our data show that wild animals dominate the corpus. Domesticated animals such as goats, chickens, donkeys, and oxen are also common in both text forms, as are animal parts. Once again, it becomes clear that the mode of animal depiction differs between character speech and stage directions. When taking a closer look at the less frequent annotations, our data show that references to animals are more diverse within character speech: Here, special species such as parasites (leeches, tapeworms) and zoonoses⁶ (viruses, tubercle bacilli) occur. These life forms, which are difficult to portray on stage, are hardly found in the stage directions (Figure 17). With regard to larger groups of animals, our data also show the connection between portrayability and frequency.

Looking at a fine-grained categorization of plants (Figures 18 and 19) one can see that especially cultivated plants that have a use for humans as food or medicine, such as almonds, cherries, rice or many different kinds of herbs, are very dominant in our corpus—in character speech and in stage directions. The great presence of cultivated and ornamental plants fits with the observation that a comparatively large number of dramas feature the garden as a cultivated space of nature. Analogous to the ranking for animals, parts of plants are among the most frequent annotations. Once again the eco-profile is

⁵We define the 'wildness' of animals as greater the more independent their lives are portrayed from those of humans.

⁶Minor life forms such as bacteria and mushrooms haven't been part of our manual annotations from the beginning, but the first prototypical classifier annotated them as animals and plants, because they are integrated into the texts in a similar way. We therefore decided to include them in our top-level categories in a second annotation round. However, as the classifier is still in a prototypical stage, these life forms might be classified in a different way in the productive version. In any case this shows that, what is annotated is not "an animal" or "a plant" but something represented in the texts like an animal or a plant.

Figure 16: Further categorization of animals mentioned in character speech.

Figure 17: Further categorization of animals mentioned in the stage directions.

more faceted within character speech. Fabulous plants such as ‘tree of life’, ‘magic flower’, or ‘fruit of heaven’ are not mentioned at all within the stage directions. More specific kinds of plants such as mushrooms—we included the realm of fungi in our plant annotations (cf. footnote 7)—(for example “truffle” or “poisonous mushroom”) and artificial plants (“paper flower”, “flowerpainting” or the “may tree”) appear in character speech in a slightly higher number.

5. Conclusion

We presented a computational approach that is suitable for the digital analysis of ecologies on stage. Abundance, richness, density and cultural presence can be used as measurable indicators. From a methodological perspective, we showed that network analysis gives us the opportunity to visualize the mesh of ecologies on stage. Follow-up research would involve adding humans and hyperobjects to this network [21, 28]. We have highlighted that eco-phenomena are a low-frequency phenomenon and the representation of plants, habitats, and animals differs depending on whether they are mentioned in the “Wortkulisse” or the stage directions.

Figure 18: Further categorization of plants mentioned in character speech.

Figure 19: Further categorization of plants mentioned in the stage directions.

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used Gemini for vibe-coding the notebook used in this analysis. After using these tool(s)/service(s), the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the publication's content. All code and data are publicly available at Github.

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A. Online Resources

Data and code used for this analysis are available at

- GitHub

Annotating Digital Traces of Performance: Methods and Approaches

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Abstract

In the project outlined in this paper, we scope the use of the TEI XML format as a means of representing the content and structure of video recordings of theatre performances based on or influenced by ancient Greek or Roman drama. We argue that to capture the multimodal nature of video recordings of drama, additional layers of TEI encoding must be devised and brought into contact with one another. Consideration of which aspects can be usefully and unambiguously captured for the purposes of computational analysis prompts questions about the differences between *collecting* data and *creating* data. The extent to which tools and data formats can shape methodological approaches and conceptual understandings becomes a salient question. The experiential nature of theatre performance, the cumulative layers of meaning in audiovisual recordings of performances, and the core theme of intermediality in reception theory, all prompt us to highlight the importance of the observer-specific, user-driven, context-aware aspects of interpretation when sharing our outputs. We propose to draw attention to these issues by embedding our TEI documents in a web interface which, through its interactive nature, defamiliarizes content, encourages debate, and allows for parallel interpretation through annotation, presenting data collection and analysis as knowledge-in-the-making.

Keywords

Text Encoding Initiative, data creation, performance archives, video recordings, Greek and Roman drama

1. Introduction

The archival collections held by the University of Oxford's Archive of Performances of Greek and Roman Drama (henceforth APGRD) consist of over 14,000 items capturing traces of performances inspired by the ancient Greek and Roman dramatic corpora; and include over 500 performance recordings.² Until now the VHS, DVDs, and mp4 files that make up this audiovisual collection have functioned primarily as discrete items of documentary evidence, called up from basement storage to be watched by researchers interested in gaining insights into specific past performances. Similarly, the items' metadata has served primarily as the means by which researchers discovered the recordings. The recordings have rarely been

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² The APGRD (<https://www.apgrd.ox.ac.uk>) is a research centre based in Oxford's Classics Faculty; it was founded in 1996 with the aim of tracing, documenting, and analysing performances inspired by the ancient Greek and Roman dramatic corpora; in 2012 Greek and Roman Epic texts were added to our selection of ancient sources, widening the APGRD's scope. Performance has always been considered in its broadest sense, encompassing not only stage plays but also operas, ballets, musicals, puppet-shows, animations, films, television and radio dramas. The APGRD has built two relational databases, one dedicated to ancient performances spanning the period from the 6th century BCE to the 5th century CE, and the other focussed on modern productions ranging from 1315 to the present day. The physical items which provide this data – programme notes, newspaper cuttings, reviews, photographs etc – quickly grew into an incidental or accidental archive of performance-related material. The APGRD's archival collections now hold around 14,000 items, including over 500 videotapes and DVDs of performance recordings: some are full-length, some only extracts, most are recordings of live performances, but the collection also includes feature films and television dramas; they are a mix of professional and commercial recordings and those made by amateur companies and individuals.

treated as material research objects in their own right and have certainly not been considered as a corpus that might be collectively interrogated.

This paper, whose authors bring together expertise from classics and classical reception studies, performance studies, archival studies, and software studies, describes the initial thinking behind an 11-month scoping project which sets out our ambitions and evolving methodologies, and which we present in the hope of engaging with and learning from the expertise and experience of the DraCor ('drama corpora') community.³ The project is the logical successor to the APGRD's Digital Ancient Theatre (DAT)⁴ initiative for the integration of audiovisual resources into the archive, using cross-institutional networks of metadata to improve discoverability.

The two key questions currently guiding our project are:

1. What aspects of performance - visual, auditory, spatial, temporal, or embodied - can be systematically encoded and compared in ways that reveal interpretive patterns within and across performances?
2. By focussing on performance, what new perspectives can be opened up on the notion of the dramatic text?

2. Methodology

2.1 Thick data

Our methodological approach is rooted in both archival science and recent developments in digital humanities, specifically Miguel Escobar Varela's description of 'data-assisted research' and 'thick data' in his 2021 *Theater as Data* – the former suited to respond to the specificities of performance research while the latter overlaps with many of the concerns of archival practice and theory. We aim to exploit the potentials of computing-based research, but rather than drawing on computing power to make definitive inferences from data, we aim to integrate computing practices into a research model which acknowledges the constructed nature of knowledge, and, in particular, the embodied experience of performance. Turning away from a 'data-driven' research, which assumes a realist, observer-independent worldview (Varela, 2021: 8), we instead adopt a constructivist 'data-assisted' approach in which data and its manipulation serve to inform debate, provide new perspectives, and prompt a mode of defamiliarisation from the objects of study (2021: 10).

Drawing on archival science, we consider the material traces of past performances as 'memory texts' mediating what Eric Ketelaar calls 'social sharing' (Ketelaar 2005: 45; see also Sabiescu 2020: 506). When viewed as such, performance recordings become social tools that can be cross-examined, collaboratively annotated, and, we hope, opened up to computational analysis. In doing so, we seek to address a broader gap within drama and theatre studies: the relative lack of sustained attention to computational approaches for analysing audiovisual data, especially when compared to the more established focus on the linguistic features of written texts (Varela 2021; Kaplan 2015).

Working in the domain of classical reception, we are aware, to quote Eleftheria Ioannidou, that 'unlike other forms of literary reception, the reception of the classical text usually involves the mediation of another text or the original text's transmutation' (2010: 208). Even at their most basic or 'naked' textual level, the ancient plays of the Greek and Roman corpora reveal an inherent intermediality: the long and complex history of the transmission of these plays destabilises the notion of 'the' dramatic text as something fixed and stable.

³ <https://dracor.org/>

⁴ <https://www.apgrd.ox.ac.uk/databases-collections/dat>

Crucially then, our approach does not start with the dramatic text as a blueprint for performance; rather the written text, in its different modes of existence across different scholarly editions and translations, is considered only one of numerous interacting layers that gives meaning to performance.

In our project, we engage with computing technology at many levels. At one level, the project is an exploration of how the qualities of standardisation which are required for computational analysis of data at scale, can fit into a nuanced framework which accounts for the multilayered meanings in performance and dramatic texts – meanings which are actively produced by readers and observers, rather than being solely inherent in documents or discoverable in analyses of their structure. Therefore, we do not only make use of the powerful processing power of computers to bring into reach large-scale transformations and analyses of data which would otherwise be impractical: we also aim to take advantage of the qualities of digital media and computer networks to facilitate new modes of sharing and interaction with research outputs.

2.2 Why TEI?

The texts of ancient dramas can function as ‘boundary objects’ (Star, 1989), sites where common themes and points of interest can offer a range of significances to different audiences, separated historically, geographically or culturally. We seek to test whether multi-layered TEI documents can function in the same way for researchers looking to gain insight into the distinctive features of performance.

How far can TEI be customized to make recordings of performance usefully open to computational analysis? What might the limitations of TEI be when applied to performance or more broadly to time-based media? Can TEI assist us in revealing and mapping the processes of change as dramatic texts are transformed into performance scripts, performance events, and material traces of performance across different media?

Currently, TEI schemata that are attuned to performance details include [7] **Performance Texts**⁵ and [8] **Transcriptions of Speech**⁶; however, the terms in these schemata are primarily focussed on performance conditions recorded in published texts via stage directions, notes or marginalia, and are thus better suited toward capturing the blueprints of performances, rather than the distinctive features of a performance event as it unfolds, and, more specifically, audiovisual recordings of those events.

Our project explores how these two existing TEI schemata may be augmented to create a new TEI-conformant schema that meets the requirements of capturing audiovisual recordings of performance events. Our semantic markup strategy is based on distinct but interdependent layers of performance. These include: the **Stage Layer** (spatial architecture: proscenium, thrust, site-specific, etc.); the **Lighting Layer** (modulation through blackouts, washes, spotlights, etc.); the **Audio Layer** (ranging from verbal language to environmental noise, marked by duration, volume, and re/mediation); the **Bodies Layer** (expression, vocal address, stage level, etc.); the **Set Layer** (including form, texture, space, and cultural reference); and the **Object Layer** (props whose function becomes narratively or symbolically charged, e.g. Clytemnestra’s axe).

Each layer captures a specific dimension of performance. Some, like the Stage Layer, describe the architectural or spatial conditions of the performance and are typically **fixed** across a production. Others, such as Lighting, Audio, Bodies, and Object Layers, are inherently **time-based**, involving dynamic elements that unfold during the performance. Time-sensitive layers can accommodate both **intra-performance** phenomena (e.g. a character screaming, a blackout, or a raised arm holding a prop) and **inter-performance factors** (e.g. ambient/

⁵ <https://www.tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/DR.html>

⁶ <https://www.tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/TS.html>

audience noise or environmental lighting in an outdoor venue). **Meaning often arises at the intersections between layers:** an expression of fear (Bodies Layer) might be intensified by a spotlight (Lighting Layer) or by the actor's location on a raised stage platform (Set Layer). A single moment, such as a character lifting a lamp, can combine expression, object, and light, and must therefore be read across multiple layers simultaneously.

This layered approach is an attempt to formalise cumulative, multisensory expressions of meaning and polyphonic complexity in ways that enable comparative annotation, revealing interpretive mechanisms as they emerge in real time. In doing so, our markup model expands TEI's current applications to include the multimodal, temporal, and spatial logic of performance reception, particularly within the long and diverse histories of Greek and Roman drama in translation and adaptation.

At the presentation level, these layers of performance elements will be complemented by additional textual layers: the performance transcript, the script on which the performance is based, and any translations and modern editions that may mediate between the performance script and the ancient play. Visually foregrounding these numerous texts, with the potential for mapping their points of convergence and divergence, acts as a defamiliarizing lens for a researcher engaging with a performance recording, facilitating reflexivity and encouraging deeper understanding. The contextual presentation and modes of dissemination of our TEI content are thus a vital component of our aspirations for its use.

2.3 Copyright Aside

A major benefit of TEI is interoperability. However, recordings of performance stand at odds with this; they are, for the most part, neither shareable, exportable, nor reusable due to copyright constraints. Nearly all our audiovisual material is under copyright and although much of it can be digitised under our archive preservation policy, what we can do with those digital files is rightly limited (for a discussion on copyright and archiving or documenting performance, see Rizzo 2017). As a closed research team, we can develop a customized shareable TEI schema, but we will only be able to share outputs that reproduce or reformat the performance recording and its script(s) if we have secured express permission from all copyright owners - including the writers, performers, composers, as well as the recordings' production and/or distribution companies. Our project therefore adopts a selective curation-driven approach for all public-facing outputs.

Although we may not always be able to enable large-scale computational research, by establishing a collaborative relationship with a select number of copyright owners, we can offer a deeper analytical insight into specific productions through the inclusion of additional 'memory texts' that can deepen the context in which researchers approach the performance recording: such as rehearsal footage, different drafts of the script, familiarity with other texts that fed into the script's development, annotations by playwrights, directors, composers, choreographers, actors, stage managers, or designers, and research inputs.

Moreover, through close collaboration with institutional partners nationally and internationally, we can begin to link our metadata to those of other research centres, archives, and repositories to create a much wider network of linked data, thus providing useful points of reference around which to explore and compare themes of interest and to pursue opportunities for annotation and interaction at the presentation level.

2.4 Collaborative Interface

The ways in which research outputs are shared, written and consumed form an important part of our computing-based methodology. By bringing into focus the qualities of digital media and computer networks, we aim to facilitate new modes of sharing and interaction with archive

items and our XML encodings of them. This includes foregrounding the malleability of digital data, their rewriteability, their potential for non-linearity, intertextuality and interactivity, and scoping opportunities for new publishing models, multiple authorship and annotation. It is these affordances of digital archives which make them 'potent means for the performative celebration of the past through contemporary acts of creation and transmission' (Sabiescu, 2020: 497-8).

The aspiration to provide support for formal innovation at the presentation level is an acknowledgement of the need for a distinctive approach to designing visualisations for the humanities (Drucker, 2011, 2014), one which embodies a constructivist epistemology. Visualisations are not somehow ontologically distinct from the objects they purport to represent; and that which is represented cannot be 'held to be independent of all practices of representing' (Barad, 2007:46). An effective strategy for challenging the implied authority of apparently neutral, 'unauthored' visualisations is simply to highlight their contingency and show that there is space for alternative perspectives. In practical terms, this can consist of making it possible to represent research outputs in a series of ways, with potential for future 'rewritings', as described below in 'Methods & Tools'.

In a 'data-driven' approach, 'objective' truths are captured and shared, and interpretation or subjective discussion of them often takes place in separate spaces: the journal article, the conference hall. Our attempt to reconcile the use of data standards with a humanities perspective, one which emphasises the **reception** of ancient Greek and Roman corpora in a range of historical and cultural contexts, and is therefore inherently multi-perspectival, prompts us to integrate an interpretative annotation layer into the presentation of our data, as well as an 'audit trail' which, as far as is possible shows how the data were 'made', by humans and LLMs (an example of Varela's 'thick data'), or even creatively performed.⁷ By introducing these features, the 'theory-laden' nature of the research process is made more explicit, and simultaneously, space for alternative readings and interpretations is created. This aligns with a key ongoing goal of the APGRD, which is to develop our resources to be more multilingual and more inclusive of a broad range of cultural and historical perspectives.

We aim to create collaborative web spaces where interpretative commentary, historical contexts/contingencies, and multilingual reception histories are embedded alongside the presentation of data formatted in standardised structures. This includes infrastructural design that enables collaboration, annotation and revision. TEI and, potentially, the use of linked open data, offers the foundations of such infrastructure/sharing, onto which may grow a community of users who contribute to, change, reshape our collection of resources over time. The aspiration is for a dynamic networked framework for knowledge-in-the-making.

3. Methods & Tools

In collaboration with colleagues from the University of Oxford's Visual Geometry Group (VGG),⁸ who have developed a diverse range of machine-learning tools, we employ a multi-pass approach to analyse video recordings of drama-based performances and use the resultant outputs to build TEI documents in a semi-automated process.

3.1 TEI Generation

3.1.1 Automated Speech and Speaker Recognition

⁷ 'archiving is indeed an artistic practice that builds its own performative presence': Batzofin, 2022: 127.

⁸ <https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/>

WhisperX⁹ (Bain et al., 2023) is an open-source automated speech recognition (ASR) model which builds on the OpenAI Whisper model¹⁰ (Radford et al., 2022), adding several key features and refinements which are important to our use case: speaker diarization (identification of different speakers); timestamps accurate to word level; and batched inference for high-speed processing. WhisperX supports a large range of languages, including Latin, but not ancient Greek.

Analysis of a video or audio recording by WhisperX results in a JSON format document in which speech is broken down into segments, which are sentences attributable to distinct speakers, with every word in a segment having its own timestamp and confidence score, based on the model's own estimate of its accuracy in making the transcription.

For evaluation and editing purposes, we run a transformation script on the transcript to convert it into a series of entities in a relational database. These are then made editable via a web interface, in which the text elements are displayed in synchronisation with the original video recording (Figure 1). The database records are ultimately used to programmatically generate a TEI-format document of the recorded performance.

⁹ <https://github.com/m-bain/whisperX>

¹⁰ <https://openai.com/index/whisper/>

Preview of [Transcription 7 \(17924.json\)](#) Scroll Sync On Hide XML

Show audio amplitude per word

<p>ID: 2433 Timeline: ✓ (11.115s) Words: 3</p> <p>Ismene: Activate the city archivist. 58.5s (00:00:58) SPEAKER_02</p> <p>👁️ ✎</p> <p>ID: 2434 Timeline: ✓ (58.472s) Words: 4</p>	<pre></u></pre> <pre><u who="#speaker_02" start="58.472" end="65.217"></pre> <p>Activate the city archivist.</p> <pre></u></pre>
<p>Chorus: City Archivist: Input query. 77.4s (00:01:17) UNKNOWN</p> <p>👁️ ✎</p> <p>ID: 2435 Timeline: ✓ (77.365s) Words: 2</p>	<pre><u who="#unknown" start="77.365" end="78.426"></pre> <p>Input query.</p> <pre></u></pre>

Figure 1. Synchronised web-based preview of video and transcript, including XML version

In addition to allowing the editing of the content of speech utterances, the web-based editing interface makes it possible to edit speaker identities, character names, and to make links to actor records elsewhere in the APGRD database. A series of database 'audit tables' captures all edits related to the transcriptions. This has a twofold function: to generate data about the quality of the WhisperX transcription, which can be used to refine the model's performance in future; and to record human interventions in the process which can later be shared in the presentation of the research outputs, as part of the goal of providing 'thick data'.

3.1.2 Multimodal analysis

WISE¹¹ is an open-source multimodal AI search tool which indexes large media collections using a series of technologies, including OpenAI's CLIP¹² (Radford et al., 2021) model for reading visual content and natural language, Microsoft CLAP¹³ and other audio-oriented language models, face recognition and speech transcription. We propose to use outputs from WISE to help build up those custom layers in our TEI documents specifically devoted to the description of performance.

WISE is particularly suited to matching instances of visual and audio objects, and could therefore be used, with the help of initial human prompts, for improving the speaker recognition results provided by WhisperX, identifying audio events or cues, or enumerating appearances of objects used in a performance. It also has potential to be used to identify timings of camera cuts, extract video recording metadata and read subtitles using character recognition.

The integration of WISE into our TEI pipeline is, at the time of writing, in the planning stage. The analysis of video material will proceed in two phases, in close collaboration with VGG colleagues: in the first trial phase, 40 hours of video will be processed, and the results assessed; in the second phase, a total of 120 hours of video will be analysed. The overall time required for analysis is anticipated to be approximately 1 week. Only after this phase will we be able to assess the opportunities for generating useful data from the indexed content.

3.1.3 Audio analysis

Independently of VGG, we have built an audio analysis tool into the web-based interface for editing WhisperX transcriptions. This makes use of the FFmpeg¹⁴ and SoX¹⁵ applications to respectively extract and analyse audio from video recordings. Audio amplitude data is generated for each spoken word in the recording, using the timestamps provided by WhisperX, and these are visualised interactively on a timeline (Figure 2). These visualisations provide a novel and intuitive sense of the rhythms of audio intensity, both in overview for each performance, and at the level of individual sentences and words and their delivery (Figure 3). This data will be used to augment the speech transcription aspects of the TEI documents, for example to identify prosodic features such as significant silences and emphases.

¹¹ <https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/software/wise/>

¹² <https://openai.com/index/clip/>

¹³ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/project-clap/>

¹⁴ <https://ffmpeg.org/>

¹⁵ <https://sourceforge.net/projects/sox/>

Preview of [Transcription 7 \(17924.json\)](#)

Scroll Sync On

Hide XML

Hide audio amplitude per word

Timeline Zoom: 1.0x Quick zoom: 1x 5x 10x 25x 50x

6207/6207 words visible | Duration: 4630.4s | Amplitude range: 0.001 - 0.156

Figure 2. Overview visualisation of word amplitudes in performance, synced with video

Audio Amplitude

16 words | Duration: 9.7s | Speaker: SPEAKER_04

Related Transcription Words

Filter

Id	Segment Id	Start	End	Word	Character	Speaker	Person	RMS Amp	Confidence	Actions
66	2452	174.445	174.765	Now	Tiresias	SPEAKER_04		0.085	0.73	View Edit Delete
67	2452	174.785	174.965	with	Tiresias	SPEAKER_04		0.036	0.478	View Edit Delete
68	2452	175.025	175.745	re-found	Tiresias	SPEAKER_04		0.081	0.435	View Edit Delete
69	2452	175.785	176.125	hope,	Tiresias	SPEAKER_04		0.106	0.712	View Edit Delete
70	2452	177.206	177.326	the	Tiresias	SPEAKER_04		0.013	0.791	View Edit Delete

Figure 3. Visualisation of time location and audio amplitude of segment words

3.1.4 Other

The VGG has other sophisticated machine-learning tools which are of potential relevance to the project in later phases, in particular visual analysis tools originally developed to 'read' sign language, which can extract data from video recordings related to physical gestures, posture, and the presence of, or spatial relationships between, people. This may have applications in relation to the documentation of actors' movements and gestures in drama-based performances, thus holding the potential of complementing the burgeoning scholarship around real-time motion capture technologies (eg Varela 2021 ch.6, Kapsali 2020).

3.2 Refining the Pipeline

Machine-assisted analysis of video recordings holds the promise of making the encoding of our large collection of audiovisual media a practical prospect, even for a very small team. However, early tests show that the outputs from WhisperX can be unreliable at times, for example when there are overlapping audio events or multiple simultaneous speakers. The model's output includes confidence scores for individual words in transcriptions, which gives us a starting point for checking for errors (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Transcription editing interface, showing option to filter words by confidence value

Part of our scoping process is to test the potential to retrain the WhisperX model by providing domain-specific reference materials (scripts, cast lists) and by using the statistical analysis of records of human corrections to WhisperX transcripts to identify its areas of weakness. The process is envisioned to be a recursive one in which customisations, optimisations and improvements to WhisperX, and other machine-learning tools such as WISE, can be integrated into future versions of the pipeline of production of encoded documents.

3.3 Presentation and dissemination

Just as we conceive of the TEI documentation of performances in terms of structural layers, we propose to present the resultant documents in a configurable, interactive multilayered web interface. This will bring together related materials which provide external context and allow researchers to highlight and explore both the intermedial nature of performances of the Greek and Roman corpora, and the cumulative significations of the layers of meaning in multimodal presentations. At this early stage of the project, the web interface is still at the design stage, but the research goals prompt certain design imperatives: in particular, rather than being a static website, the resource is conceived of as a dynamic management tool for archive items, capable of an evolving, updatable range of interactions and presentational emphases, to allow for situated research approaches to the material at hand. With this in mind, a ‘plugin’ approach is proposed for visualising documents, their mutual relationships, connections to other archive items and for the inclusion of interpretative markup. A ‘Timeline’ plugin allows for chronological depictions, a ‘Map’ plugin for geographical data, a ‘Diff’ plugin for visualising differences between texts, a ‘Node graph’ plugin for capturing clouds of relations... and so on. New plugins can be added as required, and the plugin format is made publicly available as a shared code resource. This makes it theoretically possible for a range of contributors to have control of the

configuration of the material (via their own authored plugins), rather than simply responding to it in a fixed format, of which they may have minimal ownership.

The ability to add contextualising annotation should be available on all resources. An authentication layer is required for the safe participation of institutional partners or other contributors, to respect the requirement for fair attribution and make the marks of authorship visible. The modular approach allows for an expanding set of layers of analytical content to complement the structural layers of the TEI content. Assertions of semantic ‘zones’ could be supported – i.e. tagged sections that correspond not to specific words in the source text, but to broader themes, motifs or emotions. This would expand the scope of enquiry by capturing more effectively the multiple layers of translation that an ancient Greek or Latin text necessarily undergoes, through the inclusion of thematically related scenes, such as portrayals of mourning, exile, sacrifice, etc.

As already stated, our aspirations to adopt an open scholarship model are complicated by the limitations of copyright accompanying many video materials. While we can share software tools freely, we must be careful to limit the scope of our project to recordings for which we have full permissions. This, in turn, may set limits on the comparative analysis of performance data at scale, which is one of the project’s longer-term goals.

4. Case Studies

4.1 ReTAGS *Antigone*

Antigone (not quite/quiet) is a 2019 stage play described by its director as ‘not a production of *Antigone*, but rather a series of responses to [Sophocles’] original play from the perspective of three of the play’s characters: Ismene, Antigone, Tiresias’ (ReTAGS repository, ibali Digital Collections UCT).¹⁶ This production was the first in a series of practice-as-research artistic productions created by the University of Cape Town’s ReTAGS Project: Reimagining Tragedy from Africa and the Global South. The script was developed collaboratively among seventeen performers under the direction of Mark Fleishman, Jennie Reznick, Mandisa Vundla, and SEK Mqhayi.

The ReTAGS project is unusual in that comprehensive audiovisual documentation was made not only of each production but also of the productions’ rehearsals by an embedded digital archivist, Jayne Batzofin. With 572 video files covering the full six-week rehearsal period of their *Antigone* production alone, ReTAGS’ extensive audiovisual collection is an ideal test case for the encoding and analysis of video recordings, allowing us to consider performance as a data-rich object of analysis, both in terms of its core elements (expression, lighting, sound design, spatial relationships, etc.) but also in terms of its ecology which proves both deeply intertextual and improvisational.

Part 2 of *Antigone (not quite/quiet)* features a chorus of 13 performers playing the part of Antigone collectively; we choose to focus on the opening scene of part 2, in which the chorus are introduced, as it exemplifies the rich opportunities and technical challenges of documenting performance analysis. The chorus’ verbal delivery is highly coordinated: an initial rapid stichomythic exchange, that quotes E. F. Watling’s 1947 English translation, leads to a collective recitation that accumulatively transforms one of Watling’s lines into an oral exploration of the culturally-loaded South African term ‘born free’;¹⁷ this then gives ways to collective speech, with individual performers taking turn to conduct the group as they alternate

¹⁶ <https://ibali.uct.ac.za/s/RETAGS/page/home>

¹⁷ In South Africa, “born-free” generation is anyone born after the end of apartheid and the first democratic elections in 1994.

between chanting, singing, call and response, hiccupping and sneezing, as they deconstruct the name 'Antigone' until it is verbally rebuilt as 'anarchy'.

The sound is captured by microphones and amplified in the auditorium, with an added delay effect resulting in echoing speech utterances. The text is multilingual (English; IsiXhosa; Zulu; Afrikaans and Southern Sotho). The performance's audio layer also includes an interplay of silence and pre-recorded sound textures, such as howling wind and percussion.

In this opening scene, the performers remain static: they are stood in shallow trap, (signifying both a cave and a grave); all deliver their lines upwards to a focal point stage left, beyond and above the audience. However, each 'conductor' performs a series of unique arm movements when it is their turn to lead the chorus. They all wear similar, non-identical, black dresses and are barefoot. The stage space of the black-box theatre remains in darkness (which gains its significance via contrast to Part 1); the group of performers are only partially illuminated by narrow spotlights and a dim red circle that falls behind their heads (Figure 5).

Figure 5. A scene from the ReTAGS production, *Antigone (not quite/quiet)*

Even this brief summary gives an impression of the multi-sensory layers of signifiers which make up the performance, the most important of which we hope to be able to capture in TEI format. This is a work in progress. Tests so far indicate that the overall quality of speech transcription by WhisperX is remarkably good. However, the collective delivery of speech utterances by a large number of people is a particular challenge for the model, which cannot identify when multiple people are speaking together, confuses individual speaker identities at times, and fails to transcribe some sections of singing. Loud audio effects playing at the same time as speech can also result in transcription errors. The performance of WISE has yet to be assessed.

In addition to the use of encoding standards to capture important features of the internal structure of performance videos, we intend to facilitate the exploration of the structural and conceptual development of the final recorded performance by making connections from its TEI XML document to those of rehearsals. The rehearsal recordings include: preliminary sessions in which the director discusses the nature of the ancient Greek chorus; more advanced sessions where the choreographer works on gesture and movement, and

documentation of the chorus' development and recitation of culturally-specific speech acts and movements in response to keywords such as 'grief' 'protest' 'lament' 'defiance'. These rehearsal videos could be made available, alongside other relevant contextualising materials, in the TEI presentation interface, in searchable and interactive forms that insist on the indivisibility of the production from the performers' lived experience of 'our postcolonial present' (ReTAGS repository, ibali Digital Collections UCT)¹⁸.

4.2 Actors of Dionysus' *Antigone*

Actors of Dionysus (AOD)'s production of *Antigone* toured the UK in 2017, with a video recording being made of the performance at the Sandpit theatre in St. Albans on October 3rd of that year. Playwright Christopher Adams spent two weeks workshoping with the company before writing the script. This *Antigone* serves as a useful example for how performance complicates the notion of the dramatic text. Performances are often based on scripts that go through multiple revisions: their scripts draw on one or more translations which, in turn, draw on one of the modern editions of the original text. Acknowledging the different versions of the dramatic text that are relevant to a stage production is one route towards producing an in-depth analysis of performance. In the case of AOD's *Antigone*, the APGRD has, thanks to a cooperative partnership with AOD, access to different revisions of the script: the WhisperX transcription of the recorded performance, a copy of the writer's 'final' script, along with various draft versions; and the references used in its writing and development, including the Oxford World Classics edition of *Antigone*, (trans. H. D. F. Kitto, 1962), the online Perseus edition (trans. F. Storr, 1912), R. Jebb's translation and commentary (1888), Timberlake Wertenbaker's adaptation (1997), and Jean Anouilh's French adaptation (1944) in one of its translations into English (1987).

The moment that we have chosen to focus on in this production is AOD's rendition of the famous 'Ode to Man' (lines 332–375), where the script retains the iconic Greek line πολλά τὰ δεινὰ κούδ' ἄνθρωπου δεινότερον πέλει - which they keep in the translation provided by Perseus (Storr 1912): 'Wonders are many, and none is more wonderful than man' - but in a completely reimagined context. In this version, Eurydice, the wife of Creon and queen of Thebes, activates a Chorus of City Archivists by uttering the word 'man', prompting a response first from a computer voice, reminiscent of Siri or Alexa, and then from chorus members who introduce a range of contemporary cultural references (Figure 6). A scan of the WhisperX transcription reveals that this updated choral ode incorporates quotations from figures such as Donald Trump, Margaret Thatcher, and Oscar Wilde, as well as allusions to modern self-help books and popular song lyrics, underscoring the production's layering of classical text, modern commentary, and performance innovation.

¹⁸ <https://ibali.uct.ac.za/s/RETAGS/page/home>

Figure 6. A scene from Actors of Dionysus' production of *Antigone*

We propose to use TEI XML as a common format for selected sections of these resources, as a means of running computer-assisted analyses on the relationships between them. At this phase of our project, in line with the constraints on our resources, we will limit this to analysis of a specific scene. As part of our scoping, we will explore the use of available narrative alignment tools such as BLAST (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool – for its application in humanities research, see Mahadevan et al., 2025) for generating clusters of similarities and points of divergence across of a body of documents.

Innovative uses of the chorus, and in particular, elaborate sound design, present challenges for encoding the video recording of the AOD performance in TEI format. In a reference to modern database technology, the chorus are used collectively at the beginning of the performance to represent an embodied search engine which accepts and processes verbal queries, accompanied as it does so by pseudo-mechanical set movements and electronic sounding audio effects. Lighting is used in a highly choreographed manner throughout, to guide the audience's focus, create scene transitions and help to design difference between scenes which always share the same simple set of props. As with the ReTAGS production then, the handling of structural layers is as much of interest to our research goals as is the siting of the performance and its development in contexts which deliver insight for reception-oriented research. The ancient source text of Sophocles' *Antigone* that the two case studies share brings them usefully into each other's sphere for the purposes of comparison and contrast.

5. Conclusion

In the project outlined in this paper, we scope the use of the TEI XML format as a means of representing the content and structure of video recordings of performances based on, or influenced by, ancient Greek or Roman drama. Inspired by the DraCor model, we aim to take advantage of encoding standards in order to open our resources to a range of computational analyses, while at the same time creating a focus for growing our research community and the digital modalities of our archive.

We conclude that, to capture the multimodal nature of video recordings of performances of drama, additional layers of TEI encoding must be devised and brought into contact with one another. We look to develop the drama and speech transcription modules of TEI for this purpose. Our project is a collaborative one in which we work with machine-learning experts at the University of Oxford's Visual Geometry Group, to ascertain the feasibility of using LLMs to analyse video recordings, to generate data for the construction of TEI XML documents. Automated analysis holds the promise of encoding video recordings at a scale which would not otherwise be feasible for our small team. Assessment of this machine-assisted pipeline of production is ongoing. Early results show great promise, but they highlight the need for an iterative approach in which the human input required for correcting automated transcriptions is captured in detail, and used to improve future machine-generated outputs.

The use of encoding standards to represent the rich, complex textures of drama-based performances is ambitious and challenging. The consideration of which aspects can be usefully and unambiguously captured for the purposes of computational analysis prompts sometimes difficult questions about the differences between reporting and interpretation; between *collecting* data and *creating* data. The extent to which tools and data formats can shape methodological approaches and conceptual understandings becomes a salient question. This is further complicated by the integration of Large Language Models into research methods, models which are increasingly able to bring context to calculation, but context which can often be highly opaque.

The logical and ethical response to these challenges, which are surely common to many applications of computing for humanities research, is to adopt a highly self-reflexive and accountable research practice. For our project, this aligns with the broader ambition to make our archival practice inclusive and multivocal. The experiential nature of performance, the cumulative layers of meaning in audiovisual recordings of performances, and the core theme of intermediality in reception theory, all prompt us to highlight the importance of the observer-specific, user-driven, context-aware aspects of interpretation when sharing our outputs. We propose to draw attention to these issues, along with any perceived biases of our AI models, by embedding our TEI documents in a web interface which, through its interactive nature, defamiliarizes content, encourages debate, and allows for parallel interpretation through annotation, presenting data collection and analysis as knowledge-in-the-making.

The early phase of the project, in which a web interface was developed for the management of transcription data, already demonstrates the potential for the re-presentation of aspects of performance to act as a mechanism for triggering conceptual shifts in their reading. The use of WhisperX to capture timestamps for every spoken word in a performance, for example, allows for macro and micro analysis of the rhythms of performances, and how these map onto other layers of signification. We expect other new avenues of enquiry to open up further as new transcription details emerge, and as the tools for making juxtapositions between transcriptions and related texts are made manifest in the interactive web interface. While there are difficulties related to copyright in sharing some video materials, we take inspiration from the community which has evolved around the DraCor resource, and seek to develop shared practice with partners, using in-depth analysis where wide networking is impractical.

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Sentiment Analysis of RusDraCor with BERT-Based Models: Exploring Emotional Tendencies of Russian Drama and Method Limitations

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Abstract

The study examines emotional tendencies of Russian drama using plays from the DraCor Russian Drama Corpus (RusDraCor). The description of the tendencies is based on transfer learning sentiment analysis of spoken lines, performed using BERT-based models fine-tuned on non-literary Russian texts. Preliminary evaluation on a manually annotated test set proves the effectiveness of transfer learning paradigm for the case, showing XLMRoBERTaLarge achieve sufficient performance on dramatic texts with weighted F1-score of 73%. These results indicate the method's viability for literary analysis, overcoming the limitations associated with multiclass sentiment analysis of Russian literary texts. Sentiment distribution across decades, acts, genres, and authors shows that significant shifts in emotional dynamics align with major moments in the historical trajectory of Russian dramatic form from classicism to modernism. Furthermore, the number of negative and positive spoken lines may serve as a potential genre indicator, while the dynamics of negative sentiment alone correspond to key stages of dramatic structure: exposition, climax, and resolution.

Keywords

Russian Drama, DraCor, Sentiment Analysis, Emotional Tendencies, BERT, Transfer Learning, Artistic Structure

1. Introduction

One way of exploring hidden structures of literary texts is through digital instruments that are useful even for literary analysis, as proven by the existence of the digital humanities as a scientific domain. Sentiment analysis (SA), the method originally used for the extraction of opinions, affects, emotions, from texts that do not bear much resemblance to literary ones [1], has become appealing but challenging to use for computational literary studies [2, 3].

For a sentiment analysis tool to work well one also has to consider the essence of literary text under analysis, and choose a tool inner logic of which does not contradict this essence, since the tool itself constitutes a certain theory in which the material under study has to fit. The sentiment of any literary piece is often expressed in a complicated or implicit manner. For example, in a literary piece it is possible to express apathy through description of nature, for an automated tool mapping the feeling of apathy to “negative” sentiment is rather complicated. Thus one should consider adjusting the tool according to the literary style and idea of the literary piece, genre or epoch under study, which is a time-consuming and completely different piece of work that often can't be done by scholars alone.

Transfer learning using BERT models is a promising solution for analysis of texts written in languages that lack specialized training data, considering the fact BERT models fine-tuned for sentiment analysis show excellent classification evaluation metrics [4]. One possible definition for transfer learning is fine-tuning models on texts from a domain that does not match the domain of the texts under study. Nonetheless, transfer learning with BERT may still lead to uninterpretable results, which was illustrated by Sprugnoli *et al.* when performing sentiment analysis on Odes of Horaces [5]. The problem usually is not predominantly the BERT modes nor the transfer learning but the distinction between writing style of fine-tuning data and the data under analysis. This stylistic distance is apparently limited. Consequently, one should try to stay within these limits.

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Literary genre that is naturally of more computer-readable nature is drama. Dialogues contain spoken lines which constitute direct speech. In direct speech emotions are expressed in an explicit manner. Consequently, it is highly probable for an emotional aspect to be an important feature in explaining the artistic and dramatic structure.

Russian is one of many languages for which the training data for sentiment analysis consists mostly from social media posts. The results of sentiment analysis of Russian literature tend to be particularly controversial [6], explaining why not that much studies exist on that matter.

Although it is hypothesised that a transfer learning approach with BERT-models can yield satisfactory results for sentiment analysis of Russian drama. The possibility rests on two key premises: 1) BERT models have proven to be effective for the Russian language [7]; 2) direct speech, which constitutes the dramatic text, can, to a certain extent, be compared to social media posts. In that case, transfer learning sentiment analysis of Russian drama is the method that will provide insight on how emotional dynamics describe the artistic structure of Russian Drama.

Accordingly, the study aims to:

1) at least preliminary establish whether the results of automated transfer learning SA of Russian drama can be trusted;

2) describe emotional tendencies of Russian drama and what these reveal about dramatic evolution and structure of the Russian drama.

Within the research, Russian drama is studied using the Russian Drama Corpus (RusDraCor) from the DraCor project [8]. The corpus includes 212 plays of different genres written between 1747 and 1947, offering a representative sample of Russian dramatic literature.

Positively, It was shown that even when fine-tuned on non-literary texts, BERT models may produce satisfactory results when analyzing sentiment of spoken lines, as verified on a manually annotated test sample. It was also possible to interpret the results of the SA: the emotional tendencies expressed through the ratio of spoken lines across decades, authors, genres and acts have illuminated certain features of poetics, composition and overall artistic structure of Russian drama.

2. Related Work

Despite sentiment analysis being relevant and, at the same time, not an entirely solved task for the Russian language, there are not too many recent papers trying to address the issue. The seminal work on providing models for transfer learning in Russian, i.e. fine-tuning a number of models of BERT architecture, was done by Smetanin and Komarov as a part of research that included investigation on available datasets and their contents for sentiment analysis in Russian. One of these pre-trained models, XLMRoBERTaLarge [7], is employed in this study. Another notable work was done by Smetanin classifying SA tools and domains on which the method is being applied, highlighting current challenges and opportunities for the research area. In particular, Smetanin describes the lack of formal evaluation, precisely the absence of classification metrics in cases where the tool has no relation to the target data [9], the oversight common for SA-based studies that is rectified in this research.

It is also indicative that even the most scrupulous surveys, including one in the previous paragraph, do not include the application of sentiment analysis in Russian literary studies [9]. The recent paper by Sherstinova *et al.* describes the case when automatic sentiment annotation of Russian short stories implemented with lexicon-based tools and tools based on distributional semantics had a very weak correlation with manual annotation [6]. The results described in this paper influenced the choice of deep learning tool for the SA of Russian drama.

Obviously, even the most advanced deep learning tools do not guarantee interpretable results. As it was shown by Sprugnoli *et al.*, in case of deep learning methods, BERT models in particular, the results of SA of literary text very much depend on the training data, and within this research transfer learning paradigm is not easily applicable, since it showed low classification metrics [5]. It is interesting to observe that without formal evaluation such results may have been taken into account, the situation which Smetanin describes in their survey. One way of overcoming limitations of transfer learning is

Table 1

Distribution of plays with certain amount of acts. N.B.: Plays with no acts and one-act plays are combined in one group

№ of acts	Absolute amount	Relative amount (%)
6	4	1
5	58	27
4	38	18
3	33	16
2	7	3
1	72	34

discussed in the Introduction.

Concerning the “translation” of sentiment analysis results into the language of literary studies, i.e. interpretation, it makes sense to define the meaning of artistic structure, an entity discussed by Lotman in “The Structure of the Artistic Text” [10]. A literary text is often discussed from the point of view of poetics, composition and structure. Within the present study, the artistic structure is defined as a combination of these three sides or levels of literary essence, thus the emotional dynamics is described for each of these levels of artistic structure. In terms of chronological analysis, there are very few works discussing the artistic evolution of Russian drama. In this research, we refer to Bogdanova’s monograph *Transformatsii dramy v istorii. Struktury poryadka i struktury khaosa* (in Russian; *Structural Transformations of Drama in History: Ordered and Chaotic Structures*), where different dramatic structures are analyzed in terms of changing poetics and composition within temporal dynamics [11].

This study addresses gaps in the existing research landscape, focusing on underexplored aspects from both methodological and philological perspectives.

3. Russian Drama Corpus by DraCor

The Russian Drama Corpus (RusDraCor) is part of the DraCor project, which focuses on providing infrastructure for studying European drama, it also accumulates collections of plays encoded according to the TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) guidelines. The TEI standard provides a set of recommendations for representing texts as digital objects in XML format [12].

RusDraCor contains 212 plays from the 18th to the 20th century, including 89 comedies, 29 tragedies and 94 plays for which the genre is not stated. The earliest play in the corpus, *Khorev*, was written by Sumarokov in 1747; while the most recent is Petrov’s “Ostrov mira” (in Russian; *The Island of Peace*) is dated by 1947.

The corpus can be considered representative, as it includes a substantial number of plays. Among these there are texts both from authors that are included in the literary canon, like Pushkin, Chekhov, Gogol and Bulgakov, and from ones that are usually outside of it, like Catherine II, Nikolev and Rostopchina. The most represented author of RusDraCor is Ostrovsky with 38 plays, then there are Chekhov and Sumarokov with 14 plays, the mean number of plays per author is 4.

It is also rather chronologically balanced, for each decade there is an average of 10 plays, with one outlining decade, 1850s. The genre and play count distribution is shown in Figure 1.

The corpus features a comprehensive set of metadata for each play, including information about the author; dates of premiering, publishing and the date when the play was written; number of characters of different genres and much more.

One notable feature of a play that is also included in RusDraCor metadata that is going to be examined further is the number of acts. Table 1 shows the distribution of plays of certain number of acts.

Figure 1: Count and Genre Distribution of RusDraCor plays by decade.

4. Methods

This section outlines the methodology employed to obtain reliable and meaningful results from sentiment analysis of Russian drama. The approach is structured into the following key steps:

1. Extract spoken lines from the Russian Drama Corpus to create a structured dataset.
2. Select pre-trained BERT-based models on Russian text, ensuring compatibility with the linguistic and stylistic features of the target data.
3. Design a balanced test sample of plays for manual annotation.
4. Manually annotate the test sample according to the annotation rules of the selected models' training data.
5. Perform automated sentiment analysis on the spoken lines dataset using the selected models.
6. Perform formal evaluation of the automated SA.

Each of these steps is described in detail in the next subsections.

4.1. Spoken Lines Extraction

The dataset source is Russian Drama Corpus. Each play in the corpus is stored in an XML file. The XML markup has a hierarchical tree structure, and to extract spoken lines, one generally needs to extract the "leaves" of this structure, i.e., the text contained within the *<sp>* element, specifically within the *<p>* tag for prose or the *<l>* tag for verse. The hierarchy of blocks containing spoken lines may vary slightly depending on the formal structure of each play. If stage directions appear in parentheses inside a spoken line they are not retrieved.

Spoken lines are extracted iteratively by acts when acts are present. If a play is not divided by acts but includes narrative segments labeled as "configurations" (marked by the *<configuration>* tag), these

are disregarded, and all spoken lines are extracted directly from the `<body><text>` block. The same procedure applies when a play contains neither act divisions nor configuration markers.

Spoken lines extraction was performed using the *Python* programming language and the built-in modules *os* and *xml*. The extraction code is available in the GitHub repository (see Data Availability).

For each extracted spoken line there is metadata preserved: the act number, the character's name, the play's title, author, year, number of acts, and the number of characters of different genders. The extracted spoken lines of each play are compiled into a single table, where each row represents one spoken line. The table represents the RusDraCorSpeech Dataset. The total number of spoken lines is more than 117 thousand. The dataset is publicly available on HuggingFace [13].

4.2. Model Selection Criteria

For selecting sentiment analysis models, the primary criterion is the model's performance represented by classification metrics.

The second criterion is the set of classes the model identifies. Limiting the set to only two polar classes (e.g. positive and negative) would likely result in a noisy outcome: it is improbable that all spoken lines are unequivocally positive or negative. The consideration of neutral class in that case most definitely could lower the noise. Therefore, a minimum of three classes is considered the acceptable threshold. A model's ability to distinguish more than three classes is regarded as an advantage: it may provide a more nuanced depiction of the emotional dynamics in Russian drama, especially if the additional classes represent specific emotions, and also reduce noise by including categories for ambiguous spoken lines.

Finally, the third criterion: the model must be documented in academic literature and/or its use must be an established practice among researchers.

4.3. Selected Models

The XLMRoBERTaLarge, a model fine-tuned on the RuSentiment dataset [14] by Smetanin and Komarov, meets all the required criteria. It achieves excellent performance for multiclass sentiment classification, with a weighted F1-score of 75.27%. Furthermore, as a multilingual model, it is likely better equipped to handle archaic vocabulary, French insertions, and occasional instances of an old Russian orthography. The model is capable of identifying 5 sentiment classes, according to those present in the RuSentiment dataset: *positive*, *negative*, *neutral*, *speech act*, *skip*.

The other model, Conversational RuBERT, was originally introduced by the DeepPavlov framework [15], which is widely used by NLP researchers of Russian texts. According to the DeepPavlov documentation, this model, in its pretrained version, achieves better performance in text classification than other models available within the framework [16]. In this study, we use a version fine-tuned by the Hugging Face community [17]. Conversational RuBERT is capable of identifying 3 classes: *positive*, *negative*, *neutral*.

4.4. Sentiment Analysis Evaluation

For formal evaluation of the models standard classification metrics were used. In case of Russian drama, the most critical requirement is for the model to distinguish negative lines from positive, and vice versa. Given the nature of available datasets for training sentiment analysis models, it is acceptable to assign a certain number of *positive* and *negative* spoken lines to *neutral* or *skip* class, in case the overall coherence between manual and automatic annotation remains satisfactory. This implies high recall is not strictly required.

These metrics are derived from a comparison between automatically and manually extracted sentiments of a test set from a spoken lines dataset.

Table 2

Test Set of Plays from RusDraCor

Title	Author	Year	№ of Acts	Genre
Hamlet	Sumarokov	1748	5	Tragedy
Coriolanus	Fonvizin	1764	3	Comedy
From the Life of Rurik	Catherine II	1786	5	–
A Lesson for Daughters	Krylov	1807	1	Comedy
Trip to Kronstadt	Pisarev	1823	4	Comedy
You Can’t Hide a Needle in a Bag	Nekrasov	1841	2	Comedy
The Hot Heart	Ostrovsky	1869	5	Comedy
Tatiana Repina	Chekhov	1889	1	–
The Little Booth	Blok	1906	1	–
Gas Masks	Tretiakov	1924	3	–

4.4.1. Spoken lines test set

A total of 10 plays were selected for the test set, representing approximately 5% of the corpus. They were manually annotated by the author of the paper. This is enough for a preliminary evaluation of model performance. This assumption is reasonable if the selected plays are representative of the whole corpus in terms of key characteristics.

To ensure a representative sample, the following criteria for selecting the plays for annotation were formulated: 1) One play was selected for every other decade (e.g., 1740s, 1760s, 1780s, etc.); 2) The distribution of the number of acts and genres among the 10 selected plays should approximately match the distribution in the full corpus. 3) Authors in the sample should not repeat. The selected author has to be frequent for the selected decade. They shouldn’t necessarily be the most frequent so that the authors outside of the literary canon are included in the sample as well.

The list of annotated plays and their characteristics is presented in Table 2.

4.4.2. Manual Annotation Guidelines

The label assigned to each spoken line in the test set was chosen following the annotation guidelines of the RuSentiment corpus, which served as the fine-tuning dataset for both models used in this study. As a result, each line was classified into one of five categories: *positive*, *negative*, *neutral*, *speech act*, or *skip*. The full annotation guidelines are available in the RuSentiment GitHub repository [14, 18].

Since the Conversational RuBERT model is capable of identifying only three classes, spoken lines marked as *skip* and *speech act* were excluded when converting from the original five-class annotation. *While necessary for compatibility, this may artificially improve performance by removing ambiguous spoken lines from evaluation.*

4.4.3. Formal Evaluation via Classification Metrics

Classification metrics for XLMRoBERTaLarge for sentiment analysis of Russian drama are presented in Table 3. The model’s overall accuracy is 74%, which is relatively high for sentiment analysis. However, in this context, accuracy is not a fully representative metric, since our primary interest lies in detecting *positive* and *negative* spoken lines, as they are the most semantically interpretable classes, which means they are converted into the description of the emotional tendencies. What is crucial for the case, where some classes are of more importance than the other, the weighted F1-score is also relatively high – 73%.

As shown in the confusion matrix of XLMRoBERTaLarge (Figure 2), the low recall for the *positive* and *negative* classes is primarily due to the model frequently classifying spoken lines from these categories as *neutral* or *skip*. However, as it was stated before, such misclassifications are partially acceptable within the scope of this study. Furthermore, spoken lines from the *skip* class are most often assigned to

Table 3
Classification Performance Metrics for XLMRoBERTaLarge

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
NEGATIVE	0.78	0.63	0.70	783
NEUTRAL	0.79	0.90	0.84	1906
POSITIVE	0.72	0.51	0.60	277
SKIP	0.57	0.54	0.55	735
SPEECH	0.67	0.49	0.56	45
Accuracy			0.74	3746
Macro Avg	0.70	0.53	0.65	3746
Weighted Avg	0.74	0.64	0.73	3746

Figure 2: XLMRoBERTaLarge confusion matrix

the *neutral*, which explains the poor performance metrics for *skip*. While this reflects a limitation in detecting truly ambiguous speech, it is not considered an obstacle for the current analysis.

The model almost never confuses *negative* with *positive* sentiment. Across approximately 3700 spoken lines, only 15 of such swaps occur. This indicates a high level of reliability in distinguishing between the two primary sentiment classes.

Given this rather strong performance for *positive* and *negative* classes, the subsequent analysis of emotional tendencies will focus primarily on those classes.

Conversational RuBERT performed significantly worse with weighted F1-score of 62%, often misclassifying *positive* lines as negative, and vice versa. The full report is available on GitHub (see Data Availability).

For the analysis of emotional tendencies, the preference is given to XLMRoBERTaLarge, as it demonstrates superior performance in sentiment analysis of spoken lines from Russian plays.

Table 4
Rank and Frequency of Sentiment Classes

Rank	Class	Count	% of Total
1	NEUTRAL	68,253	58
2	NEGATIVE	21,595	18
3	SKIP	18,367	17
4	POSITIVE	7,150	6
5	SPEECH	1,677	1
Total (utterances)		117,042	100%

Figure 3: Negative Sentiment Distribution over Decades

5. Results

The most common type of spoken lines is *neutral*, accounting for more than half (58%) of all lines in the spoken lines dataset. This is an expected outcome, also given that approximately one-quarter of *positive* lines were assigned to the neutral class. *Positive* spoken lines constitute only 6% of all lines, while *negative* ones make up about 18%, stating the *negative* class as the second largest class. Sentiment label counts are summarized in Table 4.

Due to its low frequency, the *speech act* class is omitted from subsequent analysis; however, it is retained in some tables for transparency. The *neutral* and *skip* classes are also out of scope of the current study, although some interesting questions may be addressed regarding their distribution. For instance, the nature of difference in the amount of *skip* spoken lines in comedies and tragedies (Table 5).

The description of emotional dynamics in Russian drama is grounded in the proportional distribution of sentiment labels, computed per decade, author, genre, and act.

5.1. Chronological Sentiment Distribution

Mean values are difficult to interpret on their own, especially considering the model's suboptimal recall on *negative* and *positive* classes. Therefore, focus is set on those decades in which the proportion of *negative* and *positive* sentiments deviate from the mean by more than one standard deviation.

Periods with negative sentiment levels (Figure 3) considerably bigger than the mean include the middle of the 18th century, when drama emerged as a literary genre in Russia and when tragedy was the

Table 5
Distribution of Sentiment Labels by Genre (in %)

Genre	NEUTRAL	NEGATIVE	SKIP	POSITIVE	SPEECH
Comedy	58.6	17.7	15.9	6.4	1.4
Tragedy	39.9	23.9	32.3	3.4	0.46
Not Stated	57.9	19.3	14.9	6.4	1.5

most popular genre. This period also includes the most negative decade — 1740s with 26, 84% *negative* lines, which is the only decade in the corpus with nothing but tragedies. The middle of the 18th century is characterized the lowest amount of *positive* lines.

The periods largely defined by Chekhov’s drama, 1880s and 1890s, are also defined by a noticeable amount of negative sentiment. The 1880s include eight plays by Chekhov and six by other authors: three by Ostrovsky, and one by Leo Tolstoy, one by Mamin-Sibiriyak, and one by Prutkov. Among Chekhov’s plays from this decade, only *Tatiana Repina* has a proportion of *negative* lines below the corpus average. Out of Chekhov’s 14 total plays, 9 exhibit a share of *negative* spoken lines higher than average. The most negative play of the period is Chekhov’s *A Tragedian in Spite of Himself*, with 40% *negative* lines. In the remaining Chekhov plays from this period the proportion of *negative* spoken lines ranges from 21% to 36%, which is above the corpus average and comparable to the negativity levels observed in mid-18th century tragedies, despite the fact that most of Chekhov’s plays are stated as comedies.

The 1890s are represented by four plays by Chekhov and one by Mamin-Sibiriyak. The least negative play of this decade is *The Wedding*, with 18.8% *negative* spoken lines, very close to the corpus average (see Table 4). The most negative play of the period also belongs to Chekhov: *The Festivities* with 30.8% *negative* lines. The 1890s also stand out in terms of positive sentiment. It shows the highest proportion of *positive* lines across all other decades: 8.81%. This peak is present also because of the dominance of Chekhov’s plays.

So far, in analyzing the dynamics of negative sentiment, the focus was set on decades where the proportion of *negative* lines is notably above the mean. Decades in which the number of *negative* lines falls more than one standard deviation below the average are also present: the 1810s and 1820s. This period is represented in the corpus primarily by vaudeville-like comedies written by authors such as Shakhovskoy, Pisarev, and Khmel’nitsky. Another period marked by an unusually low proportion of *negative* lines is the 1870s. In RusDraCor, 9 out of the 10 plays from this decade are written by Ostrovsky.

5.2. Genre Sentiment Distribution

The amount of negative lines in tragedies is approximately 6% higher than in comedies, which is a significant but does not make the huge difference (Table 5). The proportion of positive spoken lines in tragedies (3, 4%) is half smaller than in comedies (6, 4%). So, as expected, tragedies tend to accumulate more negative lines, and comedies tend to accumulate more positive ones.

5.3. Sentiment Distribution by Acts

The negative dynamics of the whole corpus by acts can be described as the one having peaks in the middle acts for comedies and ascending for tragedies, thus reflecting the stages of dramatic action for the genres: exposition, climax, and resolution. The example graph for negative dynamics in 5-act comedies and tragedies is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Negative Sentiment Distribution over Acts in 5-act Plays

6. Discussion

While direct alignment of quantitative metrics and philological insights into the artistic structure of Russian drama remains challenging, any such attempted correlation does not reveal notable contradictions.

The major predominance of *negative* over *positive* lines in a corpus where comedies significantly outnumber tragedies, contrary to expectations, is not too surprising. The effect of comedy does not necessarily rely on positive sentiment, on something straightforwardly funny; it is often achieved through irony, detachment, or the juxtaposition of incongruous elements.

The fact that exposition, climax, and resolution align with by-act negative dynamics constitutes the reflection of the composition onto the poetic level.

Deviations from the average proportion of negative sentiment across decades tend to occur during periods of transformation or in anticipation of such changes.

The middle of the 18th century marks the emergence of drama as a literary genre in Russia, accompanied by the adoption of classicistic form and closed or classical dramatic structures. The early 19th century comedies—as represent a parallel shift from classicism to sentimentalism. Later, Ostrovsky’s plays completed the formation of Russian drama as a self-contained, classical genre, creating a distinctive genre of Russian dramatic realism; shortly afterwards, Chekhov showed radically new artistic model, replacing the old one it with an open, fragmented dramatic form in line with the upcoming era of modernism [11].

The conciseness and formal rigidity of classicistic composition may naturally manifest in higher amounts of negative sentiment in tragedies and relatively higher positive sentiment in comedies.

Most likely, emotional content expressed in spoken lines, when treated as a formal textual feature, can function as a *genre indicator*. That is, sentiment distribution and emotional dynamics may allow us to distinguish one genre from another, suggesting that dramatic structures are being projected onto the level of poetic expression.

The objectivity and impersonal nature of realist drama, its focus on the individual’s struggle against an oppressive, established social order, often leads to the suppression of direct expressions of inner conflict. This may explain the relatively low proportion of negative spoken lines in realistic plays, which reflects the period’s poetic norms rather than an absence of emotional tension.

Chekhov’s dramatic system, by contrast, is characterized by openness and a broader range of emotional expression. With its focus on internal psychological conflict, it represents a unique dualistic form of expressiveness, a trend reaffirmed by this study.

A quantitative description of emotional dynamics in Russian drama from a chronological perspective provides a model that reflects changes in the emotional or expressive dimension of drama over time, in relation to evolving literary trends, creating a projection of the structural and poetic characteristics of the Russian Drama artistic structure.

7. Conclusion

This study serves as a case of effective transfer learning in a resource-constrained language and genre, leveraging pre-trained BERT models to perform sentiment analysis on Russian dramatic texts where labeled data is absent.

The effectiveness was proven by the creation and manual annotation of some plays from RusDraCor, which served as a test set for sentiment analysis formal evaluation. Although sentiment annotation is inherently subjective and ideally requires multiple annotators to ensure reliable inter-annotator agreement, resource constraints limited this study to a single annotation pass, which should be addressed in the future study.

The transfer learning approach, despite working well on the Russian Drama Corpus in the current study, is not a versatile solution for resource-constrained languages, which was mentioned in the Introduction. One can not immaculately model which domains are stylistically compatible, leaving that step for one's linguistic intuition or to an experiment to solve.

The further research on the subjects, of course, includes fine-tuning the BERT model specifically for dramatic texts. The uncovered in the paper was zero-shot approach to sentiment analysis that is now easy to implement with Large Language Models.

Nonetheless, this research presents sentiment analysis of Russian literary texts not as doomed to failure but as a challenging yet manifold experimentation field.

8. Data Availability

Full research data is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/feredl/rusdracor-sentiment>

9. Acknowledgments

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10. Declaration on Generative AI

The author has not employed any Generative AI tools.

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What Does Drama Sound Like?

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Abstract

This study examines how sound is explicitly represented in dramatic texts, focusing on marked audible cues beyond dialogue. Using the German Drama Corpus (GerDraCor, [1]), we investigate patterns of sound usage across genres, historical periods, and play types. To enable computational analysis, we prepare different sets of manual annotations and finetune a German BERT model for automated sound annotation based on the method developed by Guhr [2]. Our findings offer insights into variations in sound usage across genres, centuries, and play types, and reveal surprising differences in how dramatic and prose texts vary in their representations of sounds.

Keywords

German-language, dramatic texts, GerDraCor, annotation, sound studies, GermanBERT, computational literary studies

1. Introduction

Shouts, whispers, and offstage crashes – sounds shape dramatic texts far beyond spoken dialogue. Although unmediated dramatic speech dominates the genre, auditory elements also appear in stage directions, through expressive qualifiers, or as self- or other-assigned sound descriptions within the dialogue itself.

In a diachronic sound-analysis of the German Drama Corpus (GerDraCor, [1]), this paper investigates sound usage variation across centuries and genres. Sound is hereby understood as the explicit mentioning of anything that is / would be audible, and dramatic texts can represent them in different ways: On the one hand, there is the dramatic speech, which makes up the vast majority of a play as the primary text ([3, p. 6]). It often contains attributed speech descriptions of the speaker or other characters. For instance, in Sachs's *Eulenspiegel*, there are character sound assignments, such as the self-assigned sound in example 1 and the other-assigned sound in example 2. On the other hand, the stage directions in the secondary text also indicate sounds, such as in example 3, or they add information on the desired realization of a dialogue qualified in a way related to sound and its quality (e.g., example 4). In this investigation, we focus on these explicit markers of sound in dramatic texts and make use of existing research on sounds originally developed for the operationalization of fictional sounds in narrative prose ([2]), distinguishing between character and ambient sounds based on their origin (i.e., sound source identifiable as character(s) or as part of the identifiable or non-identifiable background sounds).

Ex. 1 “Darum ich euch sehr fleißig **bitt**”(Eulenspiegel, Sachs)

Ex. 2 “Wie du jetzt selber hast **gered't**”(Eulenspiegel, Sachs)

Ex. 3 “<stage>Man hört noch einen **Schuß**.</stage>”(Die Räuber, Schiller)

Ex. 4 “ORSINA <stage>**heftig**.</stage> Nicht gelesen?”(Emilia Galotti, Lessing)

Concretely, we investigate three research questions on GerDraCor:

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i) How does sound in drama compare to sound in prose? The absence of a narrator in drama can be expected to have an impact, particularly on how ambient sound is represented and integrated into the text. We hypothesize that dramatic features, such as explicit and implicit stage directions, or the particular strategy of teichoscopy lead to a different distribution and function of sound events in drama compared to prose.

ii) How can sound be operationalized methodologically in dramatic texts? Following the procedure established in [2], we manually annotate a representative subset of plays to create a training and test set. We then fine-tune a pretrained German-language BERT model for automated sound recognition and classification within dramatic texts. Since the GerDraCor corpus spans over two centuries, we experiment with various heuristics to improve the model's performance on this diachronic and stylistically diverse data. We hypothesize that these adaptations will enable automated sound detection across different periods and styles.

iii) How is sound used in plays across different genres, centuries, and dramatic subgenres? Analyzing the automated sound annotations, we perform a frequency-based comparison of sounds represented in the different plays, filtered by time period, literary movement, and author, to identify patterns and differences in sound use diachronically and comparing the two subgenres 'tragedy' and 'comedy'. Based on our preliminary observations and prior research, we formulate the following hypotheses:

a) Plays published in the 20th century will exhibit a higher sound representation compared to earlier periods, reflecting the rise of experimental and sound-rich theater traditions. b) Tragedies and comedies will differ significantly in their sound profiles, with comedies featuring a higher relative frequency of sounds associated with humor or social interaction, and tragedies emphasizing sounds related to dramatic tension and calls. c) Certain authors and literary movements (e.g., Naturalism, Expressionism) will demonstrate distinct sound usage patterns showing author- and literary movement-related particularities of sound representation in GerDraCor.

2. Computational Approaches to Sound in Drama

Computationally analyzing theater plays is a continuously developing branch of computational literary studies, and has been for quite some time. There is a substantial body of research that investigates questions on drama that are relevant for literature in general, such as the analysis of authors and style [4, 5] or genres [6]. While dealing with such 'general-literary' research questions, many of the works make (in addition to the raw text) use of drama-specific features, of which the exact attribution of character speech is the most obvious. A number of works have been published that focus on various character properties and employ the direct access to character speech, such as character type [7, 8, 9], co-presence with other characters on stage [10], or emotions [11]. The 'output' produced by individual characters specifically has been researched with respect to their style (e.g., in comparison with other characters) [12] or the topics of their speech [13, 14].

The sounds that characters are indicated to produce in dramatic texts have, to our knowledge, not yet been systematically investigated, and studies on the realization and interpretation of sound in literary texts in general remain limited. Existing research in the field of drama has provided valuable insights by focusing on the performative dimensions of sound. In particular, investigations into theatrical performance have explored the physicality of human speech and the spatial dynamics of stage interaction. These studies underscore the importance of perception and mediation in understanding sound, offering a broader, multimodal perspective on literature as an art form that extends beyond the written word ([15, p. 124], [16, p. 293]). From the perspective of computational textual analysis, dramatic texts present a unique challenge. Although they are confined to written form, they may include vocal and performative elements that are only fully realized in performances or audio recordings. This expanded understanding of literature encompasses readings, performances, and audiobooks. It requires new methodological approaches in literary studies to adequately capture the auditory dimensions of dramatic texts.

While traditional literary studies have approached the investigation of sound in analyses particularly

of literary prose, as in the studies by Picker (2003, [17]), Glotova (2021, [18]), Molyneux (2022, [19]), and Foley (2024, [20]), which are characterized by the identification of semantically significant sound words through close reading, Guhr (2025, [2]) offers an operationalization of sound events based on the event concept developed by Gius and Vauth (2022, [21]) to automate the annotation of sound events in literary prose. This approach enables the analysis of sound in literary texts beyond close reading of individual texts. For a comparative investigation of sound in diachronic and synchronic analyses, she proposes analyzing a text’s density of sound words and sound events. She also presents a method for dictionary-based loudness level labeling that can be adapted for dramatic texts in future research¹.

And that is where our research begins: Based on the analysis of sounds in prose, we take Guhr’s definition of fictional sound to investigate the sonic dimensions of German-language plays: “A fictional sound is a sound event with asserted *realis* in the fiction that is explicitly represented in the narrative by the presence of sound words, which are sound-representing content words used in the narrative to provide information about the fictional soundscape (e.g., ‘Stimme’/‘voice’, ‘rattern’/‘to rattle’, ‘bellen’/‘to bark’). The realization of fictional sounds can be represented in more detail by sound event qualities like loudness, which carry semantic information about how a fictional sound was realized or perceived” [2, p. 93].

3. Data and Method

For our investigation of sound in drama, we use the entire German Drama Corpus (GerDraCor), which is provided by DraCor²[1]. The corpus spans a period of four hundred years, from around 1550 to 1950, with most of the plays having a publication date between 1750 and 1950 (n=679). To adapt the sound event annotation originally developed [2] for the manual and automated annotation of literary prose to dramatic texts, we created a set of manually sound-annotated plays, and used this set to fine-tune a pretrained German BERT model for automated sound recognition and classification, as well as to evaluate the resulting predictions.

During the exploratory stage of the manual annotation process, it quickly became clear that, due to the nature of dramatic texts, with dialogue structured by a separation between speaker labels and spoken lines, and the absence of narrative mediation that typically “tells” rather than “shows”, plays lack many kinds of represented sounds commonly found in literary prose. In particular, the separation of the speaker from any accompanying stage direction that indicates the manner of speaking, and its further separation from the spoken text itself, especially as structured by the XML TEI markup used in the GerDraCor texts, presents several challenges for an event-based approach to recognizing sound events. Moreover, with regard to stage directions that suggest how speech should be delivered, it became apparent that these often rely on ellipses: They rarely include explicit sound words, instead offering adjectives or adverbs that provide limited yet pointed guidance for the realization of the ensuing dialogue (see Ex. 4). This, however, leaves substantial room for interpretation. Accordingly, event-based sound detection faces the challenge of dramatic texts not providing sound events as soon as sound is indicated in the combination of speaker indication, stage direction, and dramatic speech act. Even though the speech direction explicitly states how to carry out the speech, the texts do not provide complete sound events as soon as sound is indicated. Consequently, this type of sound indication in plays had to be addressed differently for the automated sound annotation of dramatic texts.

3.1. Augmentation of the Stage Directions

As mentioned before, character sounds coming from characters speaking (on stage) are the default case in drama and marked by the combination of an explicitly stated speaker and the respective dialogue in the primary text ([3, p. 23]). However, in our analysis, we are not interested in the frequency of

¹Due to the GerDraCor spanning more than two centuries of literary drama production, the vocabulary is not limited to the 19th century. Therefore, the dictionary-matching algorithm approach provided in [2] could not easily be adapted to enrich dramatic text sound annotation.

²As of the last update on July 23, 2025, GerDraCor contains 738 plays.

characters speaking in plays, which has already been addressed by several studies (e.g., [22, 23] and many more). Rather, we focus on the explicit indications of sounds that go beyond the character dialogues. This is, for instance, the additional information given in the combination of an explicitly stated speaker and the respective dialogue enriched by a stage direction indicating how an utterance is supposed to be realized with regard to explicit sound markers and sound qualities, such as “ORSINA *fiercely*” in example 4. These combined sound indications, however, present a challenge for the sound-event approach to sound annotation, because the actual sound event, embodied as a verbal phrase, is interrupted by the XML TEI elements <speaker>, <stage>, and paragraph <p>. Consequently, these frequent explicit sound indications could not be annotated or automatically recognized as sound event spans. Furthermore, the frequent use of ellipses for the indication of sound qualities, such as the missing *verbum dicendi* in example 4, prevents the semantically sound word-sensitive recognition of sound events in the annotation process. To make this explicit implicitness of sound (quality) indicators visible in the manual and automated annotation process, we made use of a heuristic that manipulates the stage directions as a preprocessing step before manual annotation and prediction (see Figure 1): Based on a part-of-speech tagging using spaCy’s German language model (de_core_news_sm, [24]), the algorithm identifies finite verbs within each stage direction. If no finite verb is detected, it prepends the speech verb ‘sagen’ (‘to say’), conjugated either as ‘sagt’ (singular) or as ‘sagen’ (plural), based on the speaker information in the <who> attribute (see the changes in the example taken from Hauptmann’s *Die Ratten*, the original in example 5 and the manipulated stage direction in example 6). Please note that this algorithm does not change stage directions that do not follow the XML TEI speaker indications – because they are syntactically more varied, a rule-based augmentation might cause some damage to the linguistic context. Furthermore, it avoids altering stage directions that begin with a capital letter, assuming them to be complete and properly formed sentences. Although consequently, one-word stage directions with adjectives or adverbs that start with a capital letter will not be detected as candidates for augmentation but remain unchanged, this weakness of the preprocessing does not outweigh the advantages of the approach, which ensures the grammatically coherent annotation of dramatic speech with (elliptical) sound events in stage directions.

Ex. 5 <sp who="nathanael_jettel"> <speaker>Nathanael Jettel,</speaker>
<stage>sehr ruhig.</stage><p>Könnten Sie mir nicht sagen, Direktor, wer Ihnen in Gottes Namen auf die Krawatte getreten hat?</p> </sp> (*Die Ratten*, Hauptmann)

Ex. 6 <sp who="nathanael_jettel"> <speaker>Nathanael Jettel,</speaker>
<stage>**sagt** sehr ruhig.</stage> <p>Könnten Sie mir nicht sagen, Direktor, wer Ihnen in Gottes Namen auf die Krawatte getreten hat?</p> </sp> (*Die Ratten*, Hauptmann)

Example 7 illustrates further structural difficulties of the XML TEI files for manual annotation and prediction. The sound event phrase is interrupted by the page number indicating XML element <pb n="n">. In other occurrences, the element <emph> indicating emphasis disrupts the annotation process. Additionally, line breaks, such as those visible in the example, complicate the annotation process, even though they are not indicated by XML TEI markup. All of these XML elements were deleted during preprocessing to prepare the plays for manual annotation and automated prediction. The manipulated version of example 7 can be found in example 8.

Ex. 7 <sp who="der_mann"> <speaker>Der Mann.</speaker>
<p>Gut! An jenem Tage ich, dieses <ambient_sound>**Seufzen und**</ambient_sound>
<pb n="1592"/> <ambient_sound>**Schreien**</ambient_sound> **auf einer Seite** – der Fürst auf der andern! Ich
dächte, ich wäre gerächt.</p> </sp> (*Die Pfandung*, Leisewitz)

Ex. 8 <sp who="der_mann"> <speaker>Der Mann.</speaker>
<p>Gut! An jenem Tage ich, <ambient_sound>**dieses Seufzen und Schreien auf einer Seite**</ambient_sound>
– der Fürst auf der andern! Ich dächte, ich wäre gerächt.</p> </sp> (*Die Pfandung*, Leisewitz)

Figure 1: Rule-based augmentation process of the stage directions as part of the preprocessing of the plays for sound annotation. See example 5 becoming 6.

3.2. Manual Annotation of Sound in Drama

Due to unsatisfactory results from applying the German BERT model ([25, p. 6788]), fine-tuned for sound prediction on German-language prose texts by [2], to the GerDraCor plays (see Table 3), we manually annotated plays from the target corpus following [2] to create alternative training sets for comparison. According to the guidelines, in a first decision a literary text is split into syntactic phrases which were controlled for providing information on a literary event containing a semantical sound word that represents the realization of a sound event. In a second decision the detected literary sound event is classified into one of the two classes, ‘ambient sound’ or ‘character sound’, according to the source of the sound event being either a sound-producing character or in an ex negativo decision an ambient sound if the sound has not been produced by an identifiable character.

Originally developed for the annotation of sound events in literary prose, the annotations were extended to the annotation of reduced sound events found in limited/elliptical stage directions that, for instance, only contain one-word-directions or directions that do not contain entire verbal phrases, such as those with a missing subject which often is the case for stage directions following the speaker indication in plays. Consequently, those reduced sound events were still annotated with a sound class (either ‘character sound’ or ‘ambient sound’).

Figure 2: Manual sound annotation process for training and test data preparation.

One of the main challenges in annotating plays for sound events is their segmentation into verbal phrases when written in verse. For instance, in example 9, the sound event phrase is interrupted by the line XML TEI elements `<l>`. Since, according to the definition of XML, an XML element can only be embedded/embedded but cannot surpass the borders of another XML element, the decision was in favor of a double annotation.

Ex. 9 `<sp who="nerissa"> <speaker>NERISSA.</speaker>
 <lg> <l>O Himmel! Muß ich dieses noch erfahren,</l> <l>Muß ich des Mörders Antlitz doch noch sehn!</l>
 <l>Die Stimme die mir werth ist wieder hören</l>
 <l>Und denken, <character_sound>daß sie jenes harte Wort</character_sound>,</l>
 <l><character_sound>Das grause Todes-Urtheil ausgesprochen</character_sound>,</l>
 <l>Das mich von seiner Liebe immer trennt.</l> </lg> </sp> (Udohla, Lessing)`

In developing a training set for automating sound recognition and classification in German-language plays, we manually annotated 12 plays, chosen based on publication date, text length, and author gender (taken from GerDraCor metadata [1]) and broadly spanning the four hundred years of GerDraCor (see Table 1).

	Author (Publication Year)	Title
Training Set	Ayrer (1605)	Fassnachtspiel – <i>Wie einem Weib jhr eygener Mann</i>
	Neuber (1736)	<i>Die beschützte Schauspielkunst</i>
	Lessing (1772)	<i>Emilia Galotti</i>
	Schiller (1781)	<i>Die Räuber</i>
	Günderode (1805)	<i>Udohla</i>
	Chezy (1823)	<i>Der neue Narziss</i>
	Ebner-Eschenbach (1862)	<i>Die Veilchen</i>
	Dohm (1878)	<i>Ein Schuß in’s Schwarze</i>
	Dovsky (1915)	<i>Mona Lisa</i>
	Borchert (1947)	<i>Draußen vor der Tür</i>
Test Set	Sachs (1557)	<i>Eulenspiegel mit dem blauen Hosentuch</i>
	Wedekind (1891)	<i>Frühlings Erwachen</i>

Table 1

Set of 12 manually annotated plays distributed to separate training and test sets.

3.3. Fine-tuning Across Genres and Other Tried Training Sets

Based on the experiences from [2], we used the TEI-enriching NEISS NTEE software developed by Lemke/Sperfeld/Zöllner [26] to fine-tune a pretrained German BERT model for the prediction and classification of sound events in GerDraCor. Originally developed for the task of named entity recognition, the software is specialized in automated TEI enrichment that goes beyond named entities and enables the recognition and classification of longer sequences rather than concentrating on single-word or token annotation. Also, in other earlier Computational Literary Studies use cases, the software has been employed, for instance, for the recognition and classification of spatial patterns [27], or the detection of gender depiction [28], and also for sound annotation [2, 29] in German- and English-language fiction.

For the fine-tuning of the German BERT classifier, we compared five different training sets of German-language literary texts. The input was always read in sentence-wise, split into 80% training, 10% testing, and 10% developing data.

1. The first training set was taken from Guhr (2025, [2]), containing 65 manually sound-annotated prose texts.
2. The second training set contained the 65 prose texts with additionally five manually sound-annotated plays.
3. The third training set was a reduction to five manually sound-annotated prose texts and five manually sound-annotated plays (see Table 2).
4. The fourth training set was further reduced to containing only the five manually sound-annotated plays.
5. The final training set with the best performance contained ten manually sound-annotated plays (see Table 1). These ten plays were chosen with regard to author gender, text length, and publication date, covering the period with the most plays in GerDraCor to sensitize the classifier for the most represented time periods and language varieties, the long 19th century.

However, while receiving slightly better results, the performance was still far from the evaluation results received for prose texts in [2]. By using these five different training sets, we are able to investigate the amount and scope of drama-specific training data that is needed to achieve results comparable to what [2] found for prose texts. As can be seen in Table 2, only using prose texts for training data (training set (1)) is not sufficient to make predictions on dramatic texts³, especially for the *Eulenspiegel* play. Using training set (2) results in higher scores for *Eulenspiegel*. but yields no difference for *Frühlings Erwachen*. Using only dramatic texts (training set (4)) or a combination of fewer prose texts and dramatic

³As will become clear in Section 4.1, dramatic texts and prose differ in quite a few aspects with regard to the realization of sound events.

Prose texts	Plays
Stifter (1848): <i>Leben und Haushalt dreier Wiener Studenten</i>	Lessing (1772): <i>Emilia Galotti</i>
Mackay (1859): <i>Der Unschuldige</i>	Schiller (1781): <i>Die Räuber</i>
Louran (1874): <i>Fliederzweige</i>	Günderode (1805): <i>Udohla</i>
Reuter (1895): <i>Aus guter Familie</i>	Ebner-Eschenbach (1862): <i>Die Veilchen</i>
Kafka (1915): <i>Die Verwandlung</i>	Dohm (1878): <i>Ein Schuß in's Schwarze</i>

Table 2

Manually annotated corpus containing five prose texts and five plays.

	65 prose	65 prose + 5 drama	5 prose + 5 drama	5 drama	10 drama
Training set	65 prose	65 prose + 5 drama	5 prose + 5 drama	5 drama	10 drama
Tokens	736,970	835,750	237,686	98,780	151,314
Sound events	10,763	11,876	2,896	1,113	1,761
SequEval-F1 ⁴	0.01 / 0.15	0.20 / 0.20	0.01 / 0.23	0.00 / 0.33	0.43 / 0.53
Precision	0.10 / 0.23	0.39 / 0.29	0.07 / 0.32	0.04 / 0.37	0.36 / 0.54
Recall	0.07 / 0.32	0.26 / 0.34	0.07 / 0.36	0.04 / 0.46	0.61 / 0.52
F1-Score	0.09 / 0.27	0.31 / 0.32	0.07 / 0.34	0.04 / 0.41	0.45 / 0.53
E-F1-Score	0.02 / 0.24	0.21 / 0.28	0.02 / 0.39	0.00 / 0.48	0.54 / 0.60

Table 3

Evaluation scores on the test texts: 1) Sachs’ *Eulenspiegel* and 2) Wedekind’s *Frühlings Erwachen*. The first evaluation score is always Sachs, the second Wedekind.

texts (training set (3)) gives higher results for *Frühlings Erwachen*, but no gains for *Eulenspiegel*. We achieve the highest results by using training set (5) with a combination of 10 carefully selected plays that better represents the structure of GerDraCor. However, these results are still behind those reported in [2, p.121] who achieved a precision of 0.67, a recall of 0.79, an F1-score of 0.70, and an E-F1-score of 0.80 on the independent prose text test set.

Accordingly, we wanted to build a training set free from prose data by concentrating on the manually sound-annotated plays only, resulting in the decision for a single training set containing ten manually sound-annotated plays for fine-tuning German BERT – always keeping the same separate test set (see Table 1).

3.4. Evaluation and Error Analysis

Results of the different models can be seen in table 3. As can be seen, the model trained only on plays ultimately outperformed those that included prose texts, despite being trained on a much smaller training set. An error analysis of Hauptmann’s *Die Ratten* (sound annotations predicted with the model fine-tuned on 65 prose texts) revealed persistent challenges: It became clear that the structural characteristics of dramatic texts posed particular challenges for sound event recognition. Stage directions often omit explicit grammatical subjects in sound descriptions, which led to a high number of false positives, most notably the misannotation of speaker tags as sound events. Furthermore, ambiguous phrases such as dense or poetic constructions like “stutzt und bricht und schreit, dann in ein tolles Gelächter aus” presented difficulties for clear segmentation. And also, complex syntactic combinations, such as the mixing of ambient and character sound descriptors in “klopft John auf die Schulter”, proved problematic due to overlapping semantic roles.

However, thanks to the specialized training set containing ten sound-annotated plays, some challenges could be addressed effectively: First, short, one-word stage directions, such as “Lachen”, were successfully identified and classified. Second, the model performed well with dialectal speech, as seen in Hauptmann’s *Die Ratten*, where phrases like “de Jlocken läuten” (“die Glocken” in standard German) were correctly annotated as ambient sounds despite representing vernacular speech. In general, the model showed strong performance with dialectal variants, such as with the verb form “jesacht” (“gesagt” in standard German), accurately classifying sound events despite non-standard morphology, which is

a notable advantage of the word-embedding-based approach using transformer models compared to dictionary-based approaches. Third, the rule-based manipulated stage directions, e.g., “sagt bescheiden”, were consistently well-recognized.

Nevertheless, some annotations remained opaque or semantically challenging, raising broader questions about annotation standards and the limits of automatic interpretation, for instance, when faced with metaphorical or idiosyncratic language.

3.5. Prediction and Post-Processing of the Output

Finally, we used the best-performing model to predict sound annotations in all texts of GerDraCor. For reasons unknown, for 75 plays, the NEISS NTEE software [31] produced an empty output (containing metadata but an empty `<text>` element). As one of the texts is Kraus’ *Die letzten Tage der Menschheit*, we suspect that it is related to the size of the plays. However, since we could not determine why other texts were affected, we decided to leave them out of the analysis.⁵ In total, 649 GerDraCor plays could be enriched with sound event annotations.

To improve the consistency and accuracy of the automatically predicted annotations, we applied a post-processing script that resolved several structural issues. These include redundant or inconsistent tag boundaries, false positive annotations within speaker tags, and duplicate sound annotations caused by interrupted spans. For example, we implemented a regex-based algorithm to merge fragmented annotations. We also resolved duplicate annotations by preferring the longer span and merging the annotations. Other rules include merging adjacent tags (‘character_sound’ or ‘ambient_sound’) split by line breaks and removing one-word annotations likely not to be meaningful based on a stop-word list and POS tagging results (e.g., conjunctions and determiners).

3.6. Sound Event Density Calculation (SED)

To capture how frequently sounds are represented in relation to a play’s overall length and to get comparable data to analyze potential changes of sound representation in drama over time, we calculate the sound event density (SE_D) for each annotated GerDraCor play using the SED measurement developed by [2].

$$SE_D = \frac{T_{se}}{T_{pe}} \times 100$$

The measurement relies on the absolute count of annotated sound events (T_{se}) and the calculation of the estimated count of potential events in a text (T_{pe}). The latter is calculated as the average span length (in words) of all annotated sound events in the text and dividing the total word count by this value, yielding an approximate number of possible events. The actual number of annotated sound events is then divided by this estimate and multiplied by 100, producing a density value that can be compared across plays of different lengths, genres, or historical periods. For GerDraCor, we visualized these values (average and standard deviation) against normalized publication dates from DraCor metadata (see figure 3). The mean sound event length of all sound-predicted plays is 2.9⁶.

A correlation analysis between text length and Sound Event Density (SED) (see Figure 4) reveals a very weak positive relationship ($r = 0.072$, $p = 0.0657$), which does not reach statistical significance at the conventional 0.05 threshold. In practical terms, the density of sound events appears largely independent of dramatic text length, implying that the SED metric effectively normalizes for overall textual size, with only negligible residual influence.

Another correlation analysis, this time between the number of speakers and SED (see Figure ??) reveals a very weak negative relationship ($r = -0.071$, $p = 0.0725$) that does not reach statistical significance, suggesting that SED is largely independent of the number of speakers in a text.

⁵A list of the missing texts can be found in the GitHub repository.

⁶In prose texts, this number is 4.39 [2, p. 216].

Sound Event Density per Text by Year (All Genres, n=649)

Figure 3: Sound event density of 649 GerDraCor plays.

Plays by Ludwig Thoma again rank among the texts with high Sound Event Density (SED), consistent with earlier findings on his prose works [2, p. 148]. However, within the dramatic corpus, a new author emerges as particularly prominent in terms of SED: August Stramm. Of his six plays, four exhibit SED values above 8. Similarly, Hermann Bahr stands out, with both of his plays showing SED scores exceeding 10. The works of Stramm and Bahr are also particularly noticeable in the visualization of the relationship between SED and text length as do the plays by Arno Holz (see Figure 4 and for an interactive version of the figure consult the GitHub Repository [32]).

4. Sound Analysis of GerDraCor

Given the sound-annotated GerDraCor plays as well as the calculated SED scores, in the following we will demonstrate our analysis results focusing on the difference of sound usage in drama and prose texts, across literary movements, as well as related to the drama subgenres tragedy and comedy.

4.1. Sound in Drama vs. Prose

Already in the manual annotation process and the fine-tuning experiments using different training sets revealed how differently sound is used in drama texts in comparison to prose. Pfister [3, pp. 13–14] distinguishes prose and drama especially by their presentation and communication structures: Prose usually employs a mediating narrator who shapes the story and interpretation, whereas drama communicates directly between characters and audience. Lacking a narrator, it relies on performative dialogue (primary text) and multimodal elements instructed in the stage directions (secondary text, see example 10).

Sound Event Density vs. Text Length

Figure 4: Correlation between text length and SED, with the outlier play *Ignorabimus* by Holz in the upper right corner.

Ex. 10 <stage>Während draußen ein plötzlicher Windzug die Äste bewegt und wieder stärker blinkende Tropfen fallen; <ambient_sound>der Vogellärm schwächer und nur noch vereinzelt</ambient_sound>.</stage>
(*Ignorabimus*, Holz)

In particular, stage directions in dramas differ greatly from the way information is transmitted in prose texts. For instance, in example 11, the stage direction illustrates the dramatic authors' freedom to use syntax, writing sentences without conjugated verbs in a list-style format. Furthermore, the annotated character sound unit differs from those in prose because speaker attribution is indicated in a preceding speaker reference. This reference is often written in uppercase letters and may be followed by a colon. In XML, the speaker name is indicated by the speaker element, which excludes the speaker information from the verbal phrase of the detected explicit sound event information. This information is then followed by the actual character speech, which can be interrupted by further stage directions.

Ex. 11 <sp who="uexkuell">
<speaker>UEXKÜLL</speaker>
<stage><character_sound>sagt sich zusammenraffend, energisch</character_sound>; <ambient_sound>Vogel-
lärm wieder stärker</ambient_sound>.</stage>
<p>Sie dürfen das Medium nicht mit seiner ...<stage>Einen Moment stockend, dann aber doch den ihm bis dahin
fremd gewesen, wahrscheinlich in der Zwischenzeit irgendwie von ihm aufgeschnappten terminus technicus
anstandslos über die Lippen bringend.</stage> Exteriorisation verwechseln!</p> </sp> (*Ignorabimus*, Holz)

Accordingly, in drama, we do not usually have regular verbal phrases indicating sound events, as we do in prose. On the contrary, the annotated units differ in that some stage directions explicitly state sound events using conjugated verbs and sound words, while others provide elliptical structures that do not explicitly indicate sound. Through our heuristic augmentation step in preprocessing, we made these implicit indications explicit to provide more explicit sound information for human readers and

Sound Event Density vs. Number of Speakers

Figure 5: Correlation between number of speakers and SED.

machines. One particular case of dialogue that offers explicit sound information is for instance the teichoscopy in the example 12.

Ex. 12 <div type="scene"> <head>Zehnter Auftritt</head>
 <stage>Leicester allein zurückbleibend .</stage>
 <sp who="leicester">
 <l>Ich lebe noch! Ich trag es, noch zu leben!</l> [...]
 <l>Ich kann, ich kann das Schreckliche nicht schauen,</l>
 <l>Kann sie nicht sterben sehen – **Horch!** Was war das?</l>
 <l>Sie sind schon unten – Unter meinen Füßen</l>
 <l>Bereitet sich das fürchterliche Werk.</l>
 <l><ambient_sound>Ich höre Stimmen</ambient_sound> – Fort! Hinweg! Hinweg!</l> [...]
 <l>Muß ich anhören, was mir anzuschauen graut?</l>
 <l><character_sound>Die Stimme des Dechanten – Er ermahnet sie</character_sound> – </l>
 <l> – <character_sound>Sie unterbricht ihn</character_sound> – **Horch!** – <character_sound>Laut betet sie</character_sound> – </l>
 <l><character_sound>Mit fester Stimme</character_sound> – <ambient_sound>Es wird still</ambient_sound> – <ambient_sound>Ganz still</ambient_sound>!</l>
 <l><ambient_sound>Nur schluchzen hör ich</ambient_sound>, <ambient_sound>und die Weiber weinen</ambient_sound> – </l>
 <l>Sie wird entkleidet – **Horch!** Der Schemel wird</l>
 <l>Gerückt – Sie kniet aufs Kissen – legt das Haupt –</l> </sp>
 <stage><character_sound>Nachdem er die letzten Worte mit steigender Angst gesprochen</character_sound> , und eine Weile inne gehalten, sieht man ihn plötzlich mit einer zuckenden Bewegung zusammenfahren, und ohnmächtig niedersinken, <ambient_sound>zugleich erschallt von unten herauf ein dumpfes Getöse von Stim-

men</ambient_sound>, <ambient_sound>welches lange forthallt</ambient_sound>.</stage>
(*Maria Stuart*, Schiller)

Teichoscopy, the reporting of off-stage events by an on-stage character, is used to communicate about actions and sensory experiences, i.a., sound, that cannot be directly represented on stage. In the absence of a narrator, teichoscopy allows the integration of auditory elements from beyond the stage into the dramatic world through their description mediated by characters on stage. For instance, in Schiller's *Maria Stuart*, as Leicester is unable to witness the execution of Maria Stuart, he instead reports what he hears from below, "Stimmen", "schluchzen", "Getöse", through a series of references to ambient and character sounds. This technique externalizes Leicester's emotions and immerses the audience in the unseen event through sound description, bridging the gap between visible action and off-stage auditory experience of sounds in the fictional world [3, p. 206, 270].

Ex. 13 <sp who="claudia"> <speaker>CLAUDIA</speaker>
<stage><character_sound>sagt bitter und langsam</character_sound>.</stage>
<p><character_sound>Der Name Marinelli war das letzte Wort des sterbenden Grafen</character_sound>! –
Verstehen Sie nun? – Ich verstand es erst auch nicht: <character_sound>ob schon mit einem Tone gesprochen
– mit einem Tone</character_sound>! – Ich höre ihn noch! Wo waren meine Sinne, daß sie diesen Ton nicht
sogleich verstanden?</p> </sp>
(*Emilia Galotti*, Lessing)

While the sound description in the teichoscopy example presents a particular extreme case of mediated sound description through dialogue, Pfister refers to speech-acts "impl[ying] an action carried out by either the speaker himself or one of the other figures" [3, p. 16] that can also "refer to the visual and acoustic context" [3, p. 15], such as in the example 13. However, teichoscopy as well as the action-referring speech acts can also be found in dialogues given in prose texts, building a bridge between prose and drama.

4.2. Sound across Literary Movements

Given that the most GerDraCor plays have a publication date between 1750 and 1950 (n=679 in the entire corpus; n=604 in our sound-annotated subset of 649 plays), we concentrated our SED analysis on this period (see Figure 6) and could recognize a statistically significant upward trend (slope = 0.017, $p < 0.0001$) with a particularly high proportion of high-SED plays in the first quarter of the 20th century. In an additional enrichment of the metadata, we filtered the plays by author name and their relation to the chosen literary movements and visualized the SED values as box plots in Figure 7. For the choice of authors, we consulted the list of authors of the corpora d-RoRo [33], and the literary movement subcorpora of d-Prose [34]⁷. Among these literary movements, we observed highly significant differences overall⁸ and subsequent pairwise post-hoc Dunn's tests revealed significant differences between Romanticism and Realism ($p \approx 0.0006$), extremely significant differences between Romanticism and Naturalism ($p \approx 2.8 \times 10^{-12}$), significant differences between Romanticism and Expressionism ($p \approx 7 \times 10^{-6}$), and between Realism and Naturalism ($p \approx 0.0045$). Differences between Realism and Expressionism, as well as between Naturalism and Expressionism, were not statistically significant. Especially, Naturalism and Expressionism show similar results and high-SED outlier plays.

However, since the classification of literary movements is based solely on authors' names and ignores how some authors' writing has developed, only think about the literary development of Goethe's writing, the comparison of the SED of literary movements must be treated with caution. Accordingly, we visualized the SED scores of some authors from this period (see Figure 8), regardless of publication

⁷Romanticism authors: Arnim, Brentano, Eichendorff, Fouqué, Heine, Günderode, Kleist, Klingemann, Moritz, Schiller, Schlegel, Tieck, Uhland, Zschokke; Realism authors: Klemm, Koch, Laube, Reuter, Scheerbart, Ebner-Eschenbach, Wildenbruch; Naturalism authors: Anzengruber, Bahr, Bierbaum, Bleibtreu, Dohm, Ganghofer, Hauptmann, Holz, Sudermann; Heym, Lasker-Schüler, Heym, Kaiser, Kafka, Toller, Sternheim, Stramm, Wedekind.

⁸ $p < 0.0001$; The Kruskal-Wallis test was chosen for significance testing as it compares more than two groups without assuming normality.

Sound Event Density per Text by Year (1750-1950, n=604)

Figure 6: SED visualization of all sound-predicted GerDraCor texts with a trend line showing the meaningful increase in sound event density over this period.

date or literary movement. The authors were chosen based on the number of their plays with sound annotations in GerDraCor, specifically Goethe (23), Kotzebue (21), and Scheerbart (19). We also included the two important authors Schiller (8) and Lessing (12), as well as the three SED outlier authors, Bahr (2), Holz (2), and Stramm (6); and the three female authors with the most plays in GerDraCor: Ebner-Eschenbach (8), Neuber (4), and Gnderode (4). Looking at the box plots, we can again recognize the outlier authors Holz, Bahr, and especially Stramm, who have high overall SED scores for all their plays combined. Ebner-Eschenbach’s plays also show an elevated SED. When comparing them to the other authors in the plot, it is important to note that Holz and Bahr are represented by only two plays each, as are the other two female authors, Neuber and Gnderode, who are represented by only four plays each.

Ex. 14 <sp who="laszlo"> <speaker>Laszlo.</speaker>
<p>... jagt ... <ambient_sound>und ratterert</ambient_sound> ... <ambient_sound>und knatterert</ambient_sound> und wirbelt ... <stage><character_sound>Lacht auf</character_sound> und wirft die Pfeife in die Ecke.</stage></p> </sp> (*Die Haidebraut*, Stramm)

Among the outliers in the ambient SED scores, Stramm’s plays are especially well represented. For instance, the expressionist’s rather short play, *Die Haidebraut* (3,063 words), provides information about the rich soundscape of the dramatic world. For example, it refers to rattling and laughing, as seen in example 14. Other sounds in Stramm’s play include screaming, shouting, knocking, and the sound of a collapsing hut (“zusammenknatternde[] Htte”) or the rustling of the forest. However, with a proportion of 0.3 ambient sounds among the total number of sound events, Stramm’s plays do not have a particularly higher proportion compared to other authors’ texts. For comparison, Goethe’s plays have a proportion of 0.23 ambient sound events among the total number of sound events.

Figure 7: SED of selected literary movements.

4.3. Sound across Dramatic Subgenres

In a last experiment, we analyze how SED varies across different dramatic subgenres, focusing specifically on tragedies and comedies⁹. The metadata file provided by DraCor includes a column, ‘genreNormalized’, which classifies 346 plays as either ‘Comedy’, ‘Tragedy’ or ‘Tragicomedy’. To figure out whether more subgenre information is hidden in the plays’ files, we applied an automated extraction algorithm to parse further genre information from the plays’ self-ascriptions, typically found in the subtitle within the XML element <title type="sub">. This information was added to the dataframe in a new column, ‘genre’. Plays lacking a subtitle or with subtitles that do not explicitly identify the play as a tragedy, comedy, or tragicomedy were not given a genre classification. However, only three additional play subgenre data points could be obtained in this endeavor.

The subfigures 9a and 9b highlight SED distributions for tragedies and comedies respectively. Due to the limited number of tragicomedies (n=6), they are excluded from this detailed analysis. Only looking at the distribution of the red dots, the SED distributions for tragedies and comedies resemble each other and align closely with the distribution observed in all plays. The highest SED values tend to cluster around the year 1900, with a general increase in SED from 1750 to 1900. However, in a closer look at the subgenres in the boxplots in figure 10 as well as a significance test¹⁰ revealed a significant difference ($U = 10,037$, $p = 0.00004$), indicating that sound density differs meaningfully between the two subgenres.

To look deeper into the differences between sounds in tragedies and comedies, we generated a heatmap (see Figure 11). It shows the comparison of the relative frequencies of the 15 most frequent content words (nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs) found in the annotated sound event spans (both ambient and character sound events) across the subgenres of ‘tragedy’ and ‘comedy’. The heatmap visually highlights the differences and similarities in word usage between tragedies and comedies, with color intensity and annotated values representing the relative frequency of each word within the respective subgenre. There is more ‘lachen’ in comedies and more ‘rufen’ in tragedies, but the most

⁹Since there are only six plays classified as ‘tragicomedy’, we did not take them into account as a third subgenre group. For an overview of the SED scores across all genres, see Figure 3 back in Section 3.6

¹⁰Because the subgenre data do not follow a normal distribution, we used a Mann-Whitney U test (in place of the earlier t-test) to compare SED distributions between tragedies and comedies.

Figure 8: Plots of total SED of plays filtered by author.

Sound Event Density per Text by Year (Tragedy, n=132)

(a) SED of tragedies.

Sound Event Density per Text by Year (Comedy, n=211)

(b) SED of comedies.

Figure 9: Plots of SED of plays filtered by genre.

Figure 10: Boxplots of total, character, and ambient Sound Event Density (SED) in comedies vs. tragedies.

frequent content word analysis could not provide further clues on why the two subgenres differ with regard to sounds, which remains a task for future work.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

In conclusion, our study confirms that sound in drama works differently compared to prose, shaped by dramatic features such as the separate speaker indication, or the explicit stage directions as distinctive features, but also providing more comparable elements to prose, such as implicit stage directions and the strategy of teichoscopy. Our methodological approach, based on fine-tuning a pretrained German BERT model and adapting heuristics for the diachronic and stylistic diversity of German plays, proves effective for automated sound recognition across GerDraCor. Our analyses reveal a clear increase in sound representation in plays published during the 20th century, supporting the hypothesis that experimental theater practices contributed to richer soundscapes. Furthermore, significant differences between tragedies and comedies underscore the functional variation of sound related to genre-specific dramaturgical needs. Finally, the identification of distinct sound usage patterns among authors and literary movements, particularly in Naturalism and Expressionism, highlights the nuanced role of sound as a literary and theatrical device. Future work could expand on these findings by incorporating loudness-level annotations, as demonstrated in [2], to provide a more detailed acoustic profile of sound events, and by exploring correlations with performance practices.

Figure 11: The heatmap compares the relative frequencies of the 15 most frequent content words across the two subgenres ‘tragedy’ and ‘comedy’.

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors used X-GPT-4 and DeepL Write in order to perform grammar and spell checking and to generate Python code for data preparation and analysis. After using these tools/services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication’s content.

Author Contributions

Svenja Guhr: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft
 Janis Pagel: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing
 Nils Reiter: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing

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Methodological Consequences of Computational Approaches to Literary History: A Case Study on Heinrich von Kleist's Plays

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Abstract

The position of Heinrich von Kleist's literary oeuvre within traditional literary periods remains a contentious issue, as his texts seem to resist clear categorization. This article uses Kleist's contested position as a starting point to reflect on methodological challenges regarding literary periods. To better understand the potential of quantitative methods for periodizing literary texts, the study employs two machine learning experiments on 634 German plays. The results are discussed using the example of Kleist's plays in comparison to those of his highly canonical contemporaries.

Keywords

Literary history, machine learning, Heinrich von Kleist, computational drama analysis

1. Introduction

The placement of Heinrich von Kleist's (1777–1811) oeuvre in literary history has been heavily debated in the past and is still considered to be notoriously difficult [1][2][3]. As his texts do not seem to fit the usual categories of literary history, attributing Kleist's literature to a literary period or movement has been met with caution: research contributions neither classify him as a 'true' writer of Enlightenment nor have they agreed to label him as Romanticist [1]. Instead, Kleist is oftentimes stylized as an exceptional phenomenon at the turn of the 18th to the 19th century [3][4][5] and his plays are described as an amalgamation of various dramatic trends of his time [6].

In this article, I will argue that the challenges concerning the classification of Kleist's literature present an opportunity to reflect on methodological approaches to studying literary history. In applying a comparative perspective that makes use of a computer-aided analysis of a collection of 634 dramatic texts, I will try to shed light on Kleist's plays and their role in drama history. The underlying goal is to find meaningful similarities and/or differences to dramatic texts of his contemporaries with the help of machine learning. This quantitative approach entails a number of theoretical consequences and challenges. As computational methods result in a deliberate abstraction of literary texts, the resulting models' epistemic value changes: Rather than the literary texts, the texts' models become the object of interpretation, sometimes even the means of explanation [7][8]. This raises certain follow-up questions for future investigations: What consequences are implied when dramatic texts are turned into quantifiable models? What are the underlying premises to make use of quantitative methods for identifying literary concepts? And how does an investigation's scale influence the units of analysis that are used to examine the text models?

My article is divided into five sections. In a first step, I will cursorily sum up the methodological challenges that are associated with literary history as a research field (2). I will then go on to explain my conceptual framework on how to quantitatively compare dramatic texts from different literary

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periods based on proposals from literary theory (3). This is followed by two machine learning experiments (4). Based on 634 plays of the *German Drama Corpus* [9] I will train two multidimensional models: one model to predict the plays' literary period (classification task), another model to predict their year of publication (regression task). To train the models, I make use of stylistic, thematic and conceptual dimensions of the dramatic texts. This is intended to address a desideratum, as periodization has recently "been neglected in computational literary studies despite some early discussions" [10]. In a last step, I will discuss the obtained results (5), compare the quantitative properties of Kleist's plays with those of his contemporaries and try to draw first conclusions regarding the use of quantitative methods for analyzing literary history.

2. The challenges of literary history

As Fotis Jannidis stated roughly ten years ago, literary history has still not recovered from the shock of the 1970s. Back then, scholars of deconstructivism rejected literary history in its entirety as a construction and, instead, fully focused on readings of aesthetically intriguing individual texts. Moreover, a broader concept of literature and a critical examination of the exclusionary power of the canon massively expanded the amount of literature that potentially has to be considered when doing literary history [11][12]. This exacerbated one of the fundamental difficulties of traditional literary history, namely, the need to generalize from a limited number of observations and/or interpretations of literary texts. Based on massive investments in the digitization of literary texts and new analytical approaches that are "primarily quantitative, primarily empirical, and almost entirely dependent upon computation" [13], a methodological debate on how to appropriately investigate literary history has reignited in recent years.

Generally, three reasons are given for the renewed interest: Firstly, scholars argue that the new debate is sparked by a theoretical discussion of what the literary canon should consist of. This ongoing discussion dates back to the 1970s and has implications for our understanding of theoretical concepts and literary history alike [14][15]. Robert Darnton famously described the canon as "an artifice, pieced together over many generations [that] bears little relation to the actual experience of literature in a given time" [16]. Secondly, advocates of quantitative methods promise to bring empirical rigor to text analysis [17][18]. As they commit to validate findings based on a larger number of texts, they argue to bring a more scientific approach to analyzing literary texts than close reading can do [13].² Thirdly, the commitments to ever-increasing computing power and continuously improving language models give a positive outlook for the future of a data-driven literary history. The computer as a "*number cruncher*" [20] seems to be destined for quantitative analyses of massive amounts of literary texts.

Much of the ongoing debate about new analytical perspectives on literary history dates back to or relates to Franco Moretti's still controversially discussed methodological concept of distant reading, which he introduced in his essay "Conjectures on world literature" (2000) [21]. In short, Moretti argued that literary history should neither be limited to its canonical fraction nor be extrapolated from only a few interpretations of "exceptional" literary texts. Instead, he pursued to shift the "focus from exceptional texts to 'the large mass of [literary] facts'" [22]. The underlying idea of scaling, i. e. enlarging the object of study, results in two interdependent methodological consequences [23]. On the one hand, hermeneutical interpretations based on close readings will not be feasible, once a

² Incentivizing empirical rigor in literary studies has also led to strong objections, as it might encourage "the idea that computer-aided approaches to texts reduce literary works to formalistically describable and objectively countable objects" [19].

certain number of texts are to be included in the study. As Moretti prominently put it: “Reading ‘more’ seems hardly to be the solution” [20] considering large collections consisting of 1,000, 10,000 or even more texts. On the other hand, this type of scaling influences the units of analysis. The focus on corpora rather than single texts shifts the emphasis towards infratextual and/or supratextual units, such as rhetorical terms and individual word forms or genres and literary periods. As Carlos Spoerhase has argued, quantitative corpus analysis thus deviates from the typical meso-scale of literary studies [24]: The goal of a computer-aided corpus analysis is no longer to understand one or a few literary texts, be it in the context of an author’s work, a literary period or specific genre conventions. Instead, investigations are geared towards simultaneity and have the objective to “aggregate[] a number of relatively small details into a more global perspective” [13]. In this process, texts are reduced to individual data points that gain their meaning relationally. Thus, the aesthetic value of literary texts is neglected in favor of potentially emerging patterns within the mass of data, which – hopefully – can be used to explain literary conventions and their historical development.

Faced with these kinds of quantitative analyses, literary scholars are confronted with a difficult challenge: How can you integrate the ‘large mass of literary facts’, which is only available in the form of infratextual data, with relevant concepts and research questions of literary studies? Or as Ted Underwood stated: “Revealing a new trend without connecting it to existing scholarly debate invites the question, ‘So what?’” [25] At first glance, the answer to this problem seems simple: You need a viable and at the same time valid operationalization of the concepts you try to investigate [26]. Axel Pichler and Nils Reiter have defined operationalization as “the development of measurement for a given concept”, where a concept’s instances or indicators can be identified on the basis of clearly delimited, observable phenomena [27][28]. The subsequent research procedure can be labelled as a top-down or theory-driven approach, where you start the inquiry with a hypothesis: “Instead of measuring things, finding patterns, and then finally asking what they mean, we need to start with an interpretive hypothesis (a ‘meaning’ to investigate) and invent a way to test it.” [25] However, as I will show, validating operationalizations of concepts from literary history is not a straightforward task.

3. Operationalizing literary periods

In an article from 2015, Tom Kindt states that only two assumptions about literary periods³ have gained wider acceptance in literary theory: Firstly, literary periods are constructions that delimit historical periods from one another, and secondly, they are a useful heuristic to think about literary history [29]. Kindt argues that literary periods should not be regarded as concepts with fixed boundaries, but instead as names, which are characterized but not defined by features. In his view, it is particularly promising to explain literary periods as, what he calls, “‘cluster concepts’”, i.e. by specifying a number of fundamental characteristics: Whether a literary text belongs to a period is then decided by recourse to a potentially long, but self-contained list of characteristics. Taken individually, none of these characteristics are necessary for classifying a text. Certain combinations of characteristics, however, can be sufficient to typify the text in question. Herein, Kindt refers to thematic, conceptual, stylistic and similar characteristics [29].

In the following, I will attempt to show that Kindt’s explication of literary periods is fruitful to create a conceptual framework for quantitatively analyzing drama history. The underlying operationalization must be split into several steps. *Firstly*, one would have to specify the fundamental characteristics that are relevant when trying to justify that a text belongs to a specific literary period.

³ Kindt uses the German word “Epoche”.

In Kindt's understanding of literary periods, however, a specific name (e.g., Goethe-Zeit, Romanticism, Realism) does not simply refer to a bundle of textual characteristics, but to textual characteristics that are determined within a specific historical context. Thus, the same manifestation of a characteristic might result in a different conclusion depending on the texts' specific historical context. This is based on the assumption that literary periods are types rather than classes, i.e., that they have fuzzy boundaries. For literary periods can be understood as permitting not only an 'either/or', but also a 'more or less' approach to the question of whether a text can be attributed to them. To address these circumstances, Kindt adopts two interrelated strategies: On the one hand, he suggests establishing literary periods based on texts that are prototypical for a specific time frame. On the other hand, he assumes that it is possible to identify textual characteristics that are typical (though not constitutive) for a period's literary production, if it is perceived as substantially uniform [29]. While the prototypes heavily influence the perception of a literary period, they do so, – at least in part – because they contain or shape the typical characteristics.

Secondly, the identified characteristics have to be translated into phenomena that can be located on the text surface. This oftentimes iterative process leads to manually and/or automatically created annotation data. It is, however, far from trivial. It either requires detailed annotation guidelines to manually annotate the respective phenomena and – subsequently – train a machine learning model to automatically identify them. Or it needs a validated way to directly measure the phenomena in question [30][31]. In the case of literary periods, the presented process is particularly laborious. It involves several sub-steps. First of all, prototypical texts for a literary period have to be chosen, e.g., based on conclusive research studies. Thereafter, the relevant characteristics and their typical manifestations within the analyzed periods need to be determined. Identifying these manifestations manually and/or automatically in a corpus of texts is relatively complex and time consuming, as it requires analyzing entire texts with various characteristics in mind.

Thirdly, once a text's manifestations of the characteristics are annotated, it is possible to make an informed decision about whether a text is part of a specific literary period or not when comparing it to prototypical texts. While the outlined approach seems sound and feasible for a long-term project, in this article, I will resort to a less laborious heuristic that attempts to reverse engineer the approach. Instead of manually annotating the dramatic texts I want to analyze, I am using the plays' publication dates as pseudo gold standard. Predicting these publication dates based on quantitative methods can only serve as an approximation of Kindt's depiction of literary periods. Using quantitative characteristics that draw on his explication, however, should still be of help when investigating the position of Kleist's plays in drama history. Below, I will introduce the characteristics that I want to implement in my computational analysis. Herein, I follow Kindt's suggestion and make use of a multidimensional approach covering several conceptual (a), stylistic (b) and thematic (c) characteristics.

Conceptual characteristics (a) of a dramatic text can play a part in a wide range of textual elements. I will focus on three of those elements: the play's structure, the play's plot and the play's character constellation. Distinguishing between character speech and stage directions as well as subdividing the text and the performance in acts and scenes is constitutive for the structure of plays. To represent these structural elements, I will measure the combined length of the character speeches, the length of the stage directions and count the number of scenes as well as the number of appearing characters in all the plays of the corpus.

The plot of a dramatic text is made up of at least two aspects: On one hand, it manifests itself in the actions of the individual characters on stage. On the other hand, plot is a theoretically discussed dimension. Looking at Aristotle's *Poetics*, the plot's unity comes into focus. This refers to whether the individual parts of a play follow on from one another stringently and if they are essential for the progression of the main plot [32]. While it's difficult to adequately measure and quantitatively

express what the plot's action is, it is at least partly possible to capture the idea of the plot's unity and, at the same time, a temporal dimension of the plot by calculating the so-called drama change rate. The drama change rate is a measure of alteration in the subset of characters who are on stage in consecutive scenes of a play [33]. Calculating this measure is tied to different poetological ideas about whether and how individual scenes of a play should be connected with each other. Plays that are inspired by the French *doctrine classique* typically follow the rule that at least one character must stay on stage for the upcoming scene. Furthermore, a new segment of the play is usually triggered by a change in personnel. A good example of this technique of linking scenes is Johann Christoph Gottsched's *Sterbender Cato* (1731). In contrast, plays that follow the spirit of Shakespeare adopt a different, more dynamic logic of segmentation. Characters oftentimes enter and exit the stage within the same segment; and new segments can be initiated by a change of place. The new scenery is regularly accompanied by a complete change of the stage personnel. Friedrich Schiller's debut *Die Räuber* (1781) is a prime example for such an approach.

The concept of character constellation describes an overarching structure that represents the interaction between all appearing characters of a play. The constellation combines the play's individual character configurations, i.e., the section of the personnel "that is present on stage at any particular point in the course of the play" [34]. Drawing on ideas from structuralism, it has been frequently suggested to make use of configuration based literary network analysis to capture character constellations in dramatic texts [35][36]. Networks consist of nodes and edges. In the case of drama analysis, nodes represent the characters and edges represent some kind of interaction between those characters. Quantitative network measures such as degree centrality or betweenness centrality have been widely used to identify important characters, either for the play's plot or for the composition of the character constellation [37].

In literary texts, stylistic characteristics (b) occur in a large number of different forms. This is due to the complex intension of style, which encompasses dimensions and aspects such as culture, morality, meaning, individuality, sociality, plot, holism and more [38]. In computational literary studies, stylometry has long been used to capture 'stylistic' markers in literary texts, e.g., to determine the authorship of a text [39]. Stylometric analyses are based on word frequencies. Therefore, they only cover a small part of the characteristics that are referred to as style. As stylometric markers have shown to be powerful discriminators [40], I will still use them for my analysis. I will supplement them, though, with two additional measures to capture different stylistic attributes: Looking at the character speech, I will determine the average utterance length and the type-token ratio.

Precisely locating a play's thematic characteristics (c) on the text surface is oftentimes a rather difficult task [41], even for human readers. For thematic characteristics are frequently linked to rather abstract concepts. In Kleist's plays, for instance, the question of trust serves as an important abstract concept of aboutness [42]. One method, which is commonly used in computational literary studies to – in a broader sense – identify semantic structures in larger text corpora through word collocations, is topic modeling [43]. I will make use of a simple LDA topic model [44] trained on the *German Drama Corpus*. The resulting 30 Topics serve as a heuristic to include thematic characteristics in my analyses.

Table 1 gives an overview of all characteristics and their implementation:

Table 1

Frequency of Special Characters

Characteristics	Dimensions	Implementation	Measures
Conceptual Characteristics (a)	Structure	Elements derived from TEI encoded dramatic texts	Combined length of character speech (in tokens); Combined length of stage directions (in tokens); Number of appearing characters
	Plot	Drama change rate to capture one aspect of the unity of plot	Hamming distance (mean, sd); Modified Levenshtein distance (mean, sd)
	Character Constellation	Co-Occurrence Networks based on character configuration (from TEI encoded dramatic texts)	Degree; Weighted Degree; Betweenness Centrality; Closeness Centrality; Path Length; Density
Stylistic Characteristics (b)	Stylometry	Bag of words, 1000 most frequent words;	z-scores of relative frequencies;
	Peculiarities of character speech	Complexity of vocabulary; Length of character speech	Average type-token ratio (per 1000 tokens); Average utterance length (in tokens)
Thematic Characteristics (c)	Topic Modeling	LDA with Gibbs-sampling, 30 topics. Preprocessing: Texts divided into segments of 1000 tokens, only nouns, adjectives and verbs as pos; lemmatizing, lowercasing, stopwords removed	Posterior probability of topics T1–T30

4. Experiments

As indicated earlier, one of the great promises of computational methods is to analyze large text corpora that cannot be systematically examined by reading the texts individually. For the following analyses, I make use of 727 dramatic texts of the *German Drama Corpus*. Figure 1 shows the number of texts per decade. The metadata of the *German Drama Corpus* includes the plays' year of publication and/or the year they were first performed on stage. The figure illustrates that the core of the corpus is located between the years 1730 and 1930. Since the corpus consists of only a few plays that were published before 1700, I excluded them for the upcoming experiments. I also removed plays that are either shorter than 2000 words in length or consist of only one scene, as some of the measures (network metrics, drama change rate) are pointless without segmentation. In the end, the corpus I used for the experiments consisted of 634 plays, written by 267 authors.

Figure 1: Number of plays that are contained in the *German Drama Corpus* per decade (1500 to 1950).

To better understand Kleist’s position in drama history, I will perform two machine learning experiments. The first experiment is designed as a classification task. Based on the publication dates of the plays, I chose four time periods that serve as a heuristic:

- 1730 to 1785 (142 plays)
- 1786 to 1832 (194 plays)
- 1833 to 1881 (137 plays)
- 1882 to 1940 (161 plays)

I did some experiments with more and – in terms of the time span – narrower periods. But in the end, I opted for only four periods, as it allowed me to still have decently sized classes. The periods are loosely based on important turning points in literary history, namely enlightenment, Goethezeit, realism and literary modernism [45]. Oftentimes, though, there are no clear cut-off points between literary periods or movements.

As Kindt specifically argues that literary periods should not be regarded as fixed classes, but instead as types with fuzzy boundaries, using a classification task to identify these periods might seem counterintuitive. Predicting the periods, however, is not the ultimate goal of this experiment. The classification task rather serves as an indicator, whether the chosen quantitative characteristics actually capture statistically relevant differences in dramatic texts that were produced within a limited time frame. The four periods, though, have pretty large temporal dimensions. Thus, they can include several literary (sub-)movements that sometimes might even cross the periods’ boundaries. The time frame from 1730 to 1785, for instance, includes plays that are attributed to early enlightenment, enlightenment, ‘Sturm und Drang’ and Weimar classicism. Therefore, it is neither expected nor desirable to have perfect or near perfect classification results.

The results listed in Table 2 seem reasonable and meet the aforementioned expectations. The best F1 scores of each heuristic period range from 0.667 (1833–1881) to 0.849 (1882–1940). In general, the two compared algorithms, i. e., Random Forest and Linear Support Vector Machine, achieve similar performances. In most cases, the models using Random Forest perform slightly better in

comparison. Unsurprisingly, full models making use of all the previously explained textual characteristics perform best. Comparing Models that predict the literary periods based on network metrics alone perform substantially worse than those using topics or stylometric features. Thus, the results suggest that topics are particularly useful in predicting the class membership.

Table 2

Classification Results per class: four-label task, 5-fold cross validation, 10 repeats, smote-sampling; two models: Linear Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest (RF); evaluation metrics: Precision (P), Recall (R), F1 score.

Model	1730–1785			1786–1832			1833–1881			1882–1940		
	P	R	F1									
Majority Baseline	-	-	-	.306	1	.469	-	-	-	-	-	-
RF (Network metrics)	.357	.428	.389	.344	.304	.323	.314	.305	.309	.445	.441	.443
RF (Topics T1–T30)	.771	.802	.786	.671	.678	.674	.606	.556	.580	.787	.804	.795
RF (Stylo S1–S20)	.651	.661	.656	.593	.642	.617	.600	.526	.560	.761	.757	.759
RF (full model)	.789	.801	.795	.699	.729	.714	.686	.648	.667	.857	.842	.849
SVM (Network metrics)	.351	.476	.404	.372	.205	.264	.297	.251	.272	.396	.538	.456
SVM (Topics T1–T30)	.749	.829	.787	.677	.590	.630	.542	.552	.547	.770	.805	.787
SVM (Stylo S1–S20)	.605	.716	.656	.616	.489	.545	.509	.550	.529	.712	.725	.719
SVM (full model)	.790	.829	.809	.697	.666	.681	.612	.625	.619	.830	.824	.827

Looking at Kleist’s seven plays in the analyzed corpus, the quality of the predictions varies: The final Random Forest model using all characteristics correctly classifies *Amphityon*, *Penthesilea* and *Die Hermannsschlacht*, but falsely predicts *Die Familie Schroffenstein*, *Der zerbrochne Krug* and *Das Käthchen von Heilbronn* to belong to the period from 1833 to 1881. *Prinz Friedrich von Homburg* is a bit of a mixed bag with seven repetitions correctly classifying the play, while three repetitions also predict the later time frame. The results show that with the chosen approach at least three of Kleist’s plays do not seem to fit the literary period they were written in. Interestingly, all three of these plays were placed within the same class and, thus, are deemed newer than they are.

The second experiment tries to directly predict the year the 634 plays have been released in or were staged for the first time. To do so, I make use of regression analysis. This approach avoids two problems of the classification task: Firstly, you do not have to decide on start and end points to determine a time frame that takes on the heuristic role of a literary period. Hence, plays located close to the boundaries that could have been reasonably assigned to either of the two periods, are not an issue anymore.⁴ Secondly, you are not limited to choosing a specific and – in my case – relatively small number of periods because of data representation and sparsity concerns. Directly predicting the publication dates, however, still does not solve the issue that my experiments follow a mostly “‘extensional’ approach” to drama history, as I only use “‘intensional’ aspects” to automatically reproduce a given extension [46], and not to assign plays to the extension in the first place. Predicting the publication date of the plays might be a better suited task than predicting a time frame based on those publication dates, but it is not sufficient to determine a play’s literary period. So instead of assigning the literary period the plays belong to, this second experiment asks how typical a play is for the time it was written in with regard to its quantitative characteristics.

⁴ See the argument of Köppe and Gittel regarding extensional and intensional aspects of literary concepts

Table 3

Regression model predicting year of publication: 5-fold cross validation, 10 repeats; three methods: Linear Regression (LR), Linear Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF); evaluation metrics: Root mean squared error (RMSE), Mean absolute error (MAE), R^2 .

Model	RMSE	MAE	R^2
Baseline (mean years)	52.7	44.7	-
LR (full model)	27.0	20.9	0.74
SVM (full model)	27.7	21.5	0.72
RF (full model)	26.2	20.4	0.75

Table 3 lists the results of the experiment. All tested models perform roughly the same. On average, the predictions are about 21 years off (MAE 20.4 to 21.5). The differences between the RMSE and MAE values suggest that there are quite a few heavy outliers, where the models perform particularly poorly. To further inspect this, Table 4 lists the dramatic texts with the lowest and highest absolute error. It shows that some predictions are indeed way off. It also shows that the five plays, in which the model (RF) performed worst, all stem from the late 19th or early 20th century. Furthermore, Table 4 includes the seven plays written by Kleist and their absolute errors. The values match the results of the classification task: Out of the seven plays, the years of publication of *Der zerbrochne Krug* (26.80), *Das Käthchen von Heilbronn* (30.12) and – especially – *Die Familie Schroffenstein* (43.65) seem to be the hardest to predict. For all of Kleist's plays, the model consistently predicts a publication date that is later than the actual year, the texts were written in. From this, one could hypothesize that Kleist's dramatic texts could have served as model or inspiration for the following generation of playwrights. I cannot, however, pursue this hypothesis in more detail here.

Table 4

Mean predicted year (\varnothing p. Year) and mean absolute error (\varnothing abs. Err.) for the best and worst predictions of the regression analysis (RF).

No.	Author	Play	Year	\varnothing p. Year	\varnothing abs. Err.
1	A. Bäuerle	Doktor Faust's Mantel	1817	1815.7	2.00
2	J. Weißenthurn	Johann, Herzog von Finnland	1811	1812.0	2.31
3	K. Holtei	Die Kalkbrenner	1825	1824.1	2.54
4	A. W. Iffland	Das Erbtheil des Vaters	1802	1803.9	2.56
5	F. Grillparzer	Weh dem, der lügt!	1838	1838.8	2.78
...					
185	H. Kleist	Die Hermannsschlacht	1808	1814.4	10.25
349	H. Kleist	Amphitryon	1803	1822.5	19.54
372	H. Kleist	Prinz Friedrich von Homburg	1810	1831.3	21.40
425	H. Kleist	Penthesilea	1808	1832.8	24.76
452	H. Kleist	Der zerbrochne Krug	1808	1834.8	26.80
487	H. Kleist	Das Käthchen von Heilbronn	1810	1840.1	30.12
578	H. Kleist	Die Familie Schroffenstein	1802	1845.7	43.65
...					
630	B. Ertler	Das Spiel von Doktor Faust	1922	1847.0	74.97
631	W. Schaefer	Faustine, der weibliche Faust	1898	1820.7	77.32
632	J. Kupelwieser	Fierrabras	1897	1806.4	90.65
633	H. Hofmannsthal	Die Frau im Fenster	1897	1805.3	91.70
634	K. Kraus	Die letzten Tage der Menschheit	1919	1790.8	128.23

5. Discussion

To take a closer look at Kleist's dramatic texts, I will compare his plays with those of four highly canonical contemporaries of his, namely Gotthold Ephraim Lessing (1729–1781), Johann Wolfgang von Goethe (1749–1832), Friedrich Schiller (1759–1805) and Franz Grillparzer (1791–1872). While the results in Table 4 suggested that the trained models struggle with predicting the publication date of Kleist's plays, the boxplots in Figure 2 put things into perspective. They visualize the absolute errors of the Random Forest model for Kleist, Lessing, Goethe, Schiller and Grillparzer. While the median for Kleist's plays is substantially higher than the median of all 634 plays (red dots), the publication years of Goethe's and Schiller's dramatic texts seem even harder to predict. One possible explanation lies in Kleist's rather short creative period. He wrote all his plays in a time span of less than ten years. In Goethe's case, on the other hand, more than 50 years separated his first from his last play.

Figure 2: Boxplots representing the absolute errors for plays of Lessing (12 plays), Goethe (16 plays), Schiller (11 plays), Kleist (7 plays) and Grillparzer (12 plays); the red dots represent the median absolute error of all 634 plays.

Figure 3 allows to have a closer look at the quantitative characteristics that I used to train the machine learning models. The figure visualizes the feature (or variable) importance of the Random Forest model used for the regression analysis. Variable importance is a measure that quantifies how 'important' a feature is for the model to come to a decision. 'Importance' is calculated by shuffling a feature's values to see how it influences the error rate of the model. The more the error rate increases, the more important the feature is for the prediction [47][48]. The values in Figure 3 indicate that topics (especially T 30, T 13 and T 17) and stylistic features (especially S 2, S 1 and S 12) are way more important for the model's prediction than network metrics. Degree, Weighted Degree, Density and so forth can all be found towards the bottom of the ranking. This corresponds to the results of the classification task, where the models relying on topics and stylistic features outperformed the one using network metrics.

Figure 3: Feature (or variable) importance of the Random Forest regression model.

Finally, I will have a closer look at two of the quantitative characteristics which were used to train the machine learning models: Firstly, Topic 30, which has the biggest influence on the models' performance according to the calculated feature importance. And secondly, the average utterance length of the dramatic characters'. Utterance length is one of only a few attributes of literary texts that is pretty much exclusive to drama analysis. At the same time, the feature importance lists the average utterance length as the first characteristic that does not stem from either topic modeling or stylometry.

Figure 4: Posterior probability of Topic 30 in 634 plays; in red: LOESS curve (degree = 1, span = 1/3), confidence interval (95%).

Figure 5: Boxplots representing the posterior probability of Topic 30 in the plays of Lessing, Goethe, Schiller, Kleist and Grillparzer.

Unfortunately, Topic 30 is not a straightforward topic to interpret. The ten most probable words of the topic are ‘professor’, ‘doktor’, ‘jahr’, ‘letzer’, ‘fall’, ‘sache’, ‘grund’, ‘direktor’, ‘verstehen’ und ‘moment’. It appears that two thematic areas might overlap in Topic 30: one that refers to characters from academia, and one with a focus on criminal cases or riddles. The diachronic analysis in Figure 4

shows a clear prevalence of Topic 30 in plays that were written in the late 19th and the early 20th century. From 1730 till about 1830 the values of the smoothing curve lie between 0.01 and 0.02. From then on, they start to slowly rise. The plays of Lessing, Goethe, Schiller, Kleist and Grillparzer fit into this pattern (see Figure 5). In comparison, Kleist's texts have a slightly higher median than those of the other four authors. The same holds true for the lower and upper whiskers. The differences are so small, though, that they do not serve as an indicator of Kleist's presumed status as exceptional phenomenon of the early 19th century.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 shift attention towards the average utterance length of dramatic characters as a potentially fruitful unit of analysis for studying drama history. Figure 6 shows that the values undergo a diachronic change. Generally speaking, the utterance length decreases until the year 1800 according to the smoothing curve. From there on it stays on a relatively stable level with a slight rise after 1870. By 1900, another dip in the values is recognizable.

The Boxplots in Figure 7 reveal some instructive patterns. While the box and whiskers that represent Goethe's plays suggest that he experimented with quite different ideas on how to compose character speech and dialogues, the plays of Grillparzer, Schiller and especially Kleist seem to follow a stricter or more uniform set of (implicit) regulations. Schiller's plays are shown to have a median that is well below the median of all 634 plays (17.97). They also have by far the lowest average utterance length of the plays represented in Figure 7. The values of Kleist's plays are similar to those of Grillparzer but lie within even narrower limits. For Kleist, this raises the question of whether a uniform concept and/or style in his composition of the characters' speech is typical or even indicative for his plays.

Figure 6: Values of the characters' average utterance length in 634 plays; in red: LOESS curve (degree = 1, span = 1/3), confidence interval (95%).

Figure 7: Boxplots representing the characters' average utterance in the plays of Lessing, Goethe, Schiller, Kleist and Grillparzer.

6. Outlook

While both the classification and the regression task yield promising results, they can only serve as a first step. With respect to my research questions, two main challenges have emerged that still remain. Firstly, a play's year of publication is no theoretical concept that guides interpretations – be it of the dramatic text itself or of the text's relation to other texts or authors. Instead, it serves either as an indicator for literary periods or helps in choosing adequate contexts. Secondly, regarding the question on Kleist's placement in literary history further research is needed to give an adequate answer. Although the analyses have brought to light some interesting details about Kleist's plays. The quantitative results alone, however, are not conclusive enough to derive that Kleist's dramatic texts have played a pioneering role or represent a singular case in the early 19th century. More in-depth analysis is needed here.

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